

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**AI-Driven Self-Optimisation of Network
Control Functions in multi-tenant
Beyond 5G Networks**

Jimena Andrade Hoz

Supervisors: Professor Jose Maria Alcaraz Calero

Professor Qi Wang

School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences (CEPS)

University of the West of Scotland (UWS)

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific references that are made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements.

Jimena Andrade Hoz

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The presented thesis, has been funded by two large European Commission research projects.

- **Project 1:**

Project Title	ARCADIAN-IoT (Autonomous trust, security and privacy management framework for IoT) [1]
Horizon Call Topic Type of action Duration Start date	H2020-SU-DS02-2020 Intelligent security and privacy management Research and Innovation Action (RIA) 36 months 01/05/2021
Description	ARCADIAN-IoT, the acronym for Autonomous trust, security and privacy management framework for IoT, is an EC-funded project which aims to develop innovative and advanced security and privacy management mechanisms and technologies that can seamlessly be integrated in a variety of contexts and applications. The ARCADIAN-IoT project addresses the challenge of ensuring that the digitisation and technological transformation benefits all citizens in a way that warrants security and privacy. The ARCADIAN-IoT framework will accelerate the development of IoT systems towards decentralized, transparent and user controllable privacy in three real use cases.
Partners	University of the West of Scotland (UK) Instituto Pedro Nunes (POR) Atos (ES) E-Lex (ITA) Load (POR) Martel Innovate (SWI) RGB (ES) Rise (SWE) Box2m (ROM) Thuphone (POR) Universidad de Navarra (ES) Xlab (SLO)

- **Project 2:**

Project Title	RIGOUROUS (secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsth-woRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services) [2]
Horizon Call Topic Type of action Duration Start date	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022 Secure Service development and Smart Security Research and Innovation Action (RIA) 36 months 01/01/2023
Description	The onset of 6G (sixth-generation wireless) technologies has reaffirmed the need for improved and efficient security and privacy when these technologies finally arrive. The EU-funded RIGOUROUS project aims to improve the security, privacy and trust present in both 6G and other novel computing technologies and services. It aspires to identify and address the major cyber-security, trust and privacy risks threatening the network, devices, computing infrastructure, and next generation of services. To do so, it will develop an innovative smart service framework that will make software and AI parts comply with security requirements throughout their development and up to launch while detecting and stopping security breaches. The project is also researching possibilities to improve the secure and efficient automation of security management.
Partners	University of the West of Scotland (UK) Universidad de Murcia (ES) Orange (ROM) Lenovo (DEU) eBOS (CYPR) Rhea Group (LUX) Wings ICT solutions (GR) University of Oulu (FIN) OneSource (POR) Instituto de Telecomunicações (POR) ICTFICIAL OY (FIN)

The research work carried out in this thesis has resulted in a detailed set of outcomes listed below. These include a total of four publications as first author including two journal articles and two conference papers.

- **Outcome 1 (Journal):**

Journal	Journal of Communications and Networks
Title	NetLabeller: Architecture with data extraction and labelling framework for beyond 5G networks [3]
Authors	Jimena Andrade-Hoz Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero Qi Wang
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	3.6
Volume	26
Issue	February 2024
Pages	80-98
Year of Publication	2024
DOI	10.23919/JCN.2023.000063
URL	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10459140
Contribution	The contribution of this research work is multi-fold. First an analysis of the most relevant metrics in terms of network control to create a training dataset for future AI development purposes is developed. Additionally, it presents a new data extraction framework able to compile real-time network-related datasets from the most novel networks available today, specifically from beyond 5G networks. This data extraction framework is complemented in a tailored labelling tool specially designed to perform the visualisation and labelling of network-related datasets.

- **Outcome 2 (Journal):**

Journal	Sensors
Title	Infrastructure-Wide and Intent-Based Networking Dataset for 5G-and-beyond AI-Driven Autonomous Networks [4]
Authors	Jimena Andrade-Hoz Qi Wang Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	3.4
Volume Issue Year of Publication DOI URL	24 January 2024 2024 10.3390/s24030783 https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/24/3/783
Contribution	In this research work, a new networking dataset called the IW-IB-5GNET is presented. It is an infrastructure-wide and intent-based dataset, which is intended to be of use in research and development of network management and optimisation solutions in 5G and beyond networks. It is infrastructure-wide as the dataset includes information from all layers of the 5G network. It is also intent-based as it is initiated based on predefined user-intents. The proposed dataset has been generated in an emulated 5G network, with a wide deployment of network sensors for its creation. IW-IB-5GNET dataset is promising to facilitate the development of autonomous and intelligent network management solutions that enhance network performance and optimisation.

- **Outcome 3 (Conference):**

Conference	IWCMC 2024 International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing WS-1: Advanced AI for Future Mobile Networks & Communication Systems Workshop (AI-NECOS)
Title	Handling Imbalanced 5G and Beyond Network Tabular Data Using Conditional Generative Models [5]
Authors	Jimena Andrade-Hoz Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero Qi Wang
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE B
Date of Conference Location DOI URL	27–31 May 2024 Ayia Napa, Cyprus 10.1109/IWCMC61514.2024.10592409 https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10592409
Contribution	The contribution of this research work is the development, implementation, evaluation and comparison of four generative models for tabular data on a B5G network management dataset. These models have been previously optimised according to certain evaluation metrics of the generated synthetic data. The dataset presents a problem of imbalance between its classes, which is improved by using generative models to enrich it with synthetic data. The results show that machine learning based generative models obtain more accurate data than traditional statistical models, and are much faster in terms of conditional data sampling.

- **Outcome 4 (Conference):**

Conference	CSNDSP 2024 14th International Symposium on Communication Systems, Networks and Digital Signal Processing
Title	Multi-layer Multi-technology Firewall Optimisation in Beyond 5G and Pre-6G networks Using Machine Learning Classifiers [6]
Authors	Jimena Andrade-Hoz Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero Qi Wang
Date of Conference Location DOI URL	17-19 July 2024 Rome, Italy 10.1109/CSNDSP60683.2024.10636539 https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10636539
Contribution	In this work, an architecture that enables the optimisation of multi-layer multi-technology firewalls integrated in a B5G network testbed is presented. The proposed framework supports network control monitoring and automatic deployment of firewall rules in three different virtual function implementations: iptables, Open vSwitch and Linux traffic control. Real-time network monitoring allows the proposed machine learning based classifier to predict the optimal technology of each of the firewall rules inserted in the network. After performing a comparison among four popular machine learning models for the optimal selection, the results obtained show that Random Forest is the best algorithm for the proposed solution.

In addition, multiple software outcomes have been developed as a result of the research process. These are detailed below:

- **Outcome 5 (Software):**

Title	Resource Monitoring Agent (RMA)
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz, Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Ana Serrano-Mamorlar
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/aserranouws/rma
Description	This software tool has been specifically designed in Java to monitor metrics from different layers of the network components where it is deployed. The software allows the monitoring of metrics from devices, interfaces and technology network functions such as iptables, OpenVSwitch and Linux Traffic Control. The metrics to be monitored are configured in a configuration file and can be easily extended using such configuration file. In addition, the tool allows the information to be published in JSON format to message broker services such as RabbitMQ.

- **Outcome 6 (Software):**

Title	Infrastructure Data-Extractor Manager (IDEM)
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/deca
Description	IDEM is a python component responsible for real-time data extraction, data shaping, data sorting and data adaptation to a CSV file format, ready for network-based AI management purposes. The IDEM extracts from a MySQL database metadata and metrics coming from different network resources: device, interfaces, technology, flow and network rules. Metrics to be extracted can be selected in a configuration file.

- **Outcome 7 (Software):**

Title	5GNetLabeller
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/feature-viewer
Description	NetLabeller is a Graphical User Interface (GUI) implemented in Python that allows the user to visually interact with a networking dataset and to direct label it. NetLabeller abstracts all the complexity that a user can find in a CSV file, as it transforms a bunch of values and commas into an interface that represents all those values in an orderly and visually arranged way. The type of label and its classes can be customised through the configuration file.

- **Outcome 8 (Dataset):**

Title	IW-IB-5GNET unlabelled
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/iw-ib-5gnet
Description	<i>IW-IB-5GNET-unlabelled</i> is an Infrastructure-wide and Intent-Based networking dataset for 5G and beyond networks management and optimisation. The dataset compiles a total of 120 experiment executions explained in [4]. Its total size is 64291 instances (rows) and 107 features (columns).

- **Outcome 9 (Dataset):**

Title	IW-IB-5GNET labelled
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/iw-ib-5gnet
Description	<i>IW-IB-5GNET-labelled</i> is a subset of the original dataset containing 10% of the extracted data. This dataset is labelled according to the three datapath technologies available in the network: iptables, traffic control and OpenV Switch.

- **Outcome 10 (Software):**

Title	C5GT-GAN: conditional tabular data generator
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/c5gt-gan
Description	Software tool developed in python for generating and evaluating synthetic tabular data using generative models. The tools allows four different actions based on a tabular dataset: train a synthesizer, tune a synthesizer, sample data using a concrete synthesizer and evaluate synthetic data generated. The available synthesizers are: CTGAN, CopulaGAN, GaussianCopula and TVAE.

- **Outcome 11 (Algorithm):**

Title	CopulaGAN-UWS
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/c5gt-gan
Description	Corresponds to the implementation of the CopulaGAN deep learning model, trained with data from the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. This model is able to sample synthetic data according to conditional constraints and based on the training data samples.

- **Outcome 12 (Dataset):**

Title	IW-IB-5GNET balanced
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/iw-ib-5gnet
Description	<i>IW-IB-5GNET-balanced</i> dataset contains the real dataset together with synthetic samples generated to balance the minority classes.

- **Outcome 13 (Software):**

Title	Firewall Optimiser
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/firewall-optimiser
Description	Software framework developed in Python for training and evaluating five different machine learning algorithms: Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, K-nearest Neighbours and XGBoost. The tool also allow the hyperparameter tuning of the models and basic representation of results.

- **Outcome 14 (Algorithm):**

Title	RF-FO-UWS
Author	Jimena Andrade-Hoz
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Jandrade/firewall-optimiser
Description	RF-FO-UWS is a Random Forest based implementation which represents the proposed solution for the optimal technology selection. The letters FO refer to the model being called Firewall Optimiser. The model can be found in the following path <i>firewall-optimiser/rf-fo-uws.pkl</i>

List of Acronyms

1G	First Generation 7
2G	Second Generation 7
3G	Third Generation 7
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project 8
4G	Fourth Generation 1, 8
5G	Fifth Generation 1, 2, 4, 8, 22, 145, 148
5G NSA	5G non-Standalone 8
5G SA	5G Standalone 8
5GPPP	5G Public Private Partnership 11
ACGAN	Auxiliary Classifier GAN 126
ADASYN	Adaptive Synthetic Minority Oversampling 124
AI	Artificial Intelligence xxxiii, 3–5, 12, 25–27, 31, 33, 34, 36, 44, 45, 50, 54, 69, 75, 78, 79, 83, 86, 105, 145, 146, 149, 176–178
AMF	Core Access and Mobility Management Function 9
AMPS	Advanced Mobile Phone System 7
AN	Autonomous Network 12, 77, 78, 82
AUSF	Authentication Server Function 9
B5G	Beyond 5G Networks xxxiii, 2, 4, 10, 16, 18, 19, 25, 26, 30, 31, 37, 38, 42, 46, 50, 74, 77–79, 82, 105, 123, 124, 137, 145–147, 149, 151, 153, 159, 171, 176, 178
BPF	Berkeley Packet Filters 3, 180
CART	Classification and Regression Trees 126
CDP	Cisco Discovery Protocol 85
CGAN	Conditional GAN 126, 127
CLI	Command-line Interface 89
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network 126
CORE	Common Open Research Emulator 85, 87
CPM	Cognitive Policy Manager 23, 84, 85, 89, 90
CPU	Central Processing Unit 49
CSV	Comma-separated values 39, 41, 44, 45, 54, 58, 59, 61, 65, 68–70, 72, 73, 92, 93, 95
CTGAN	Conditional Tabular GAN 124–126, 130, 137, 139–141, 143, 144, 160, 177
CU	Centralised Unit 9, 10, 67

DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service 86, 88, 90, 152, 177
DL	Deep Learning 125
DMA	Direct Memory Allocation 16
DoS	Denial of Service 80
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit 13
DSP	Digital Service Provider 11, 12, 105
DT	Decision Tree 126
DU	Distributed Unit 9, 10, 67
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter 15, 16
EDA	Exploratory Data Analysis 40, 54, 62, 108
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband 1
EMC	Exact Match Cache 116, 117
FCA	Flow Control Agent 23, 24, 64, 65, 67, 68, 84, 85, 91, 118, 151, 152
FFN	Feed Forward Neural Network 126, 128
FlexRIC	Flexible RAN Intelligent Controller 17
fqcode	Fair Queuing Controlled Delay 113
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network 125–127, 130, 138, 140, 144, 160
gNB	Next-Generation Node B 9
GPS	Global Positioning System 39
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol 10, 86, 98
GUI	Graphical User Interface xiv, 31, 58, 60–62, 65, 119
HTB	Hierarchical Token Bucket 113
IB	Intent-based 79
IBN	Intent-Based Network xxvii, 18–21, 78, 176
IDEM	Infrastructure Data Extractor manager xxvii, xxviii, xxxi, 44, 54, 56–59, 63–72, 85, 108, 176, 178, 181
IDS	Intrusion Detection System 12, 22, 80, 103
IoT	Internet of Things 1, 12, 80, 81, 127
ISP	Infrastructure Service Provider 11, 90, 105
ITU	International Telecommunication Union 1
IW	Infrastructure-wide 79
KDE	Kernel Density Estimation xxviii, xxix, 138, 141, 142
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors 126, 146, 153, 163–166, 172
LAN	Local Area Network 67, 80
LLDP	Link Layer Discovery Protocol 85
LR	Learning rate 138
MAAS	Metal-as-a-Service 66

MAE	Mean Absolute Error xxxii, 143, 144
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing 10
ML	Machine Learning xxix, 4, 27, 30, 34, 39, 78, 79, 108–111, 122–124, 126, 128, 129, 138, 139, 144, 146, 147, 150–154, 159, 160, 163, 165, 172, 176–179
MLP	Multi-layer Perceptron 126, 127
mMTC	massive mMachine Type Communications 1
MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit 132
MVC	Model-View-Controller 59
NCF	Network Control Functions 25, 26, 31, 32, 34, 176, 179
NFV	Network Functions Virtualisation 10, 13, 145
NIC	Network Interface Card 3, 15, 49
NID	Network Intrusion Detection 81, 82
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System 22
NIMS	Management and Security Group 126
NMT	Nordic Mobile Telephony 7
O-RAN	Open RAN 17
OAI	Open Air Interface 65–67, 85
ORO	Optimal Rule Ordering 148
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection 50
OVS	Open vSwitch 3, 16, 23, 37, 47, 49, 61, 85–87, 90, 91, 97–101, 108, 111, 114–122, 176, 180, 181
PCAP	Packet Capture 67
PCC	Pearson correlation coefficients 102, 142
PCF	Policy Control Function 9
PDN	Packet Data Network 9
qdisc	Queueing Discipline 113, 114
R2L	Remote to Local 80
RAM	Random-access memory 86
RAN	Radio Access Network 8–10, 65, 66, 85, 87, 93
RBF	Radial Basis Function 155
RF	Random forest 126, 127, 147, 155, 164–167, 170–172, 180
RIA	Resource Inventory Agent 22, 23, 52, 57, 64, 65, 67, 84, 85, 151
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller 17
RMA	Resource Monitoring Agent 22, 23, 42, 43, 51–53, 57, 64, 65, 67, 84, 151
RU	Radio Unit 9, 66
RX	received 15, 16, 47
SDN	Software-Defined Networking 2, 10, 85, 115, 145, 152
SDV	Synthetic Data Vault 137
SKB	Socket Buffer 16
SMA	Security Monitoring Agent 22, 23, 57, 64, 65, 67, 84, 85, 90, 151

SMF	Session Management Function 9
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique 124, 126, 127
SPA	Single-page Application 74
SQL	Structured query language 24, 44, 64, 68, 85
SVM	Support Vector Machines 126, 127, 147, 155, 163–166, 172
TC	Traffic Control 3, 13, 16, 23, 47, 49, 53, 61, 85, 87, 90, 91, 97–101, 108, 111, 113, 114, 117, 119–122, 129, 134, 137, 144, 160, 162, 165, 171, 176, 180
TCAM	Ternary Content Address Memory 49
TGAN	Tabular GAN 125, 130
TVAE	Tabular Variational Auto-encoder 124, 126, 130, 131, 137–140, 143, 144, 160, 177
TVD	Total Variation Distance 135
TX	Transmitted 47
U2R	User to Root 80
UDM	User Data Management 9
UDP	User Datagram Protocol 86
UE	User Equipment 8–10, 66, 67, 69, 85, 87–91
UI	User Interface 60
UPF	User plane Function 9
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-latency Communications 1
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral 66
VAE	Variational Auto-encoders 125, 130
VNF	Virtual Network Functions 2, 12, 146, 148
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local-Area Network 10, 86, 98
XDP	Express Data Path 13, 15, 16, 36, 37, 180
XGB	Extreme Gradient Boosting, XGBoost 126, 147, 156, 163–166, 172

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in mobile networks driven by softwarisation and virtualisation offers innovative solutions for network control and network optimisation. This research focuses on a concrete case of self-optimisation network control in Beyond 5G Networks (B5G), investigating the use of different network control functions for optimal implementation of network rules.

This thesis proposes an AI-driven approach to select the most appropriate network control function technology (e.g., Linux Traffic Control, iptables, Open Virtual Switch) based on specific network conditions and external factors. For this purpose, this research work first analyses key metrics for network control and creates a comprehensive training dataset. To make the creation of this dataset possible, two software components have been developed. A network monitoring component and a network data extractor capable of gathering more than 100 metrics in less than 1 second. The networking dataset has been extracted from a lab-based B5G network by running four different use cases. The resulting dataset, called the IW-IB-5GNET dataset, consisting of 7,708 labelled instances, was labelled using a newly developed labelling tool, NetLabeller. Labels represent the optimal network control technology for each scenario deployed. After the labelling process, various data augmentation techniques, including GAN-based algorithms, were performed to enrich the dataset. Finally, a Random Forest classifier has been selected as a result of the empirical comparison of different supervised ML algorithms. The Random Forest outperforms the rest of the classifiers, obtaining a total of 90.83% F1-score and an accuracy of 97.10%. This research work and its contributions collectively prepare the way for advanced, autonomous B5G networks by optimising network policies using AI algorithms.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The transition from Fourth Generation (4G) of mobile networks to Fifth Generation (5G) marked a significant leap in mobile network technology, driven by the increasing demands of a connected world since 2020 [7]. As 4G networks evidenced their capacity limits, the need for a more advanced and versatile network became apparent. The exponential growth of data consumption, the proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and the emergence of new applications requiring ultra-low latency and high reliability needed an advanced approach to mobile networks [8]. This is due to the fact that 4G networks, while capable of providing high-speed broadband access, were not designed to handle the diverse and complex requirements of emerging technologies such as autonomous vehicles, industrial automation, and augmented reality. The limitations in spectrum efficiency, network capacity, and latency of 4G networks [9] became increasingly evident as user expectations and technological advancements exceeded its capabilities.

In the new era of connectivity, 5G lead the evolution of mobile networks advancing the three key features defined by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), including enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable and Low-latency Communications (URLLC) and massive mMachin e Type Communications (mMTC) [10]. 5G technology has introduced a paradigm shift in mobile network architecture and functionality, enabling a wide range of innovative technological challenges derived from previous generations, which includes enhanced data speeds, ultra-low latency, increased capacity in terms of

number of connected devices, network slicing, Software-Defined Networking (SDN), network softwarisation and Virtual Network Functions (VNF). Such features make possible the existence of multiple tenants in the same network, enabling efficient resource sharing, isolation, customisation, and service management [11].

From a business perspective 5G has a vital role to play in accelerating industry productivity [12] and transforming economic sectors such as healthcare, transportation and energy, among others. This is clearly reflected in the adoption and subscription trends, since 5G subscriptions are forecast to increase drastically worldwide, from over 12 million in 2019 to over 4.5 billion subscriptions by 2028 [13]. Due to this massive increase, 5G research highlights the need for network automation, self-organisation and simplification of network management for administrators and users. These three features will facilitate the adoption, deployment, performance and evolution of future mobile networks, which are known as B5G.

The introduction of network softwarisation has brought with it numerous benefits to B5G such as reduced hardware dependency, increased scalability, faster and intelligent service deployment, advanced operation, network slicing and multi-tenancy [14]. However, several costs and challenges have arisen since then. Capital costs have increased due to investment in data centres, cloud infrastructures, and software licenses to support virtualised network functions [12]. Additionally, operational costs are significant due to investments in software-defined infrastructure, ongoing maintenance, and training for personnel to adapt to new technologies and complexities. One of the key challenges introduced by B5G networks is the effective management of data traffic, which has become increasingly complex. This complexity arises from the diverse requirements of B5G networks, which support a wide range of services with varying demands for bandwidth, latency, and reliability. The heterogeneous network architecture further complicates the network traffic management [15]. Moreover, B5G networks need to adapt to rapidly changing network conditions and user demands, while also accommodating the massive device connectivity brought about by the proliferation of IoT devices and machine-type communications [16].

To address these challenges, B5G networks employ various technologies and techniques for network traffic control management. Today's networks have multiple programmable

technologies on the same network interface for network control and traffic manipulation. This results from (i) network softwarisation, particularly the softwarisation of network interfaces, (ii) the evolution of the operating systems themselves that have been providing more programmability for the network interface and (iii) the proliferation of more and new technologies to implement the programming of the network interface. These technologies provide network administrators with powerful tools to implement traffic management, security policies, and performance optimisation in programmable networks [17]. Examples of these technologies are Linux Traffic Control (TC), Netronome BPF offloading, Mellanox offloading, Linux iptables and, Open vSwitch (OVS), among others. Some of these technologies have been widespread due to new trends in hardware offloading, where the Network Interface Card (NIC) can be programmed in hardware to perform specific network tasks [18, 19]. Numerous advantages can be drawn from this, of which three are particularly noteworthy. First, the possibility of getting multiple technologies for the same logical network interface. Second, the possibility of selecting the most suitable one for each specific use case, in terms of throughput, latency, rule volume, packet losses, jitter, etc. Third, the multi-layer protection, so that if one of the points has a vulnerability, this can be addressed by another technology.

Despite the many advantages offered by multi-technology in network interfaces, there are limitations associated with it. The main one is that now, the network administrator not only has to be concerned about the configuration of a particular network policy/rule on a particular interface. But the administrator has to know also how to program the same rule on multiple technologies available on the network interface and how to select which of them is most suitable for the desired use case. The complexity of knowledge for the network administrator is, therefore, highly increased. This leads to administrator's decisions incomplete, late and far to be optimal in many cases. The problem is exacerbated by the current trend towards automation and self-governance of networks, which aims to configure and deploy systems in a matter of milliseconds, automatically and without human intervention [20].

With respect to automation, where users are not involved in decision making but complexity exists, the possibility of using AI tools to introduce new levels of intelligence in the management and provisioning layers of the 5G network [21] is raised. This can be achieved

by following an AI-driven approach where intelligence will be an intrinsic feature of the future 6G architecture [22]. Employing AI, or more specifically Machine Learning (ML), to solve the initial problem poses new associated challenges. At present, despite the existence of multiple network monitoring datasets, the presence of datasets containing features from multiple network interface technologies is practically non-existent. This lack of data is even greater if the focus is on 5G networks. This makes any attempt to use ML techniques for selecting the best technology impossible, creating a major challenge. Thus, the need to define those datasets and what information should they include to fulfil that particular purpose is another main challenge.

The principal objective of this research work is to address the challenges outlined above. Specifically, the endeavour of exploiting the multi-technology characteristics of B5G networks to optimise network control rules by applying AI techniques. This one entails overcoming the challenge of creating a novel network dataset to obtain an AI-based model for implementing such network control optimisation. Therefore, this document presents the design, prototype, development and empirical validation of an AI-driven algorithm to perform the self-governance of multi-tenant B5G in multi-technology selection within network interfaces (both physical and virtual). This is achieved in a way that takes full advantage of all the benefits associated with these multiple technologies while providing the simplicity and complexity management necessary for effective implementation. To achieve this, an architecture with data extraction and dataset generation has also been designed, developed and empirically validated in a 5G network infrastructure. Such data set has been used to train an ML algorithm that has been later on being used to perform the optimal selection of technology according to the use case being addressed.

The rest of the document is organised as follows. Chapter 2 contextualises and familiarises the reader with an overview of architectural concepts, technologies and terminology related to the scope of this thesis. Chapter 3 outlines the aim and objectives of this research work. Chapter 4 provides the reader with a clear understanding of the methodological approach followed to conduct the thesis. The following five chapters present the development of the different objectives of the research work. Thus, Chapter 5 the process of monitoring,

extracting and visualising the desired network data is presented. Then, the experiments carried out to obtain the dataset and the actual dataset are explained in Chapter 6. The labelling process is presented in Chapter 7. The dataset processing and other relevant issues after the labelling process are addressed in Chapter 8. Finally, the AI model is developed in Chapter 9. To conclude this dissertation, some conclusions, limitations and future work are presented in Chapter 10.

Chapter 2

Background and Architectural principles

This section aims to provide the knowledge base for the future development of the subsequent chapters, explaining theoretical concepts of importance for understanding the procedure carried out.

2.1 Mobile network generations

Mobile network technology has undergone significant evolution since its initiation, with each generation bringing substantial improvements in performance, capacity, and functionality. The journey began with the First Generation (1G) of mobile networks in the 1980s, which utilised analogue technologies such as the Advanced Mobile Phone System (AMPS) in the United States and the Nordic Mobile Telephony (NMT) in Europe. These early networks were primarily focused on enabling voice calls, but they suffered from poor quality, limited coverage, and security vulnerabilities [23].

The transition to digital technology marked the origin of Second Generation (2G) networks in the 1990s. This shift brought about increased bandwidth, improved audio quality, and the introduction of text messaging (SMS) [24]. However, 2G networks still had limitations, particularly in terms of data transmission speeds and security. The Third Generation (3G) arrived at the turn of the millennium, leading in the era of mobile Internet. 3G networks offered significantly higher bandwidth, allowing for web browsing, email access, and basic

multimedia consumption on mobile devices [25]. The Fourth Generation (4G) followed in the 2010s, further enhancing data speeds, network capacity, and supporting new technologies such as the IoT.

Despite the advancements made with each generation, several limitations persisted. 2G networks, which are still supported by many modern smartphones, are known to be vulnerable to eavesdropping and spoofing attacks [26]. 3G and 4G networks, while more secure, still face challenges in meeting the growing demands for data from both consumer and industrial users [27]. These limitations, coupled with the increasing demand for higher data rates, lower latency, and support for emerging technologies like autonomous vehicles and smart city applications, have created a compelling need for the development of 5G networks. With its ability to support up to one million connected devices per square kilometre and peak data rates of up to 20 Gbps, 5G is transforming mobile communications, enabling a wide range of new applications and services [8]. The rest of this chapter focuses on the technical aspects of this technology.

2.2 5G Network Architecture

The 5G technology can be deployed using two different network architectures, 5G non-Standalone (5G NSA) and 5G Standalone (5G SA). The main difference between them is that the 5G NSA uses the core of the previous generation, which is 4G. This section focuses on the 5G SA architecture, standardised by 3GPP, as the subsequent development of the thesis has been based on this. Please note that the purpose of this section is not to provide an exhaustive analysis of this type of networks. In the case that the reader is interested in going deeper into the subject, please refer to the reference [28].

The 5G SA cellular infrastructure is composed of two main segments, the 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) and the 5G Core. These segments, their specific components and the interfaces linking them are specified in Figure 2.1.

The RAN is part of the 5G network infrastructure that facilitates the connection between User Equipment (UE) and the Core network [29]. It corresponds to a distributed collection

Fig. 2.1 5G SA architecture - main components and interfaces.

of antennas or Radio Unit (RU), where the radio frequency signals are transmitted, received, amplified, and digitised. Each RU has its own Distributed Unit (DU) associated, which is connected to a Centralised Unit (CU). These two components form what is called the Next-Generation Node B (gNB) and form the computation parts of the base station, sending the digitised radio signal into the network. They handle the control plane and the data plane. The DU is responsible for handling real-time, lower-layer processing tasks and the CU handles non-real-time, higher-layer processing tasks. There is a single CU for each gNB, but one CU can control multiple DUs. DU and CU are connected by the standardised F1 interface. After these components, RAN and Core are connected through the Transport Segment.

The Core network segment is where access for the user to other networks is provided. The 5G Core functions are divided into six principal components, split up by service. Five of them handle the control plane: Core Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), Policy Control Function (PCF), Authentication Server Function (AUSF) and User Data Management (UDM). In summary, these components are responsible for UE authentication, UE management and IP addresses, session management for the data transfer, policy control and UE data storage. Finally, the User plane Function (UPF) handles the data plane and provides connectivity with the external Packet Data Network (PDN), e.g. Internet access or operator services [30].

2.3 Beyond 5G Mobile Edge Architecture

In the present section, the B5G network of reference in this thesis is presented. Figure 2.2 presents a 5G network where physical resources are shared through virtualisation by multiple tenants (e.g., network operators) in a multi-tenant environment. In such infrastructure, the traffic remains isolated between tenants in consequence of virtualisation capabilities and traffic tunnelling across network segments. Specifically, the UE payload is encapsulated by the GTP protocol to provide user mobility across the infrastructure and the VXLAN encapsulation is used to isolate the tenant traffic over the physical infrastructure. Two virtual tenants are depicted in the figure marked with dashed lines representing the isolation of each tenant's virtual infrastructure.

Virtualisation and softwarisation are seen as a fundamental paradigm in the design of B5G networks [31]. As a result, two key technologies are leveraged in this type of network: SDN and Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) [32]. SDN is an approach to networking that uses software-based controllers to communicate with the underlying hardware infrastructure and route traffic in the network. This allows the virtualisation of different network functionalities. NFV enables agile and automated deployment of virtual network services such as routers, firewalls or load balancers that have traditionally been run on hardware.

Five different network segments are shown in Fig. 2.2: RAN, Edge network, Transport network, Core network, and Inter-Domain network. For a shake of simplicity, only datapath components have been represented in the figure. The data flow traverses every segment, each serving a distinct purpose. Starting with the RAN segment, it represents the interface between UEs and the 5G network. As mentioned in the previous section, the RAN handles tasks such as signal modulation, demodulation, and encryption. The RAN is connected to the Edge segment through CUs, which are virtualised and deployed in the Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) network [33]. It is noted that DUs can be deployed either in the RAN or in the Edge segment. The Edge segment constitutes geo-distributed servers with virtualisation capabilities that provide computing and storage resources closer to the end users, reducing latency and improving service quality [34]. It enables the analysis and processing of data near

Fig. 2.2 Overview of the segments of a softwarised 5G multi-tenant infrastructure.

the source, facilitating real-time and low-latency applications. Deploying Edge computing at the base station enhances computation and avoids bottlenecks and system failure [33]. Although in our reference network, the Edge segment is only used for the deployment of monitoring and control network components.

Edge and Core segments are connected through the Transport segment. The Transport network is responsible for carrying data between both segments, ensuring efficient data transmission with high capacity and low latency. The Core network is the central part of the 5G network. As explained before, it provides advanced functions such as session management, mobility management, and authentication through different control plane components. Note that the Core components have not been included in this figure, as they have already been specified in Figure 2.1. It is connected to the Interdomain segment, which encompasses the interconnection between different administrative domains or service providers. Finally, as shown in Figure 2.2, the 5G system is composed of different stakeholders described in [35] by the 5G Public Private Partnership (5GPPP). These include Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) and Digital Service Provider (DSP), both involved in the provisioning of network resources. ISPs are in charge of delivering Internet connectivity to end-users. ISPs also manage the network infrastructure and facilitate the distribution of data to and from

end-users. DSPs, on the other hand, offer digital services and applications to end-users over the 5G network. DSPs create and deploy digital services that enhance user experiences and drive innovation, such as video streaming, cloud computing and IoT applications. In the figure, each DSP corresponds to a different tenant where all these services could be deployed.

The presented architecture supports the quest for network automation that is achieved through cognitive loops. Autonomous Network (AN) capabilities empower the network to self-manage and self-optimize its operations. Such automation is conducted by the deployment of different network layers, which are the compute, service and management layer. These network layers are represented as blue boxes in Figure 2.2. The compute layer plays a crucial role in enabling autonomous network capabilities as it provides the processing power to support VNF. They interact with the network traffic in the Edge and Core segments. Some examples of the advanced capabilities enabled are distributed computing, scalability, elasticity, resource optimisation and AI deployments. The service layer encompasses the creation, deployment, and management of services provided over the 5G network infrastructure. This layer does not interact directly with network traffic, but with mirrored traffic to perform monitoring and runtime management [35]. It focuses on delivering a large set of services that meet the diverse requirements of end-users and applications such as Intrusion Detection System (IDS). Finally, the management layer is responsible for supervising and controlling network's operation and resources. It makes use of advanced analytics and AI algorithms to monitor, analyse and optimise different network characteristics such as security, performance and resource allocation. This layer utilises data and information coming from the compute and service layers to create informed decisions and automate network management processes and network control functions. The integration of these three layers in the 5G network allows the development of closed-loop capabilities such as adaptation to changing conditions, self-protection against attacks and optimisation of the resource utilisation [21].

2.4 Network Control Functions

2.4.1 Definition

Network control refers to the management, orchestration and supervision of a network to ensure its efficient operation, optimal performance, and security. It involves the administration of network devices, protocols, and resources to facilitate communication and data exchange between devices within the network. Network control includes a wide range of functions, such as network and traffic management, routing and switching control, performance monitoring and optimisation, firewalling, security control and policy enforcement. In today's modern network infrastructures, these network control functions are virtualised and controlled by software-defined networking and NFV technologies, rather than relying solely on traditional hardware-based infrastructure [36]. This allows operators to dynamically allocate resources, optimise traffic routing and apply network policies based on real-time network conditions and user demands.

As introduced in Chapter 1, the most modern mobile infrastructures today make use of innovative technologies for the implementation of network control functions. Examples of these datapath technologies are network accelerators (Mellanox, Netronome, Intel, etc.), kernel bypass technologies (Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK), Express Data Path (XDP), etc.) on top of the traditional and well-established kernel technologies (TC, iptables, etc.). This heterogeneity of technologies is no longer a matter of choosing one technology to perform all network control functions, but multiple datapath technologies are now available at the same time on the same network interface.

Some of these technologies allow interaction with certain network hooks, which are predefined points in the Linux kernel's network stack where packets can be intercepted and processed [37]. The Netfilter [38] framework provides these hooks, allowing kernel modules to register callback functions that are called when packets traverse specific points in the network stack. For example, iptables is a user-space application that interfaces with the Netfilter hooks to implement packet filtering, address translation, and packet mangling.

Fig. 2.3 Identification of datapath technologies location within the network interface.

In other words, network hooks provide a point in the network where to implement packet manipulation through datapath technologies.

2.4.2 Datapath technologies for network control functions

Datapath technologies are located at a particular stage in the ingress data path of the network interface. In Linux, the ingress data path refers to the journey a packet takes from the moment it arrives at the network interface hardware until it is processed by the kernel network stack. Figure 2.3 represents the various stages of the ingress/egress data path of a physical

network interface. Different datapath technologies are represented as orange dots. The figure allows the reader to locate each datapath technology on a network interface and to understand how data flow passes through them. The figure is a zoomed-in view of each of the network interfaces depicted in Figure 2.2 as white squares. It is worth mentioning that just a few datapath technologies have been represented in the figure as an example but other technologies previously mentioned can also be present. Additionally, note that the existing number of datapath technologies might vary when it comes to a virtual interface.

A brief explanation of the ingress data path is provided below. During such process, packets pass through several datapath technologies that provide mechanisms for managing and controlling network traffic.

Focusing on the lower part of the figure, the packets arrive at the network interface hardware (NIC), where physical layer processing is undergone. The NIC interacts directly with memory using Direct Memory Access (DMA). Thus, the NIC driver reads/writes packet data from/to the ring-buffer structures where packets are left/gathered by the NIC and copies them into the kernel memory. It also performs any necessary initial processing, such as checksum validation. The packets are enqueued into the driver received (RX) queue associated with the network interface. As it is shown in the figure, XDP datapath is located in both hardware and driver stages, even in the earliest point of the network stack. XDP is a programmable high-performance networking datapath that works in conjunction with the Linux stack, and relies on extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) to perform very fast packet processing. eBPF is an instruction set and an execution environment inside the Linux kernel that enables modification, interaction, and kernel programmability at runtime [39]. It enables programmed code to be executed in the kernel space in a secure and restricted environment. The main benefit of XDP technology is their capability to execute programs for packet processing at extremely early stages, even before the packets reach the Linux network stack. XDP can only be executed in the ingress path. The execution of this datapath can happen in three different places (as shown in Fig. 2.3): (1) Offloaded Mode which involves attaching eBPF programs directly into hardware network devices, making it the fastest mode among all; (2) Native Mode, where the execution takes place in the driver before the kernel

allocates a Socket Buffer (SKB); and (3) Generic Mode, in which the XDP hook is invoked after the packet Direct Memory Allocation (DMA) and SKB allocation are finished. This mode tends to diminish most of the performance advantages of this datapath.

If kernel bypass is not performed, packets are then dequeued from the RX queue and passed to the network stack for further processing. Packets are then processed by the appropriate protocol layer in the network stack based on its destination address and protocol type. This includes tasks such as IP forwarding, routing table lookup, and potential firewall processing. At the initial stage of this network stack, Linux TC [40] is placed. TC acts as a packet scheduler, offering hooking points within the Linux kernel, enabling the configuration of various queue disciplines for scheduling and shaping tasks. In addition to its inherent packet processing and classification abilities, TC can utilise u32 modules for classification and facilitate the attachment of eBPF programs. Subsequently, packets proceed to Linux bridges or virtual switches for further processing. OVS [41] is among the most commonly used tools at the bridging level. OVS, an open-source virtual multi-layer distributed switch, is integrated into the mainstream of the Linux kernel, providing a switching stack for virtualised hardware environments. Following this, packets requiring network-level processing traverse multiple Netfilter hooks. At these points, diverse packet filtering and mangling expressions can be applied using the widely-known user-space tool iptables [42]. Iptables demonstrates excellent performance in traditional networks, particularly for firewalling tasks. However, it might not scale effectively for high traffic rates and lacks native support for handling the deeply encapsulated traffic of modern networks such as B5G networks.

Once the protocol processing phase has finished, the packet is added to the socket's receive queue, awaiting delivery to the application. Finally, the packet is delivered to the receiving application.

To conclude this section, a table enumerating different network control functions, together with the datapath technologies able to perform them is presented. Table 2.1 summarises different network control functions both on ingress and egress. Datapath technologies are classified by their location in the datapath (see yellow labels in Fig. 2.3) following the abbreviations: Firmware (FW), Driver (DR), Scheduler (SCHE), Bridge (BR) and Network

Table 2.1 Network control function capabilities by different datapath technologies (I: Ingress, E: Egress).

		FW FLEXRIC	DR XDP	SCHE TC	BR OVS	NET IPTABLES
Drop	I	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
	E	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Priority	I	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
	E	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
BWD Limitation	I	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
	E	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
BWD guaranteed	I	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
	E	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
L1 Outer mirror	I	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
	E	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗
L1 Outer redirect	I	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
	E	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
L3 Outer redirect	I	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
	E	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
Outer TOS	I	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
	E	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Queue config	I	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
	E	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
Kernel Bypass	I	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
	E	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

(NET). From now on, we will refer to network control functions indistinctively as network policies or network rules. Examples of network control policies are performing a drop to a malicious traffic, prioritising specific traffic flows, setting concrete bandwidth limitation or guaranteeing a particular bandwidth to specified traffic.

It is worth mentioning a new datapath technology that appears in the table and which has not been explained above as it is not found within the network interface, which is Flexible RAN Intelligent Controller (FlexRIC) [43]. It is an Open RAN (O-RAN) Alliance software implementation of various components in the RAN segment that provides, among others, applications (called xApps) that run on the Near-Real-Time RIC to implement various control and optimisation functions for the RAN segment. The specific control functions offered by

this technology are shown in the table. This datapath will not be explored further as the focus of this research work is once the traffic reaches the Edge network interface.

As can be seen from the table, there are a multitude of control functions and many datapath technologies as a possibility to perform them. The choice of which one to use will be determined by many factors to take into account, such as the technology complexity of programming, the complexity of the rule to be enforced, the execution time of the rule, the status of the network and the network interface, among many others.

2.5 Intent-based management framework

The following two sections are aimed to explain the design and functioning of the intent-based B5G network on which this thesis has been based. Therefore, section 2.5.1 provides an explanation of the Intent-Based Network (IBN) fundamentals, contextualised in a B5G network. Then, section 2.5.2 explains the different network components that make it possible to monitor and collect data and, execute intents.

2.5.1 Description of 5G intent-based architecture

An IBN is a network that can be managed using intent. Intent is a high-level description of a set of operational goals and outcomes that a network should meet and is supposed to deliver, respectively [44]. It defines objectives and outcomes in a purely declarative manner, rather than specifying the detailed network configuration [35] or how to achieve it. Intents are then translated into network policies, which provide much more specific details concerning network configurations [45]. Such network policies will result in the execution of network actions, achieving the desired outcome specified in the intent. Examples of intents in a 5G network are: (i) “Ensure the deployment of the network slice meets the specified service-level agreement (SLA) with regard to latency, bandwidth, and reliability.”, (ii) “Assign the highest priority to critical application traffic, ensuring low-latency and guaranteed bandwidth, while maintaining a minimum level of service for standard traffic.” and (iii) “Eliminate any traffic

flow exhibiting malicious behaviour or unauthorised access attempts, without disrupting legitimate network traffic.”

The primary objective of IBN is to establish an autonomic network by simplifying its management and operation. By this end, IBN conceives to create a complete autonomous network framework [45], improving the robustness of the network and achieving dynamic operation and maintenance [46]. Figure 2.4 represents our IBN approach in order to achieve the closed-loop capabilities in the reference B5G network shown in Fig. 2.2. Such IBN approach automates the process of network configuration, provisioning and assurance by reducing human expert intervention. The proposed architecture consists of the three layers explained above, which are management, service and compute, in detail. Multiple network components (sensors and actuators) allocated in these layers work together to accomplish such autonomous features. This section is focused on the explanation of the intent-based networking process. In the following one, each of the components deployed in the proposed architecture will be explained in detail.

In our proposed IBN system high-level service requirements are autonomously orchestrated and executed in the network. The full process since the intent is inserted on the network until the moment that is removed from it (if necessary), consists of five different steps [45]. Each of them indicated in Figure 2.4 by yellow boxes and black arrows. The process is explained as follows:

1. Intent profiling. It is the first step of IBN, where the user interacts with the system to specify the desired intent. The intent is a straightforward declarative specification that must consider the network results expected by the user.
2. Intent translation. The intent statement is translated into a network policy, which will consist on a series of network rules and configurations. A policy is a set of rules defining what to do under what circumstances [47]. During this step, different cognitive algorithms (depending on the policy type) are performed in order to generate the best possible outcome.

Fig. 2.4 Design of the proposed IBN and overview of the different network components for closed-loop controls.

3. Intent resolution. It must be taken into account that multiple intents can happen in the network, at the same time. For this reason, during the intent translation it is essential to prevent the network from leading to contradictory and conflicting network configurations. For this reason, our IBN incorporates a policy resolution module, capable of resolving conflicting intents by suggesting conflict resolution strategies.
4. Intent activation. The next step after confirming there are not conflicts with other intent statements on the network, is the intent orchestration and activation. This step includes the network configuration and provisioning of the requested network policy. In other

words, the network is told what needs to be done, where and with what software technology. So the network is able to enforce the policy unambiguously. As shown in Figure 2.4, this process results in the enforcement of a rule (or more than one) that will be reflected in the data plane.

5. Intent assurance. This ultimate step entails ensuring that the network indeed complies with the desired intent once it has been achieved. To accomplish it, our IBN comprises multiple sensors capable of monitoring the status of the network in near real-time. Such components report metrics back to the management layer (see “5” yellow boxes in Fig. 2.4), which is in charge of assuring the intent fulfilment. Depending on the type of intent, after step 5, the intent-process will be finished or not.

By having intents in the network and multiple sensors monitoring its status, with the right services to provide alerts, a platform can be set up to support closed control loops. Specifically for this research work, a closed-loop to self-detect and self-heal the network in case malicious traffic traverses it. Such loop operates as a self-contained system, responding autonomously to identified tasks and ensuring that the network aligns with the user-specified intents without requiring human intervention throughout the entire process. In order to achieve this complete process, several network components are used, which are part of our proposed framework. Such software components are explained in detail in the next subsection.

2.5.2 Framework for Data Collection

This subsection describes the different software components necessary for the intent achievement and with which closed-loop features are provided. The data extraction process is detailed in Figure 2.4 by orange arrows and red circles. The presented design prioritises the extraction of metrics from the network, encompassing their subsequent storage. The infrastructure network approach consists of a set of network software components distributed in the three layers previously defined working together to conform a cognitive closed-loop system. Each component runs a specific task and the combination of all of them leads to

the accurate enforcement of network control rules. Such control rules have been previously translated from an intent. As depicted in orange in Figure 2.4, the communication and data exchange between components are facilitated by a message bus software through a publishing and subscription architecture. The red circles represent the type of data being exchanged in each case, while the orange arrows represent whether it is a subscription or a publication to that data exchange. The software components are described below.

- **Resource Inventory Agent (RIA).** It is a network component in charge of publishing topological network information in real-time. Such information is related to both physical and virtual devices, ports and connections between ports and devices available on each machine. RIA discovers the topology of the 5G network where it is instantiated and publish it for the rest of the network components. The performance and capabilities of this component are presented in [48].
- **Security Monitoring Agent (SMA).** It has two differentiated functionalities. First, it is in charge of enhancing and extending the capabilities provided by a traditional IDS. The reason behind this limitation can be attributed to the inadequacy of the capabilities possessed by traditional Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS), which are unable to fully leverage the potential offered by the 5G infrastructure and the accompanying network information. Hence, the SMA works together with Snort [49] extending the information provided by this traditional NIDS. Second, it supplies information about network flows, providing an inventory of all flows traversing each of the network interfaces and traffic alerts. It also provides metrics associated to the reported network flows. This sensor and its capabilities are presented in [50].
- **Resource Monitoring Agent (RMA).** It allows the monitoring of different network resources. This agent extracts metrics from network devices and network interfaces (physical and virtual network interfaces) previously discovered and published by the RIA component. The monitored metrics are configured using a configuration file and can be easily extended modifying such configuration file. This component has

been extended in the presented thesis to provide also the monitoring of datapath technologies.

- **Cognitive Policy Manager (CPM).** This component performs four differentiated tasks in order to generate network policies. First, it translates the user intent statements in network policies. At the same time, it is analysing flows and resource metrics provided by the SMA and RMA, together with the RIA's spatial information. Thus, it is able to generate an intensive analysis of the current status of the network. Taking into account the network policy, it generates a decision using such analysis, which includes what action should be taken, where and with what datapath technology. Such information will be used to complete the network policy. Depending on the intent type, the consequent policies can be diverse. Network policy examples are: performing a drop, mirroring traffic, redirecting specified traffic, prioritising a concrete flow and etcetera. Once the action to be done is decided, it performs the computation needed to complete the policy information, which is: what action to enforce, in which interface of the network, how to enforce it and for how long will the policy be active. Once all this information is completed, it orchestrates the policy and publish it in the message bus [51].
- **Flow Control Agent (FCA).** It exposes network traffic control capabilities to the management plane. The FCA is subscribed to the policy exchange and when it receives one, it translates the policy into specific network configurations and rules that can be executed by the network infrastructure in the data plane. The FCA is distributed across the whole infrastructure and it is an abstraction layer on top of different datapath control technologies such as TC, OVS and iptables. Once a rule is enforced in the network, the FCA also provides metrics associated with such rule periodically. Those metrics have been designed and included as part of this thesis contribution. Extensive explanation of this agent and its performance can be found in [52].
- **Data Collectors.** All data exchanged on the network through the message bus, such as the topology, extracted by the RIA, the metrics, collected by the RMA, and SMA and

the rule metrics reported by the FCA, are collected by the Data Collectors. The Data Collectors are in charge of transforming all data in Structured query language (SQL) queries and insert them into a database in real-time. As shown in Figure 2.4, there is a specialised collector for each data type. The collectors extract the information published by the network agents, adapt the data and store it into a SQL database. As a result, the management layer keeps an up-to-date database with all the network information published in real-time.

Chapter 3

Aim and Objectives

The main goal of this research work is the empowerment of multi-tenant B5G infrastructures with AI capabilities able to perform the self-governance in the selection of optimal network control function technologies and configurations. Additionally, the concrete application of such self-governance capabilities for the selection of the optimal firewall technology to protect infrastructures against cyber-attacks. Such self-governance and automation includes the creation of an architecture with data extraction, dataset generation and labelling in a multi-tenant 5G network infrastructure. The objective of such architecture is to be generic enough to be used for other real AI-driven up-to-date challenges in B5G.

In order to address the aim outlined above, a total of nine objectives have been identified, presented and undertaken.

- **Objective 1:** To design, implement, test and deploy a network monitoring tool for extracting all existing metrics from three different multi-technology NCF, during the first year. These NCF include iptables, Linux Traffic Control and Open Virtual Switch. The tool's functionalities include metric definition, real-time monitoring and publication of metrics on a message broker, maintaining data consistency with the rest of the network components.
- **Objective 2:** To design, implement, test and deploy a real-time online infrastructure-level dataset extractor tool for intent-based network data during the first year. The

dataset is infrastructure-level as it will contain data from each of the layers of the considered architecture: network device, network interface and datapath technologies. The data is intent-based as it reflects the state of the network architecture based on policies associated with intents. The extraction tool will gather information from multiple network sensors from the 3 network layers, and compile it on a single CSV file.

- **Objective 3:** To prototype, design and implement a manual labelling tool during the first year tailored for network infrastructure-level datasets, featuring a dashboard that visualises at least 30 key network metrics and allows instant labelling of instances. The tool will not only be used for labelling the intent-based data collected in Objective 2 with optimal technology selection but also for providing a dashboard where to represent, understand and visualise such data.
- **Objective 4:** Using outcomes from Objectives 1, 2 and 3, to compile a comprehensive dataset of 4 different multi-tenant B5G infrastructure topologies and 3 NCF technologies within 1 year. Several scenarios will be performed in order to incorporate at least 10,000 data instances to ensure dataset richness.
- **Objective 5:** To perform the manual labelling of the dataset obtained in Objective 4 for optimal datapath technology selection within 3 months, covering 3 different NCF options (iptables, TC and OVS) and 5,000 labelled instances to ensure comprehensive representation.
- **Objective 6:** To design, implement, test and deploy a generative AI-driven conditional tabular data framework within 6 months, covering the sampling of new synthetic data using 4 different generative algorithms. The framework will allow the comparison of different types of generative algorithms, from traditional copula-based models to state-of-the-art neural network-based models, so that the best one can be selected to be used as a tool to enrich the initially generated data.

- **Objective 7:** To generate a balanced dataset for optimal firewall technology selection within 1 month using the conditional data generator framework from Objective 6. The synthetic data obtained will be used to oversample minority classes of the dataset obtained in Objective 5, resulting in at least 10,000 total instances.
- **Objective 8:** To design, implement, test and deploy an AI predictive classifier generator framework for tabular data within 2 months, incorporating the training, evaluation and automated tuning capabilities of at least 4 popular supervised ML algorithms nowadays. This framework will facilitate the selection of the best ML algorithm to use, as it automates the entire AI process in a single software component.
- **Objective 9:** To design, implement, test and validate an AI classifier model able to predict automatically the optimal firewall technology within 2 months, achieving at least 95% accuracy in less than 1 second of training time. To accomplish this objective, the classifier generator framework obtained from Objective 8 will be used to obtain the best performing ML algorithm.

Table 3.1 represents the mapping between these research objectives and the thesis' outcomes. These outcomes are explained at the beginning of the document. It can be seen that different objectives are related to several outcomes and, conversely, several outcomes are associated with the same objective. When there is a relationship between them, it is coloured green.

Table 3.1 Mapping between research objectives and outcomes.

		Outcomes													
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Objectives	1														
	2														
	3														
	4														
	5														
	6														
	7														
	8														
	9														

Additionally, Fig. 3.1 represents the dependency between outcomes in the thesis. The arrows represent a direct dependence. The outcomes are divided into four categories: publications, software (blue), algorithms (orange) and datasets (grey). Furthermore, the horizontal axis indicates the order in time in which these outcomes took place.

Fig. 3.1 Dependency between outcomes.

Chapter 4

Methodology

This chapter presents the methodology followed in this dissertation to accomplish the previously defined aim and objectives. For this purpose, the type of research method used, what was done and how it was done are described. The methodology is accompanied by several tables and diagrams that help to understand the development of the thesis throughout the entire research period.

Given the nature of the research problem addressed in this dissertation, the methodology employed relies on quantitative analysis. This quantitative research was mainly carried out through two strategies: the implementation of controlled experiments and the collection of data through case studies [53]. Both approaches were lab-based conducted, with the data collected from them analysed to showcase the suitability and feasibility of the proposed solution. Figure 4.1 presents the organisation of the methodology in several phases and tasks. Specifically, the methodology was divided into 5 distinct phases (ordered using Roman numerals in the figure), each with several associated tasks. Each phase has an associated background colour and description. In addition, each of the tasks has a number (red circle) that indicates the objective referred to in the task. Descriptions of each are provided below.

- **Phase I:** Planning, gap identification, analysis of requirements and design.
 - Task 1: This task involved an in-depth analysis of the state of the art of each of the particular topics of the thesis. Such state of the art was accompanied by a

Fig. 4.1 Methodology: organisation of work into phases and tasks. Interdependence between tasks and associated objectives (red circles).

phase of knowledge acquisition related to B5G networks, specifically network softwarisation, management and network control functions, firewall technologies, autonomous networks, synthetic data generation, ML-based classifiers, and etcetera. This task was conducted throughout the whole period of the thesis, since at the beginning of each phase it was necessary to acquire new knowledge and to review the literature of such specific phase.

- Task 2: The purpose of this task was to identify all possible data (metadata and metrics) related to the Edge and Core segments of a B5G network in order to collect as much information as possible on the current status of the network. The focus of this task was to analyse and identify all existing metrics related to

multi-technology NCF. The outcome of this task was a clear description of each of the features to be used in the future AI component for the optimal selection of NCF technology. Furthermore, this task carried out the design of a network monitoring tool for obtaining those metrics. This network component needed to be aligned with the already working closed-loop framework of our lab-based B5G network.

- Task 3: This task included the design of a novel tool able to extract real-time data from the B5G network and to compile it into a dataset. Similarly to the design of task 2, this network component had to be designed in such a way that it could be integrated into the existing system.
- Task 4: The outcome of this task was the design of a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to represent in a dashboard all the features identified in task 2. The design also included the capability to specify the possible targets for labelling the dataset and the action of labelling it.
- Task 5: This task included the design of a management system integrating all network components for the generation of networking datasets. This included all network sensors, actuators, database, message bus, etc., necessary for the execution of control functions in the network.
- Task 6: The objective of this task was to design different topologies and multi-tenant B5G scenarios in order to have a wide variety of experiments to collect the dataset from.
- Task 7: The outcome of this task was the design of two different AI-based tools for tabular data. The first one, the design of a tool for generating tabular and conditional data. The second one, the design of a tool for generating ML models based on tabular networking data.

It is worth noting that some interdependencies between tasks in this phase have not been specified in Figure 4.1 for the sake of simplicity. Such is the case of task 3, which has a direct dependency with task 5.

- **Phase II:** Implementation and empirical validation.
 - Task 8: This task encompassed the implementation, testing and empirical validation of the network monitoring tool for multi-technology NCF designed in task 2.
 - Task 9: This task comprised the implementation, testing and empirical validation of the dataset extraction tool designed in task 3.
 - Task 10: This task included the implementation, testing and empirical validation of the visualising and labelling tool prototyped in task 4.

- **Phase III:** Experiment and use cases integration, deployment and automation.
 - Task 11: The purpose of this task was to test, integrate and deploy all software components delivered in tasks 8, 9 and 10 together with other components already in our testbed. As a result of this task, an automated framework capable of deploying the management system automatically, ready to launch experiments and generate datasets, was obtained.
 - Task 12: The outcome of this task was the generation of several multi-tenant 5G network topologies in which to deploy the management system. Additionally, multiple scenarios varying certain basic network parameters were implemented, so that there would be enough variability to have a rich dataset.

- **Phase IV:** Experiment execution and dataset refinement.
 - Task 13: Once the dataset extraction framework and the scenarios to be run were automated, the specific dataset was generated for the chosen use case: the selection of the optimal firewall technology. As a result of this task, numerous networking datasets were obtained. The validity of these datasets needed to be checked.
 - Task 14: This task was based on checking that the data obtained in the previous task were valid. This step was critical in the dataset generation process, as on

numerous occasions it was necessary to return to tasks 8, 9 and 11 to improve these outcomes respectively and to solve bugs.

- Task 15: Once the data were valid, the next step was to check their completeness in terms of features. This process was iterative and incremental, as missing features were found in every iteration of the task. So, when a missing feature was detected, it was necessary to go back to tasks 8 and 9 to extract these new metrics. In addition, it was essential to continue with task 10 to represent that new field in the labelling tool. Finally, it was necessary to go back to tasks 11 and 12 to integrate these new changes in the management system. Finally, tasks 13 and 14 had to be performed again, to reflect these new features in the dataset. Once no further required changes were detected, the final dataset was labelled. To do so, the labelling tool, which was the outcome from task 10, was used. Due to the large amount of data collected in the experiments, undersampling methods were used to achieve a reduced dataset and to label it.
 - Task 16: The goal of this task was to check if all classes of the target feature were balanced in the dataset. This task's outcome was to identify the minority classes and to found oversampling methods to overcome the problem. This task triggered task 7.
- **Phase V:** AI-based experimentation and deployment with tabular data.
 - Task 17: To address the problem of data imbalance, synthetic tabular data generation methods were chosen. The outcome of this task was the implementation and empirical validation of a data generation framework, where it was possible to choose which generative method to use from a variety of algorithms and which conditions to select to sample the synthetic data.
 - Task 18: This task consisted of generating a balanced dataset using an AI-based conditional generative model. The framework from task 17 was used in order to generate multiple types of generative conditional tabular models and to compare their performance and results.

- Task 19: The final step was to choose an algorithm capable of accurately predicting one of the control technologies available in the network. Due to the large number of AI algorithms available nowadays, a framework capable of testing multiple algorithms and comparing them was implemented. The algorithms selected were ML-based, as we were dealing with tabular data and the nature of such data was not complex.
- Task 20: This final task delivered a ML classifier able to predict the optimal technology for NCF. To this end, this task consisted of training, testing and comparing several algorithms using the outcome of task 19. The model that provided the best results in predicting the desired target was selected.

To conclude with the methodology chapter, Table 4.1 identifies each objective over the three years of the PhD studies. Each year is divided into four quartiles, for a period of 3 months. Each coloured cell corresponds to a time period in which an objective was achieved. It is worth mentioning that several objectives were undertaken in parallel throughout the progress of the dissertation due to the connection between them. In addition, the numbers in the cells indicate the completion of a specific outcome. The writing period is also included in the table.

Table 4.1 Gantt chart: timeline of objectives and identification of outcomes.

		2021		2022				2023				2024		
		Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	
Objectives	1		5											
	2			6										
	3				1, 7									
	4									2, 8				
	5									9				
	6											10		
	7												3, 11, 12	
	8													13
	9													4, 14
Thesis writing														

Chapter 5

Architecture with Data Extraction and Labelling framework

This chapter and all its contributions are directly related to outcome number 1, the accepted journal article entitled “NetLabeller: Architecture with data extraction and labelling framework for beyond 5G networks” [3]. In addition to the information available to the associated journal, the design of the network monitoring tool has been included in this chapter to provide a complete coherent plot line of this work. The objectives associated are 1, 2, 3 and 4.

5.1 Introduction

Self-optimisation capabilities in 5G networks require advanced network control. Network control involves functions such as the generation of network policies and the subsequent execution of those policies, requiring less human intervention and effort [54, 55]. The anatomy of such policy (or control rule, indistinctly) consists mainly of two differentiating parts. Firstly, the matching part is used to determine which packets/network flows the rule will apply to. Secondly, the targets are used to determine what will be done with those packets/flows [42]. The dynamic generation of such rules imposes a level of complexity for the understanding of these rules that is very difficult to process in acceptable response times even for the most expert network administrators. This problem is exacerbated when it is

foreseen the ultra-fast next-generation network such as 100GbE networks where the latency budget is very reduced, in terms of 1 nanosecond.

As a result, our network control policies are far from being optimised for several reasons, as introduced in Chapter 1. First, the vast majority of network control systems rely on the usage of only one particular datapath technology to perform the enforcement of such control, for example, OpenFlow [56] or XDP [57]. By doing so, these solutions are simply ignoring the benefits or drawbacks that can be brought by using a wider set of technologies available for the same purpose. Second, when network control rules are enforced into the system, they are already applied and considered the best decision taken. This fact clearly ignores the possibility of optimising such already enforced rules by i) making use of a more efficient datapath technology; ii) rewriting the rule in a more efficient way; or iii) reallocating the rule in a more efficient place. Third, the selection of the datapath technology used to enforce the rule, if any, simply ignores the current state of the system. Leveraging insights into the network's current state, one can make informed decisions to effectively utilise existing resources while simultaneously maximising the quality of user experience. And fourth, it is crucial to note that the decision-making process regarding the selection of datapath technology often neglects the significant considerations of bandwidth, packet losses, and latency associated with the chosen technology. Consequently, situations arise when the desired quality of services cannot be fulfilled due to decisions regarding technology selection.

The use of AI can significantly address this current deficiency in optimising network policies. AI can make the continuous optimisation of control rules feasible when it is combined with a high level of automation [58]. In this way, the AI can generate decisions considering all available possibilities. Not only considering all possibilities related to the type of technology to use, but also the state of the network at any given moment. This AI-native approach enables the network to be agile, intelligent and able to learn and self-adapt to changing network conditions [59]. In addition, these decisions will be made much faster than if compared to any human network expert. This speed is essential, especially when these network policies are intended to deal with network attacks, one of the most important concerns of 5G operators nowadays [60].

To achieve so, it is essential to first learn which datapath technology is the most appropriate for each specific use case. This decision will depend on multiple factors, in particular, the state of the network at any given time, the type of rule to be enforced and the number of rules currently enforced in every datapath technology. For example, in a use case where a drop rule is desired to be optimised, we will prioritise speed of execution, choosing datapath technologies located at the lowest point in the software stack, such as XDP. Another example in the same scenario, taking into account other criteria such as having a lot of rules enforced in XDP, we could optimise the insertion of a new rule using a faster one such as OVS. Considering all these variables and the range of applicable use cases in a B5G, it is imperative to have a novel framework with the necessary tools to monitor it. This will allow to extract as much information as possible regarding network status, control and management [61]. Developing a framework with these characteristics will allow to access to network metrics, metadata, network topology, and rule-specific information, thereby enabling the generation of comprehensive datasets. These datasets will enhance the knowledge of what is the state of the network and how is it performing. Subsequently, such datasets can be utilised to extract multitude of insights. Also, to identify potential patterns that can facilitate the labelling process. To the best of our knowledge, it has not been encountered any existing framework that adequately addresses the extraction, storage, and labelling of the current state of a network infrastructure.

The previous challenges have motivated this chapter. The following list enumerates the contributions included in it:

1. To provide a novel architecture to allow the monitoring, extraction, analysis and labelling of data from a B5G network.
2. To perform the analysis of different network features among the immense number of available metrics in the network related to interfaces, flows, devices, queues, rules, etcetera.
3. To provide a novel mechanism to allow the visualisation of network-related datasets that will help to perform the labelling process.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows: Section 5.2 provides a state of art in available frameworks for visualising and labelling network-related datasets. Section 5.3 introduces the architecture proposed to fulfil our contribution along with an overview of data flow in a B5G network infrastructure. Section 5.4 provides the analysis of the most relevant network features that will compose the 5G networking dataset. Section 5.6 presents the design of our contribution, emphasising the workflow and the necessary elements for the correct functioning of the framework. Section 5.7 provides the implementation details in terms of hardware and software used for the deployment of the framework and the testbed used for executing the experiments. Section 5.8 presents some analytical experiment results of the framework proposed and its performance. Finally, conclusions are drawn with future research activities outlined in Section 5.9.

5.2 Related Work

This section focuses on the search for related work similar to that presented in this chapter. Therefore, it is first analysed frameworks for joint data extraction and labelling in 5G networks. In the absence of frameworks with such specific characteristics, the analysis is then carried out only on labelling tools available in the literature.

5.2.1 Data extraction frameworks

The search for frameworks that included data extraction and network labelling has been carried out. The explicit methodology for searching such related work has been the following. First, the search was conducted in major scientific research sources in the field of Computer Science, namely, IEEE Xplore, Elsevier via Scopus and SpringerLink. In addition, we performed the same search on GitHub, for extending the search to code-based results. Second, we performed the same advanced search with the following terms: "Network dataset" AND "labelling tool" AND "labeller" AND "5G". The results were restricted to articles and conferences in the period of the last 10 years, i.e. from 2014 to 2023. The results obtained were as follows. Elsevier obtained 95 results, after reading their title, any reader

can easily see that none of them are related to our work and that the search engine is not as accurate as other engines. The same was the case for the 2 results obtained on SpringerLink and the other 2 on GitHub. All of them were out of the context of our research work. Two results relevant to our subject were found on IEEE Xplore. Lee et al. presented in [62] a network collector system, data analyser and a 5G-based labelled dataset. Similarly, Lee et al. proposed a system that performs data labelling, filtering, preprocessing, and learning for 5G network flow and security event data [63]. Despite being closely related strategies, the authors do not present an in-depth analysis of these framework' performance to compare with.

5.2.2 Data labelling tools

Supervised ML algorithms need tools that make the labelling process as fast, easy, accessible and effective as possible for data engineers. Table 5.1 compares the key features addressed in this section that are essential to be present in a labelling framework in order to fulfil the innovations characteristics mentioned in the previous section. Such comparison is done with respect to the state of the art and the analysis presented has led to the identification of some gaps described below. The features have been classified into six categories: Data Visualisation, related to the way that data is visualised; Data Labelling, related to the fact whether the tool has the functionality to label datasets or not; Dataset type, describing the different data types that are possible to represent and label using the framework; Input: related to the data source given as input to the framework; Output: describes the labelled dataset format, focusing on CSV; and finally, open source and license. Each category sub-types are numbered from 1 to 18 due to space limitations and their respective description together with an explanation of the feature is shown in Table 5.2. Table 5.1 also shows a logical grouping of some of the analysed research works using roman numbers for such grouping purpose.

The first group (see group I in Table 5.1) represents some recent research focused on the visualisation and exploration of different-purpose datasets. For example, Stopar et al. [64] presents an interactive web-based visualisation tool called StreamStory that helps to interpret and analyse data coming from time-varying systems such as weather, Global

Table 5.1 Comparison of different labelling tools (np: not provided).

		Data Visualisation				Data Labelling			Dataset Type						Input	Output	Other		
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
I	[64]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	np	✗	✓	np
	[65]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	-	✗	✓	np
	[66]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	Tabular	✗	✓	BSD-3-Clause
II	[67]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	Media	✗	✓	np
	[68]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	Media	✓	✓	Apache 2.0
	[69]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	Media	✓	✓	Apache 2.0
	[70]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	Media	✗	✓	Open source*
III	[71]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	np	Tabular	✓	✓	AGPLv3
	[72]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	np	Elasticsearch	✓	✓	Elastic 2.0
	[73]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	Tabular	✓	✗	np
IV	[74]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	np	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	np	np	✓	MIT
	Our	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	Tabular	✓	✓	Apache 2.0

Positioning System (GPS) and wind data. The purpose is to provide a high-level conceptual summary of such data, allowing users to interactively identify and interpret large multivariate time series datasets. Another example is the provided by Philip et al. [65], whose work presents an exploratory and visual data analysis for diabetes disease datasets. The analytic is implemented in the R programming language and represents the first steps in a framework development, but it has not been implemented at the end. Finally, an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) process of COVID-19 data was carried out by Dsouza and Velan S. [66] using the Python libraries Matplotlib and Seaborn. These three research works reveal two key points: i) there is a tendency to perform EDA on datasets as a step before labelling data and ii) the lack of tools that allow visual analysis and labelling of the data being observed in the same software.

Therefore, the next group analysed (see group II in Table 5.1) corresponds to specific labelling data tools. Four different labelling tools have been examined: Colabeler [67], Label Studio [68], DAML [69] and Diffgram [70]. As is shown in Table 5.1, some of them allow to include graphs, and user interactive visualisations. Furthermore, multi-feature dashboards

Table 5.2 Description of the characteristics analysed in Table I.

Classification capabilities			Description
Data Visualization	1	Graphs	The tool has the functionality to add graphs.
	2	Data Exploration Visualisations	The tool allows the user to explore and interact with the data being displayed.
	3	Multi-Feature Dashboard	The dashboard allows displaying multiple features.
	4	Dashboard Personalisation	The tool allows the user to personalize the dashboard.
Data Labelling	5	Dataset labelling	The tool allows the user to label the dataset displayed.
	6	Cooperative Labelling	The tool has functionalities that enable collaborative labelling.
	7	Automatic Label Navigation	During the labelling process, the tool automatically moves on to the next instance to be labelled.
Dataset type Support	8	Multi-modal Data	The dataset contains features coming from more than one data representation mode.
	9	Multi-Feature Data	The dataset contains more than one feature.
	10	Time-Series Data	The dataset contains features coming from a series of data points indexed in time order.
	11	Discrete Feature Data	The dataset has features that come from a limited number of values.
	12	Continuous Feature Data	The dataset has features that come from an unlimited number of values.
	13	Multi-media	The dataset has features that come from image, audio, animation, graphics, etc.
Input	14	Streaming Support	The dataset is being consumed from a streaming data source
	15	Format	Describes the different formats the dataset can have.
Output	16	Format	Identifies whether the output data is exported in CSV format.
Other	17	Open Source	Describes whether the software is designed to be publicly accessible.
	18	License	Specifies the type of legally binding guidelines for the use and distribution of the software. (*) It has also Enterprise options.

are common in all of them. Remarkably, all of them are very sophisticated in terms of data labelling characteristics, allowing them to be used by more than one person at once or to move to the next item to be labelled automatically. They allow all types of media as input format: images, audio, CSV, JSON and etc. Finally, recall that all these tools are open source. The results show that there is high popularity in labelling tools whose purpose is to label multi-media datasets, such as images, videos and text, but there is a clear lack of labelling tools whose purpose is other different from these three ones.

For the reason mentioned above, some visualisation tools (see group III in Table 5.1) have been examined in which it is possible to create personalised dashboards. Visualisation frameworks such as Grafana, examined by Chakraborty and Kundan [71], Kibana, studied by Sharma [72] or Google Looker Studio, Snipes [73], are appropriate in terms of visualising time-series, discrete and continuous data in complex dashboards. Furthermore, they allow

a wide range of input data types. These frameworks would be suitable for our purpose if it were not for the fact that they do not allow the labelling of the data being displayed. Finally, Chegini et al. [74] present a system called mVis as a visual analytical approach that allows interactively labelling datasets. This system is the closest to what it is being looked for in this research because it facilitates interactive visual interfaces for data exploration, allowing the meaningful selection and labelling of records based on insights gained by the user. The tool has many graphs to represent the data, but on the downside, it is not possible to customise a dashboard or add data that is not representable in a form of a graph.

As the reader can see, from the state of the art no research work delivering a proper framework that facilitates network data extraction, visualising and labelling has been found.

5.3 Architecture for Data Extraction and Labelling

This section presents the proposed architecture including the new contributions associated to this chapter over the B5G network infrastructure presented in Figure 2.2. The managed infrastructure (B5G network architecture in a multi-tenant environment) has been omitted for the sake of simplicity. Figure 5.1 represents the control plane of the B5G network, where the network components explained in Section 2.5.2 are placed (see grey rectangles in the figure). As previously explained, this architecture executes autonomously the enforcement and monitoring of network control policies, coming from intents. It is worth noting that the step of inserting the intents into the network is omitted to simplify the figure. Additionally, the management layer keeps an up-to-date database with all the network information published in real-time.

Two green labels have been included in Figure 5.1 to highlight the contributions added in the architecture. The first one at the bottom, related to the monitoring of network components, in which new monitoring metrics have been added to the RMA software. The second one at the top of the figure, related to the data extraction and labelling of network metrics. These components are explained below.

Fig. 5.1 Overview of the proposed data extraction and labelling architecture.

5.3.1 Data Monitoring

Multiple network agents were already integrated in our lab-based network. One of the network components in charge of the network monitoring is the RMA component. As shown in label 1 of Figure 5.1, this component provides information regarding resource metrics. These resources are: devices, network interfaces and datapath technologies. First, RMA needs the network topology information in order to know the different resources from which to extract information. It then performs the extraction. Once the data is obtained, the RMA adapts the information in JSON format and publishes it on the message bus.

5.3.2 Data Storage

In this step, the network topology and metrics information are consumed by the Data Collector component (see 2 in Fig. 5.1). This component extracts the information published in the message bus by the loop agents, adapts the data and stores it into a database. Note that the information associated with the control policy to be optimised is also stored. The architecture is generic enough to make use of any SQL and non-SQL database. As a result, this step generates and updates a database with all the network information published in real-time. It is important to mention that both topology and metrics have associated metadata to each of the values in order to allow the identification of the producer of the data (see `monitoringResourceId` in Listing 5.1), the source of the data (`monitoredResourceId`), the time the data have been produced (`reportedTime`) and other relevant metadata information shown in Listing 5.1.

```
"MetricSample": [  
  {  
    "monitoringResourceId": "QG54TY8U",  
    "monitoredResourceId": "YTR56HJ8",  
    "metricName": "devicePortSpeed",  
    "metricValue": "1000000",  
    "startSamplingTime": 1659107373856,  
    "resourceId": "4BA92944",  
    "reportedTime": 1659106981511  
  }  
]
```

Listing 5.1 Example of the metadata stored in the database associated to a metric.

5.3.3 Data Extraction and Labelling

The next step involves both Data Extraction and Data Labelling where data is extracted, shaped, sorted and adapted to CSV format ready for future AI steps. To achieve so, firstly, the Infrastructure Data Extractor manager (IDEM) connects with the database and carries

out a continuous loop of queries to extract the selected data periodically (see 3 in Fig. 5.1). Then, the data is sorted and written in a CSV file, which is represented as the unlabelled dataset in Figure 5.1 (see 4). A new instance of the CSV file is generated each time the data is extracted. The dataset contains as many columns as features selected and as many rows as instances have been written.

As a supervised machine learning problem will be faced, once the dataset is completed, it is necessary to label each instance of it. This process must be done manually by a network expert and ideally with the help of a tool that facilitates the visualisation of each of the values in the CSV file. The labelling tool NetLabeller is in charge of this task, allowing the visualisation of the values in a user interface that allows labelling each of the instances of the dataset. As a result of this phase, the dataset is labelled and ready to be used in supervised learning (see 5 in Fig. 5.1). It is worth mentioning that the labelling is carried out in an offline phase although it is presented in the network infrastructure with the rest of the components.

5.4 Networking data analysis

In order to a better explanation of the usage of the proposed architecture, this section aims to indicate a concrete problem to be addressed by an AI model as a running example throughout the whole chapter. However, it is worth indicating that the proposed architecture is generic and not tailored to any particular use-case. Therefore, this proposed infrastructure holds potential for application in various other AI-driven use cases.

As mentioned in Section 2.4, modern infrastructures today have at their disposal multiple datapath technologies through which to perform network control functions. It causes a lot of confusion as it is incredibly difficult for network administrators to determine which one is the best technology to implement a concrete network control policy (or rule). This is because it depends on a significantly wide number of parameters such as the current status of the system, the anatomy of the rule and its usage, and other related metrics and metadata. Thus, this is where an AI model can help to determine which one is the best technology to materialise a given network control rule in a given acceptable response time. For the present

use-case example, the output of the model will be the optimal datapath technology for every enforced rule on the network.

5.4.1 Analysis of features

This section provides an analysis of different network metrics related to the Edge and Core segments of a B5G network selected for the use-case proposed. The characteristics come from each network element (hardware and software) capable of reporting any information related to the control and data plane. This information includes the actual status about network flows, network devices, network interfaces, network queues and network rules.

As the optimal datapath technology is desired to be selected depending on the state of the network, the vast majority of the metrics are associated with network interfaces. Such network interface will be henceforth referred to indistinctly as Device Port. Furthermore, each datapath technology for network control available in each Device Port will be henceforth referred to as Datapath Point. Figure 5.2 represents a simplification of a physical network interface with some datapath technologies represented as orange dots. It is worth noting that just a high-level overview of the stages of the ingress data path is provided. The reader can refer to Section 2.4 for details.

Fig. 5.2 Identification of the data flow through different datapath technologies of a network interface (input path).

The data flow goes through the network interface crossing each datapath technology as indicated by the arrow. The reader can see in Fig. 5.2 the firmware used to refer to hardware-offloading rules. The driver is to refer to those rules enforced before the packet arrives at the kernel network stack. Then, the traditional kernel datapath points within the Linux kernel

that allows packet filtering, network address translation (NAT), and other network-related operations. Examples are TC used to deal with Quality of Service rules, the OVS bridge control and the iptables control.

The feature analysis is done in a top-down approach, starting with device features, then device port features, datapath technology features, queues and finally, features related to network flows and rules. Figure 5.3 shows a device, i.e. a physical or a virtual machine in purple, with a device port coloured in grey. The device port depicted in this example contains two different datapath technologies coloured in yellow as a mere simplification to improve readability. Each datapath point may or may not have rules enforced for every packet that traverses it. These rules are represented in the figure in red. Arrows represent the direction of data flow: ingress and egress. Figure 5.3 also presents 34 features located in both the bottom and the top part of the figure. They are coming from these components and are coloured with the same colour of the entity they belong to. This allows the reader to understand if they are metrics related to device, device port, datapath points, rules, queues or flows. They have been divided into control plane features and data plane features, which will be explained in detail in the following subsections.

The control plane is responsible for making decisions about how data should be managed, routed, and processed within the network, while the data plane is responsible for the actual movement of packets from source to destination. The data plane operates based on the decisions made by the control plane. Thus, control plane features focus on decision-making efficiency, technology rule's metadata and network components status, and data plane features emphasise packet forwarding rates, throughput, and QoS enforcement.

5.4.2 Data plane feature metrics

Data plane metrics are depicted in the lower part of Figure 5.3 (number 16 to 34). Within network metrics, we can distinguish between received (RX) and Transmitted (TX) network metrics. These metrics can be bytes or packets. In the diagram, different types of queues are schematically represented according to the datapath technology concerned. For instance, Datapath Point 1 has a single transmit and receive queue. For simplicity, the receive and

Fig. 5.3 Identification of 5G network features in different network resource levels: device, device port, datapath technology, flows and queues.

transmit queues are represented as a single queue. On the other hand, as shown in the figure, Datapath Point 2 has two queues for reception and two for transmission.

Starting with flow metrics, the type of encapsulation and the sense is included. By analysing the encapsulation type and flow direction, we can determine the behaviour of different traffic types and understand how they impact network performance. Also, the size of each packet of the flow and the total packets is gathered. With the use of these two metrics we can calculate the overall data volume transmitted. This information helps in analysing bandwidth utilisation and identifying potential bottlenecks or congestion points. Focusing now on the metrics related to datapath points, both packets and bytes transmitted and received per second have been selected. Packets dropped describe dropped packets of data not reaching their destination during data transmission. This group of metrics gives us

insights into whether there is network congestion. The packets dropped per second indicate if the network traffic is hitting its maximum limit at the moment, while the total packets dropped specifies the idea of how often the network reaches its limit and needs to drop packets. Regarding rule metrics, it is essential to know how many packets and bytes are matching each rule in total (total matched packets and bytes), at the moment (current matched packets and bytes) and on average. These metrics can be compared with the datapath point metrics to determine what percentage of packets are being matched compared to all packets passing through the network. This gives us an idea of the rule efficiency. The last matched time indicates when the last time a packet was matched. Finally, the activated rule time specifies how many seconds has a rule been activated. We conclude the data plane metrics with the queue current usage, which describes how congested each of the queues of a datapath point is. This metric, when compared to the maximum values described in the control plane, can estimate whether the network is in a nearly congested state that will lead to packet loss.

5.4.3 Control plane feature metrics

Control plane feature metrics are depicted in the upper part of Figure 5.3 (number 1 to 15). Device metrics are represented in purple. The `IsPhysical` represents whether the device is physical or logical/virtual. This feature has some relevance for technology selection, since it has already been mentioned above that certain datapath points are not found in virtual network interfaces. Device metrics also include context switching related to the number of times the Central Processing Unit (CPU) is performing context switching between processes. Device port metrics are represented in grey. The device port speed indicates the port's NIC. Knowing the speed limit of the NIC can be helpful to diagnose performance issues related to the bandwidth and the performance expected. Datapath point metrics are depicted in yellow. The Datapath Point NIC Speed is included as it may differ from the device port speed. The time search complexity represents the difficulty in terms of the time it takes for a datapath technology to locate a rule. Some datapath technologies have lists of rules, for example, TC or OVS, some others have hash-maps or Ternary Content Address Memory (TCAM) structures to deal with the time search complexity.

In addition, several datapath technologies provide support for network queues. Therefore, queue metrics are also included in the diagram, coloured in white. They indicate how many queues the datapath technology has (Number queues), the length of each queue (Queue length), the maximum bandwidth of the queue and the queue discipline, which describes the scheduling algorithm determining the formation of a queue or queues [75]. The information related to the queues will give us an idea of the maximum capacities of the queues and their respective limits.

We conclude with the control features introducing the ones related to the rules. The rule technology specifies the datapath technology, which could be any of those shown in Figure 5.2 or another one. For our concrete AI model, this will be in fact the label we want to infer. The rule description includes extra information about the rule, such as the action type and the action name. To avoid reaching the maximum number of enforced rules, it is necessary to know the maximum number of rules that can be inserted in each datapath point. This value, together with the number of rules activated in total, will give an idea of how much percentage of rule resources are used/available. The rule sense indicates whether the packets to be affected are ingress or egress packets. Finally, the rule complexity represents a value that measures the complexity of the rule to be enforced (the longer, the most complex).

The reader can understand the effort underneath carried out in order to design, discover, understand, prototype and refine the system able to extract all these sources of heterogeneous features in order to allow to have enough data to be used for training purposes in AI-models. This is probably the first manuscript we have found in the literature with this deep reveal of the network metrics involved in the decision taking process of network control technology selection. It is worth remarking that all the metrics collected are related to L2-L7 of the OSI stack and there is not any attempt to gather L1 metrics, mainly relevant to wireless interfaces. This is because we are currently focused on Edge and Core network segments of the B5G infrastructure.

Fig. 5.4 Design of the resource monitoring agent.

5.5 Design of the Network Resource Monitoring tool

Figure 5.4 shows the architectural design of the RMA component, which allows the monitoring of network resources. In order for the agent to produce metrics, it is necessary that the user specifies the metric definitions of the desired metrics. These metric definitions are declared in a JSON file. There is one file per resource, as shown in the figure. Its design makes it fully configurable and scalable, as new metrics can be added by simply including them in the metric definition files. An example of a metric definition can be seen in Listing 5.2.

```
{
  "MonitoringRules": [
    {
      "command": "./TC_rx_bytes_seconds.sh {iface}",
      "metricDefinitionName": "TC_RX_bytes_seconds",
      "metricDefinitionResourceType": "DATAPATH_POINT",
      "metricDefinitionProgrammableTechnology": "TRAFFIC_CONTROL",
      "metricDefinitionPublicationChannel": "METRICS",
      "metricStoreType": "HISTOGRAM",
    }
  ]
}
```

```
"metricRepresentationType": "GAUGE",  
"metricUnit": "bytes/s",  
"metricUnitType": "LONG",  
"samplingPeriod": 5,  
"reportOnlyChanges": true,  
"reportingType": "PERIODIC",  
},  
]  
}
```

Listing 5.2 Example of a metric definition. Resource type: Datapath Technology

RMA component needs to be implemented with a message bus. It is both consumer and producer. RMA is subscribed to the topology exchange of the message bus. It should be noted that this exchange is produced by RIA (software component explained in Section 2.5.2). Through this exchange, the agent has a real-time record of all network resources.

The Metric Definition Module is in charge of extracting the metric definitions from the files and inserting them in the Monitoring Engine. This engine needs three essential information: i) a record of the metrics to extract (metric definitions), ii) the real-time topology and iii) the scripts that correspond to the metric definitions. The configuration file specifies different user-configurable parameters, such as how often to extract metrics, from which type of resource to extract them or how many threads the component should use.

Once the RMA receives topology information, the workflow is as follows. The Monitoring Engine maps each of the metric definitions with its script to obtain the result. There is a monitoring engine per resource. These are device, device port (network interface) and datapath technology. Then, a thread is created that executes the script in the kernel of the operating system. The response to that command is adapted, in a JSON, in the Metric Formatter module and sent to the metrics exchange. The RMA can handle in parallel as many metrics as threads specified in the configuration file.

As discussed in Chapter 2, this component has been extended to include technology-level metrics. Therefore, the implementation work carried out has been the creation of the metrics definition file and the elaboration of all the necessary scripts to extract them. That is, the

design and implementation of the files corresponding to each of the metrics for each type of technology. Listings 5.3 and 5.4 show an example of the implementation of the same metric for datapath technologies iptables and TC, respectively. The implementation work has also included the adaptation of existing code to include the monitoring engine of the datapath resource.

The code of the RMA component is available in our GitLab repository¹.

```
#!/bin/bash
B1='sudo iptables -t raw -nvxL | grep OUTPUT | awk '{print $7}''
echo $B1
```

Listing 5.3 Script to get the number of bytes transmitted in iptables.

```
if [ $# -eq 0 ]; then
    echo "No Interface provided"
    echo "[Usage] --> ./TC_tx_bytes.sh <interface>"
    exit
fi

if [[ ! -f "/sys/class/net/${1}/statistics/tx_bytes" ]]; then
    exit
fi

B1=$(sudo tc -s qdisc show dev "${1}" | awk '/root/ {getline; print
    $2;}')
echo "$B1"
```

Listing 5.4 Script to get the number of bytes transmitted in TC.

¹<https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/aserranouws/rma>

5.6 Design of the Data Extraction and Labelling Components

As shown in Figure 5.1, the management architecture is composed of two modules. This section will introduce in more detail the Data Extraction and Labelling module where the features described in the previous section are extracted, shaped and written in a dataset for a resulting EDA and labelling process. This process has been analysed mathematically in Section 5.6.1. Then, subsections 5.6.2 and 5.6.3 describe the design of the two components, these are the IDEM and NetLabeller. Both components provide, as a result, a CSV file. The IDEM produces a CSV file with all the metrics and metadata extracted in the network and the NetLabeller produces a CSV file with labels added to each instance. The labelled CSV file represents the networking dataset that will be used for AI purposes. Finally, in Section 5.6.4, a sequence diagram is presented to help the reader understand where all the data extracted by IDEM comes from.

5.6.1 Mathematical Analysis of proposed architecture

This section provides a pseudo-code-based algorithm for the proposed data extraction and labelling architecture. The primary focus lies in the dataset generation part. We first start with the definition of the origin of the different feature metrics as well as the resource they are associated with.

We define $\mathbb{M} = \{\mathbb{D}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{T}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{F}, \mathbb{R}\}$ as the set of metrics associated to the device port p where a rule R is enforced. The specification of all these metrics is detailed below.

\mathbb{D} corresponds to the b metrics associated with the device d on which the device port p is located. It is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{D} = \{D_1^p, \dots, D_b^p\} \quad (5.1)$$

\mathbb{P} corresponds to the c metrics associated with the device port p , given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{P} = \{P_1^p, \dots, P_c^p\} \quad (5.2)$$

\mathbb{T} corresponds to the f datapath technology metrics associated with the device port p from the x different datapath technologies available in p . It is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{T} = \{T_1^{1p}, \dots, T_f^{1p}, \dots, T_1^{xp}, \dots, T_f^{xp}\} \quad (5.3)$$

\mathbb{Q} corresponds to the g queue metrics for each of the q queues in the datapath technology x from the device port p . It is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{Q} = \{Q_1^{11p}, \dots, Q_g^{q1p}, Q_1^{12p}, \dots, Q_g^{q2p}, \dots, Q_1^{1xp}, \dots, Q_g^{qxp}\} \quad (5.4)$$

\mathbb{F} corresponds to the h flow metrics associated with the i flows affected by the rule R in the device port p . It is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{F} = \{F_1^{1pR}, \dots, F_h^{1pR}, \dots, F_1^{ipR}, \dots, F_h^{ipR}\} \quad (5.5)$$

\mathbb{R} corresponds to the j rule metrics associated with the rule R and enforced in the device port p . It is given by the following equation:

$$\mathbb{R} = \{R_1^{pR}, \dots, R_j^{pR}\} \quad (5.6)$$

The sets \mathbb{D} , \mathbb{P} , \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{Q} are provided by the RMA agent. The sets \mathbb{F} and \mathbb{R} are provided by the FCA agent.

Let I_t^{pR} be the instance corresponding to the extraction at time t of \mathbb{M} , given by the following equation:

$$I_t^{pR} = \{D_1^p, \dots, D_b^p, P_1^p, \dots, P_c^p, T_1^{1p}, \dots, T_f^{1p}, \dots, T_1^{xp}, \dots, T_f^{xp}, \\ Q_1^{11p}, \dots, Q_g^{11p}, Q_1^{12p}, \dots, Q_g^{12p}, \dots, Q_1^{1xp}, \dots, Q_g^{1xp}, \\ F_1^{1pR}, \dots, F_h^{1pR}, \dots, F_1^{ipR}, \dots, F_h^{ipR}, R_1^{pR}, \dots, R_j^{pR}\} \quad (5.7)$$

Then, Algorithm 1 represents the mathematical steps followed to perform the extraction and labelling in order to obtain the labelled dataset. Finally, note that \mathbb{I} corresponds to the unlabelled dataset, while \mathbb{L} to the labelled dataset.

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code algorithm for the extraction and labelling.

```

1: while  $n < \text{number\_extractions}$  do
2:   for  $R$  in available_R do
3:     extract  $I_t^{pR}$ 
4:     human assign target  $L_t = I_t^{pR}$ 
5:   end for
6:    $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 
7: end while
8:  $\mathbb{I} = \{I_1, I_2, \dots, I_z\}$  for a given  $R$  over a time  $z$ 
9:  $\mathbb{L} = \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_z\}$  for a given  $R$  over a time  $z$ 

```

As specified in line 4 of Algorithm 1, the time it takes to label the data is human-dependent. Therefore, this algorithm is always determined by the time it takes for the human to respond to the system. Assuming line 4 would be automatic, Algorithm 1 exhibits a time complexity of $O(n^2)$ in Big O notation, as there are two nested loops iterating. The first loop iterates n times, representing the number of iterations, and for each of these iterations, a second loop is executed, iterating r times, which represents the number of rules being monitored.

5.6.2 Infrastructure Data Extractor Manager

Figure 5.5 shows the architectural design of the IDEM component. The IDEM is responsible for data extraction and data adequacy. The user can specify in the configuration file the metrics to be extracted.

Fig. 5.5 Design of the Infrastructure Data Extractor manager.

Once the component is started, the following workflow proceeds. First, the database connection is made (see 0 in Fig. 5.5). Then, once the connection has been successfully made, it is time for data extraction. Note that the data reported by the software components (RIA, RMA, SMA, etc.) have already been populated in the database by means of the Data Collector.

The IDEM extraction engine (see 1 in Fig. 5.5) carries out several tasks. First, it makes a database query to obtain the topology of the network. Then, it performs in parallel the necessary queries to obtain all the features previously specified in the configuration file. One query to obtain the device information, another one to know the features of the device port and its datapath technologies. The third query is to obtain the flow features and, finally, the fourth one to obtain the metrics related to the rules currently enforced on the network. In addition, it connects to the configuration engine to store information related to whether the extraction has a finite number of instances to be extracted and, if so, how many to extract. It

is also responsible for monitoring a counter to keep track of the number of instances extracted so far.

When the extraction is finished, the output formatter module starts (see 2 in Fig. 5.5). It oversees writing all the features corresponding to an instance in each of the CSV files. Once the writing has finished, it is checked whether it was set to have finite iteration instances. If false, the extraction engine starts again, adding another instance to the counter. If true, the value of the counter and the number of iterations are compared. If it is the same, the extraction has finished and the exit agent stops the component. If not, data extraction continues. The result of the IDEM is a CSV file containing all the network features, which is represented in Figure 5.5 as the Unlabelled Dataset (see 3 in Fig. 5.5). This design allows quantifying streaming data in iterations that are used for training purposes. This is a key ingredient in addressing the streaming aspect associated with the dynamics of a fully functional network infrastructure.

Table 5.3 displays a sample of one instance of the dataset generated by the IDEM. Note that features are the ones described in Section 5.4 but additional network metrics could have been specified. It is also important to highlight that, for simplicity, only the metrics extracted from the TC datapath technology are being shown. Therefore, in a network interface where there are also e.g., IPTABLES and OVS, the number of features associated with the datapath would multiply.

Once the IDEM has finished, the unlabelled dataset is ready for the next step, to be labelled. With Table 5.3, reader can gain a profound understanding of the complexity involved in comprehending and labelling such a vast amount of data in the absence of a visualisation tool. It is therefore necessary to use a visualisation and labelling tool such as NetLabeller.

5.6.3 NetLabeller: Data Visualisation and Labelling Agent

NetLabeller is the labelling tool in charge of labelling the dataset. Figure 5.6 shows its design. NetLabeller is a GUI that allows the user to visually interact with a networking dataset and to direct label it. NetLabeller abstracts all the complexity that a user can find in a CSV file, as it

Feature name	Value	Feature name	Value
Is physical	0	Packet size	284
Context switches	9	Total pkt	8163
Device port speed	10 ⁹	TC RX pkt/sec	365
TC NIC speed	10 ⁹	TC RX bytes/sec	118260
Time search complex	8	TC RX pkts drop/sec	269
TC Number queues	1	TC TX pkt/sec	0
TC Queue length	1000	TC TX bytes/sec	0
TC Queue discipline	<i>noqueue</i>	TC TX pkts drop/sec	0
TC Queue Max bwd	—	Total matched pkts	109
Rule technology	<i>TC</i>	Current matched pkts	109
TC Maximum rules	4096	Avg matched pkts	109
Num rules activated	5	Last matched time	0
Rule description	<i>InsertDROP</i>	Total matched bytes	35316
Rule sense	<i>INGRESS</i>	Current matched bytes	35316
Rule complexity	3	Avg matched bytes	35316
Encapsulation	<i>gtp</i>	Activated rule time	0
Flow Sense	<i>INGRESS</i>	TC queue usage	—

Table 5.3 Sample of features extracted by IDEM in a concrete iteration.

transforms a bunch of values and commas into an interface that represents all those values in an orderly and visually arranged way. As it is shown in the figure, the design follows a Model-View-Controller (MVC) pattern. This pattern is based on the separation of the application domain model and the user interface in two layers, having the domain model being unaware of the user interface [76].

Once the application is started, the workflow follows the steps described below. First, the Configuration file is uploaded to the model engine. The Configuration file has the information about two important aspects. Firstly, about what CSV file to upload. This CSV file is called Unlabelled Dataset in the figure. Secondly, the labels and values for each label. This allows the user to customise the type of labelling and the value to be associated with each labelling,

Fig. 5.6 Design of the data visualisation and labelling tool.

allowing the tool to be used for distinct use cases where the target is different. For example, the user could have a multi-class problem whose classes are: TC, OVS and IPTABLES but wants to labelling them with the values 0, 1 and 2 respectively. Another example could be if the user wants to identify anomalies in the displayed traffic, so the labelling could be Benign or Malign and the values, 0 or 1.

The Model Engine loads all the values contained in the dataset at once and sends the first iteration to the view module to be displayed in the User Interface (UI). In the meanwhile, the View module loads the UI template in which the data from the Model will be displayed. Having the template and the data to be displayed, the View Module renders the GUI and displays it to the user. The View Module allows the user to (i) select the instance to be displayed, (ii) select the value to put in the label and (iii) save the dataset. The Controller oversees the handling user inputs. On certain user actions, the Controller triggers Model methods that will result in (i) changing the instance and displaying the new values, (ii) saving the value selected and moving automatically to the next instance or (iii) grouping all the values stored and create a new dataset which contains both the unlabelled dataset values and the labels. This dataset is represented in the figure as the Labelled Dataset.

The NetLabeller GUI is presented as follows. Figure 5.7 shows the NetLabeller GUI once it has been run. Before starting the application, it is necessary to edit the configuration file to select the dataset to be labelled and indicate the label names and values. In this example, TC, OVS and IPTABLES. Once the configuration is finished, the Python component can be started. The data presented in Table 5.3 have been used to show their representation in the NetLabeller tool. Different yellow circles have been added to the figure for a better explanation of the user interface.

In number 1 it is displayed the actual instance whose data is being visualised in the dashboard. The user can select other instances by simply clicking on the input box. On the cards selected with number 2 and 3, both device and flows metadata and metrics are displayed. In section number 4 is displayed the rule information where it can be shown the rule action type and name, the rule technology, or the different rule metrics. In the same section, marked with the number 5, some box-plots are represented to allow the graphical and exploratory analysis of the metrics gathered separated by mean, quarterlies, standard deviations and a descriptive quantifier. In summary, the graph illustrates a descriptive analysis of all the rules applied to the network, providing a better understanding of the rule's performance. These box-plots allow to make an in-depth exploratory data analysis of the feature metrics extracted. Specifically, the values corresponding to the currently matched packages are represented in red and the total matched packages in TC, respectively. The same has been done with OVS, in orange, and IPTABLES, in white. The information about every box-plot can be expanded by simply clicking each of them. Section number 6 displays metrics associated with the available datapath technologies: TC, OVS and IPTABLES in our testbed infrastructure. The user can select the label to add in the checkbox marked in number 7 and also save it. Finally, once the dataset is completely labelled, it can be saved with the Save as CSV button marked in number 8. NetLabeller will generate a new CSV with all labelled instances. The name of this dataset must also be specified in the configuration file.

The tool allows resuming an unfinished labelling task and other user-centric features to achieve an efficient data labelling process.

Fig. 5.7 NetLabeller Graphical User Interface for visualising and labelling networking datasets

The exploratory data analysis is achieved by using the GUI. The EDA process allows the user to understand the data and gather as many insights as possible from it. Making use of it, the user performs critical investigations on data that will result in labelling such data. The GUI template has been designed to represent all the features of one iteration in the same dashboard. More specifically, the characteristics of each technology have been grouped and represented in different colours. This allows the user to perform a quicker exploratory analysis by associating the different technologies with different colours. It is also worth mentioning that this way of representing all the technologies at a glance, close to each other and all the contextual information about the technologies in the same dashboard allows an intrinsic horizontal exploration of the data. Furthermore, the capability to jump to any iteration available in the dataset allows a vertical exploration of it in order to establish comparisons among two similar scenarios.

Fig. 5.8 Sequence diagram representing the connections between components necessary for IDEM to extract data.

5.6.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 5.8 shows a sequence diagram representing the detailed communications between the components of the architecture presented in Figure 5.1. Such interactions make the operation of the IDEM possible. To achieve a better figure explanation, different numbered labels have been included in the figure. The numbers represent interactions between IDEM and other network agents. The rectangles at the top of the figure represent all the agents involved. The interactions are time-dependent, so they happen in the order specified in the figure, from the top down.

The first step (see label 1 in Fig. 5.8) involves the IDEM being started and connected to the database. For the connection, it is necessary to extract the database credentials from the configuration file. For this reason, the database connection module connects with

the configuration engine, where the credentials are obtained and returned to the database connection module (see label 2). Then, all the components represented in Figure 5.8 should be started and running. To reduce the size of the diagram, it is assumed that the components have been previously started up and are already in operation.

The second step is made by RIA (see label 3). RIA publishes into RabbitMQ the discovered topology in a JSON file. Every component subscribed to the topology exchange in RabbitMQ will receive such information. These are the RMA, the SMA, the FCA and the Data Collector. Once the topology is published, different actions are carried out in parallel before the IDEM starts its loop. They have been described in a certain order but executed simultaneously.

- Looking at label 4, the Data Collector transforms the information related to the topology into a SQL sentence and writes the information into the corresponding table.
- In the meantime, looking at label 5, both RMA and SMA use this topological information to produce metrics. For RMA, it runs the scripts that will output the related metrics associated to the devices device ports and datapath technologies available in such topological information and publishes them. In the case of SMA, it produces the metrics associated with the flows. It is important to note that, for the sake of simplicity, the diagram omits the steps of the components themselves, focusing only on the exchanges of information between them.
- Focusing on label 6, the Data Collector is also subscribed to the metrics exchange. For this reason, once the metrics from the RMA and SMA have been published, it can transform them into a SQL sentence and store this information in the corresponding table.
- Additionally, the FCA uses the topology to know where it can apply rules and publish the associated rule metrics. Label 7 is inside an optional box (opt) as the FCA will only publish rule metrics if there are rules enforced in the network.

- Finally, as shown in label 8, the Data Collector does the appropriate with the metrics associated with the rules enforced on the network.

At this point, the IDEM performs the data extraction loop (see loop box in Fig. 7). That loop gets all the topological information of the network (see label 9). Then, as many parallel query threads are created as device ports with enforced rules are on the network (see the parallel box in label 10). In each thread, a total of four queries are made to obtain the information related with devices, device ports, flows and rules enforced. Then, the information extracted is stored in a CSV file (see label 11) and optionally, in label 12, the IDEM is stopped if there is a limitation in the number of iterations to extract.

5.7 Implementation Details and testbed

This section is divided in two subsections. First, it provides some implementation details of the components presented in previous sections. Then, information about the testbed infrastructure deployed in order to validate and evaluate the proposed framework is given. A detailed explanation of the hardware used to deploy the framework prototyped is also provided.

5.7.1 Implementation Details

In terms of software specifications, the components RIA, RMA, SMA and the Data Collector are implemented in Java openjdk version 17.0.3 and FCA in Python 3.7. The software used for the implementation of both components, IDEM and NetLabeller, is Python 3.8.10. The IDEM component basically uses libraries that allow data manipulation and analysis, such as Pandas and NumPy. NetLabeller makes use of libraries related to data visualisation in a GUI and data visualisation in graphs such as Dash and Plotly. Dash allows the deployment of interactive dashboards in a web application. NetLabeller also makes use of Pandas and Numpy for data manipulation. Regarding the softwarised 5G network, the RAN and Core of the Open Air Interface (OAI) software components (git develop branch) [77] were

implemented. Finally, we employ RabbitMq version 3.8.2 as message bus and MySQL 8.15 as database.

5.7.2 Testbed infrastructure

Fig. 5.9 Architecture and workflow of the testbed deployed for the empirical evaluation of the framework.

Figure 5.9 illustrates the testbed deployed to carry out the empirical validation and evaluation of the IDEM and NetLabeller. The testbed infrastructure is based on Linux Ubuntu 20.04 with Metal-as-a-Service (MAAS) 3.0, Canonical Juju 1.8, OpenStack Wallaby and OAI 5G-RAN and Core. Three physical computers have been used for the deployment of the complete infrastructure. Each computer has the following specifications: Dell Precision T5810 with an Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 CPU, 10 cores with hyper-threading, 32794 MB of RAM and 512 GB SSD hard disk. The operative system is Ubuntu release 20.04.4 LTS. For the RU, a Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) model b210 and a BLUESPOT mini antenna have been used. For simplicity, there is only one UE connected to the RAN and one tenant (represented in green colour on the figure). As shown in the figure, the testbed is

composed of three different machines connected to the same LAN. In Machine 1 the OAI DU and CU have been deployed. Also, the purple box inside the Edge represents the compute layer where both softwares are deployed. In Machine 2, the OAI Core components have been deployed. Finally, the whole management framework has been deployed in Machine 3. It includes the RabbitMq message bus, the data collector, the MySQL database, the IDEM and the NetLabeller software. Finally, we have deployed a component called Rule Publisher whose purpose is to publish rules in the network. It is a way to insert rules in a programmatic way, thus impersonating a user administrator to insert a control rule in the network. It was developed for conducting the following experiments. Thus, the SMA component is not needed in this testbed.

5.8 System validation and performance

This section presents the framework validation and performance. In Section 5.8.1, the methodology adopted to execute the different experiments and analyse the results is presented. Then, in Sections 5.8.2 and 5.8.3, some results showing the validation of the framework are illustrated.

5.8.1 Experiments description

Along the complete execution of the experiments, the UE is simply sending a Packet Capture (PCAP) file to Machine 2 using the Linux command `tcpreplay`. Note that the experiments have been carried out once the UE is connected to the network. The traffic sent by the UE reaches the Edge (Machine 1 in Figure 5.9) and the core through the central switch. While traffic is passing through the network, the compute components in the compute layer are each performing their specific function. Therefore, the RIA is publishing the topology information and the RMA, metrics associated with the machine resources. Whereas the FCA is both publishing rule metrics and listening for directives to enforce new rules.

In order to initiate the extraction process, the IDEM relies on pre-existing rules that are already enforced on the network. To fulfil this requirement and only for experiment purposes,

the Rule Publisher has been utilised. Rule Publisher is a Python component that publishes in a JSON file the necessary directives for the FCA to enforce rules in the network. It is possible to configure the type of rule, where to apply it, the technology to use and the number of rules to publish. In our testbed, it will be possible to apply rules to any of the three network device ports that machines 1 and 2 have (see label of device port in Figure 5.9). In addition, the FCA is implemented to support rules from TC, OVS and IPTABLES technologies, so the experiments will be done with rules from these three technologies. The Data Collector is subscribed to the RabbitMq message bus and transforms all the messages into SQL queries.

Once all the components are running and there are some rules enforced on the network, the IDEM is started. It will extract the features a pre-set number of times. The extraction is performed every pre-determined number of seconds. These parameters have been set in the configuration file. At each iteration, in addition to writing the metrics extracted from the network to the unlabelled dataset, IDEM writes in a CSV instrumentation file the times taken to complete every step labelled in Figure 5.5 with yellow circles. As shown in Figure 5.9, this data will be analysed later in a Microsoft Excel file. Finally, the CSV generated by the IDEM will be uploaded to the NetLabeller. Some performance tests have been carried out during the labelling process in order to analytically measure the performance of the tool. A more detailed description of these experiments is provided in the following subsections.

Concerning the procedure followed to execute the experiments and gather results, all the experiments have been reproduced five times. To achieve more accurate results, the arithmetic mean of these values has been done. As the performance of two very different tools will be tested, the procedures for each will be described in each of the subsections.

5.8.2 Infrastructure Data Extractor manager performance analysis

To perform the IDEM experiments, times have been collected in four different parts of the component code and have been written in an Excel file. These steps are indicated in Figure 5.5 as yellow circles. Step 0 registers the time when the IDEM is started. Step 1 saves the timestamp when the connection to the database has been successfully established. Step 2 registers when the feature extraction has finished and Step 3 saves the timestamp when

the instances have been written in the different CSV files. The differences between steps represent how much does the IDEM take to perform the three modules depicted in Figure 5.5: i) database connection, ii) data extraction and data adequation and iii) data output witting. All experiments have been executed during 100 iterations.

As described previously, the IDEM extracts data every number of seconds chosen in the configuration file. The first experiment has been carried out to check what is the minimum time the component needs to finish one iteration and what is its performance depending on the number of seconds defined. To do so, three different times have been chosen: 3 seconds, 5 seconds and 10 seconds. The test scenario is the same for all three cases, with the same number of rules in the network and the same traffic sent from the UE. Five repetitions have been performed for each time between iterations (3, 5 and 10 sec), then averaging these values to obtain more accurate results. Figure 5.10 represents the evolution of the total time taken by IDEM to complete an extraction of each iteration. It can be seen that the time is very variable, although it should be noted that it is a matter of milliseconds of difference. This variation occurs in all three cases analysed. The results show that, in the worst case, IDEM takes 1.45 seconds to finish the iteration. This worst case corresponds to the experiment when 3 seconds per extraction are selected.

Figure 5.11 represents the total average time taken by IDEM, over these 100 iterations. The total execution time is shorter when iterations are performed every 10 seconds. Again, it should be noted that these differences are milliseconds. The standard deviation has also been represented in the figure. It can be noted that it is significant in relation to the mean, which indicates that data are spread out. This measure confirms that the results are variable, as shown in Fig 5.10. Apart from this fact, the time in all cases is around half a second. This allows the reader to understand what minimum response time is required to generate the dataset. Such time is directly related to the minimum time it will be required to update the AI model during the training phase.

The second experiment has been carried out to prove the IDEM scalability, as performance may vary depending on the number of rules in the network. For this experiment, a fixed time between iterations has been chosen, which is 10 seconds as proved before that is the

Fig. 5.10 Evolution of the execution time of IDEM along hundred different extractions.

optimum value. Then, results from a variant number of rules have been gathered: 1 to 32 in steps of 2 rules (1, 2, 4, ..., 30, 32) enforced in the network. Again, five repetitions have been executed for each number of rules. The results shown in Figure 5.12 are the arithmetic average of the repetitions. The graph represents a bar per number of enforced rules. Each bar has 3 different colours, representing the times in milliseconds the IDEM takes for each step.

As we can see, the database connection time is insignificant in comparison with the rest, with an average of 0.5 milliseconds. The data extraction time is depicted in blue. Is the most time-consuming task, for a duration of almost half a second (around 470 milliseconds). It is worth noting that the extraction time does not depend on the number of rules enforced in the network, as it is a process that is done in parallel by several threads. Therefore, the times are practically the same in all tests. Finally, we can see the data writing time in mustard-coloured. It is observed that the writing time increases linearly with the number of rules by steps of 16 milliseconds approximately. This makes sense since a different CSV is written for each rule enforced in the network. This experiment proves that the average extraction time is less than 700 millisecond in most cases and independent of the number of network rules.

Fig. 5.11 Results of the average IDEM execution time for extraction intervals.

5.8.3 NetLabeller runtime performance analysis

Runtime performance shows how the NetLabeller web page performs when it is running. Chrome DevTools Performance panel [78] has been used for analysing the NetLabeller performance. The panel allows to record the page and provides a detailed explanation of the actions being executed. The explanation includes the following times about the page performance: loading, scripting, rendering, painting, system and idle. For our analysis, the idle time has been ignored, as can be considered as the time taken by the user to think about what label to put according to the data being displayed. This time will depend on the user; therefore, it is of no interest when measuring the performance of the tool. Performance evaluation consisted of measuring these times, varying the size of the dataset to be labelled. That is, by changing the number of instances. For this purpose, the following actions have been carried out in all cases:

1. Launch the framework with X instances.
2. Start recording the performance.

Fig. 5.12 Results of the average execution time of each of the IDEM steps as a function of the number of rules enforced in the network.

3. Reload the page.
4. Select a technology and click on the save button.
5. Repeat step (4) 5 times.
6. Click the save button to save the CSV file.
7. Stop the recording.

The X number in step 1 has been ranged with values 10, 100, 1000, 10,000 and 100,000 instances respectively. These actions have been repeated 5 times for each number of instances. The arithmetic means of the results obtained were then calculated. Figure 5.13 shows bar charts of the results obtained with 1000 and 10,000 instances.

As the reader can see, both cases show a very similar distribution of the times. This means that the NetLabeller runtime performance is not affected by the number of instances to be labelled. This is a very desirable feature of our framework, as it means that we will not

have performance problems if the number of instances to label is very high. These results are similar to the cases not plotted for a shake of simplicity (10, 100 and 100,000).

Fig. 5.13 NetLabeller runtime performance analysis.

To highlight the excellent performance of our framework, we have performed a comparison against one of the visualisation tools presented in Table 5.1. Google Looker Studio has been used for this purpose because of its user-friendly and intuitive interface. We produced a similar dashboard, where we present the same features as those shown in Figure 5.7.

Fig. 5.14 Google Looker Studio runtime performance analysis.

We then followed the same steps as above. Except for step 6, since as mentioned in the literature review section (5.2), Google Looker Studio does not allow CSV labelling. Figure 5.14 shows the obtained results. They show two clear conclusions: (i) NetLabeller's runtime performance is better in any of the 5 measured times and (ii) the performance of second tool used is affected by the number of instances to be labelled, in contrast to ours.

On the other side, at a network level, the analysis of the runtime performance shows a clear linear relationship between the number of instances and the time NetLabeller takes to save the labelled dataset. The relationship can be shown in Figure 5.15, which represents the time NetLabeller takes to save a labelled dataset as a function of the number of labelled instances. Notice the time is on a millisecond scale which clearly validates the good performance of the tool as it takes 16 seconds in recording 1 million iterations in labelled data. Finally, it is worth noting that the dashboard updates instantaneously when switching from instance to label. This is because NetLabeller is a Single-page Application (SPA), so the data is loaded all at once when the application is started. This makes navigation through the application highly fluid.

Fig. 5.15 Time taken by NetLabeller to save the labelled dataset, depending on the size of the input dataset.

5.9 Conclusion

This chapter has presented a novel architecture to extract and label networking data coming from a B5G network. The in-depth study of the state of the art regarding similar frameworks has revealed the importance of the contribution presented. The proposed architecture has been implemented and integrated in our lab-based realistic 5G infrastructure, showing how

this contribution will fit in such a real network infrastructure environment. The framework developed is able to monitor, gather, extract, adapt and visualise networking data.

The next chapter explores and evaluates the applicability of the proposed architecture by obtaining a new dataset. This dataset will be used to implement an AI model for network optimisation use cases.

Chapter 6

Infrastructure-wide and Intent-based networking dataset

This chapter and all its contributions are directly related to outcome number 2, the accepted journal article entitled “Infrastructure-wide and Intent-Based networking dataset for 5G and beyond AI-driven Autonomous Networks” [4]. The objective associated with this chapter is number 4.

6.1 Introduction

A B5G AN refers to a network infrastructure that combines the capabilities of 5G and beyond technologies and autonomous networking principles. ANs are composed of virtualised components, automated agents and intelligent decision engines able to perform closed-loop controls [21]. Such self-dynamic capabilities facilitate a wide range of applications in terms of network maintenance, network planning, network diagnosis, network control and network optimisation [58].

In terms of B5G networks, an AN leverages the evolution of traditional cellular networks by incorporating advanced features such as network slicing, virtualisation, softwarisation and Edge computing. In order for AN to be established in our actual infrastructures, it is necessary to have management networks capable of carrying out all these advanced features.

One of the paradigms commonly used nowadays is the IBN, concept already explained in Section 2.5.1.

ANs pursue Intent-Based interactions, moving from human-machine interaction to closed-loop resource interaction [21]. In this context, AI emerges to enable this transition. Meanwhile, before AI training and development, some data-related steps are indispensable. This includes, not only the implementation and deployment of network sensors and data collectors but also the further processing and adequacy of the data. Such procedures allow not only data extraction coming from every resource of the network topology but also gaining significant insights on real-time networking processes [58]. This enhances network optimisation because such data can now be used in ML models to perform quicker and better decisions. Decisions that traditionally are taken by slow human interactions can now be autonomously performed by ML algorithms.

Despite all the benefits that ML-based solutions can bring to B5G networks, their practical implementation is difficult and introduces a number of challenges. First of all, AI systems need a wide variety of data for training. This implies having access to a realistic (real or emulated) network and also having the possibility and the necessary tools to access and extract real-time data. This challenge has been overcome in the previous chapter because of the scarcity of public networking datasets. Furthermore, most of them are out of date and unreliable. This is due to the speed of change that networks, especially cellular networks, experience over the years. This change in network behaviours and patterns demands more dynamically generated datasets [58]. Such new datasets reflect not only the traffic flows and different types of attacks but also the inventory of the network topology where the data is being captured. Thus, the datasets are infrastructure-wide aware, taking into account all infrastructure levels: network-level, node-level, interface-level and technology-level. The capture of such data will make these datasets comprehensive, reproducible, modifiable and extensible.

The above challenges have motivated this chapter, which proposes and presents a novel comprehensive dataset for network management and optimisation purposes in AI-driven B5G networks. The testbed infrastructure exhibits properties of an AN, as it performs self-healing

and self-protection tasks. The resulting dataset is composed of Infrastructure-wide (IW) and Intent-based (IB) data, extracted from an emulated B5G network. Such data is extracted real-time using a closed-loop framework containing all network components presented in previous sections.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows. Section 6.2 summarises the state of the art related to existing available network-related datasets. In Section 6.3 the materials and methods used to create the proposed dataset are exposed. Section 6.4 describes the scenario emulation for the dataset generation. This section includes the implementation details, and the design and execution of the experiments. Section 6.5 provides a detailed explanation of the dataset structure. The dataset analysis and validation is then presented in Section 6.6. Discussion is included in Section 6.7. Finally, the conclusion is provided in Section 6.8.

6.2 Related Work

In order to ensure that AI models are effective in addressing real-world B5G networking challenges, it is essential to have access to real and complete datasets. Such datasets must accurately represent the network traffic, network topology and activities that the model is intended to analyse and predict. Hence, the availability of high-quality datasets is a crucial prerequisite for implementing any AI-based solution for network control, management and optimisation. During the last years, network-based datasets are increasing in popularity. Research communities have expanded their efforts in creating datasets to enhance ML-based networks, addressing the limitations of existing datasets while introducing further enhancements. In this section, a deep explanation of different networking datasets is presented. These datasets are described in Table 6.1, which contains different categories specified in rows.

First, in row “Network type”, it is specified what kind of network infrastructure has been developed to generate the dataset. Then, some rows are designated to describe the dataset’s information. The “Topology” rows refer to the level of detail of the network topology reported in the dataset. We refer to “infrastructure-wide dataset” as a dataset that includes information from all network layers specified in the topology rows. Finally, there are some

rows dedicated to specifying whether the dataset has metadata and metrics according with the different infrastructure-level components: host, port (or network interface), datapath technologies in each port, data flows, port queues and datapath technology port rules. The datasets described are placed in the columns, divided into three different types. Type 1 includes datasets extracted from common network architectures such as LAN, military network or cloud. Type 2 focuses on IoT networks integrated into 5G networks and type 3 collects datasets extracted from a 5G network. Below is a summary of them.

Starting with datasets included in type 1. The KDDCUP99 dataset was created in order to develop a network intrusion detector. This dataset has been widely used over the past years for anomaly detection problems [85]. More than 20 attack types are simulated in the dataset, which can be divided in four categories: DoS, Remote to Local (R2L), User to Root (U2R), and probing. To achieve the generation of the dataset, a wide variety of instructions were simulated in a military network environment. However, this dataset has been detected to have significant issues that highly affect the performance of IDSs. To overcome such problems, other datasets were generated from this one. For example, the NSL-KDD dataset proposed by Tavallaee et al. in [86]. Ferriyan et al. proposed in [87] the dataset HIKARI-2021, an IDS dataset that presents encrypted network traffic in a real-world environment. The dataset is labelled with different network attacks. It has up to 86 features extracted with the Zeek tool, which includes hosts and flows metrics.

There are some other datasets with similar purposes and characteristics as the ones previously described, but not included in the table for the sake of simplicity. For example, Bagui et al. presented in [88] the UWF-ZeekData22 dataset, a labelled network dataset for identifying attack traffic and network anomaly behaviours. Other example is what Sharafaldin et al. presented in [89], the CICDDoS2019, a network dataset designed for DDoS attack examination and detection. The dataset contains up to 80 features extracted from pcap files using the CICFlowMeter tool [90].

Focusing now on other type of network datasets, we have highlighted type 2 in Table 6.1. Ferrag et al. present in [91] the Edge-IIoTset, a cybersecurity dataset of IoT applications. The authors prepared a IoT/IIoT testbed with different IoT devices. In such scenario, they

Table 6.1 Table comparing different networking datasets. (np: not provided)

		TYPE 1		TYPE 2		TYPE 3	
		KDDCUP99	HIKARI-2021	Edge-IIoTset	Bot-IoT	5G-NIDD	Ours
Network type		Military	LAN	Edge-IoT	IoT	5G	5G
Dataset info	Extraction tools	tcpdump	tcpdump, Zeek	Zeek	pcap capturing	pcap capturing	Linux scripts, Python tools
	Purpose	NID	NID	NID	NID	NID	NMC *
	Format	csv	csv	csv	different sets	pcap, csv	csv
	Resolution	n.p	n.p	timestamp	timestamp	timestamp	timestamp
	Simulated	Yes	Partial	No	No	No	No
	Features	42	86	61	n.p	112	101
	Year	1999	2021	2022	2019	2022	2023
	Available	[79]	[80]	[81]	[82]	[83]	[84]
Topology	Host	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Port	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Technology	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Flow	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Host	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Port	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
	Technology	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Queue	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Flow	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metrics	Host	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Port	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
	Technology	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Queue	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
	Flow	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Rule	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓

* Network Management and Control.

identified and analysed different attacks related to IoT and IIoT connectivity protocols. Additionally, Koroniotis et al. presents Bot-IoT [92], a network traffic dataset that includes Botnet scenarios in a realistic IoT network. It is an intrusion detection dataset that trains models to detect various botnet attacks in IoT networks. Both research works come out with realistic and high quality IoT network traffic datasets for NID. However, both of them are

based only on flow metrics and are not infrastructure aware. Furthermore, another drawback is that neither of them has been deployed in a 5G network architecture.

Finally, type 3 includes the 5G-NIDD dataset, presented by Samarakoon et al. in [93], a fully labelled dataset built on a functional 5G test network. The network has the presence of different attack scenarios and non-malicious traffic from real users. The dataset is focused on NID, with a total 112 features including flow metadata and metrics.

All these exposed datasets were created with the same purpose: attack and anomaly detection. For this reason, all of them have similar characteristics regarding the topology level and its metrics and metadata at both port and flow level. However, none of them meets the necessary needs for the development of this thesis. This is, a dataset that records the network topology in more depth, along with its intent-based data; data that reflect metadata and metrics associated with network policies, which are linked with network intents. Providing not only information related to network monitoring, but also information related to network control. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, none of the datasets found include intent-based data in a 5G network architecture. This has been the principal motivation of the current chapter.

6.3 Materials and methods

In this section, the study area of the dataset is presented. This refers to a 5G multi-tenant and intent-based AN. Section 6.3.1 gives a brief overview of what an intent-based network is and the data collection framework. Section 6.3.2 then presents the requirements of the dataset at the time of its creation.

6.3.1 Intent-based autonomous framework

The reference B5G network architecture for this research work is divided into 3 different layers (compute, service and management), which are deployed to provide the network with autonomous protection and healing capabilities. Specifically, the lab-based B5G network contains an intent-based loop where multiple network components work together to obtain an

effective policy enforcement. The reader is recommended to refer to section 2.5.1 to review these contents. On this architecture, the proposed framework explained in the previous chapter has been implemented in order to collect the dataset. The specific functioning of the joint framework will be described in the following sections.

After providing an overview of the data extraction and collection framework, we will now proceed to delineate the specific requirements pertaining to the dataset.

6.3.2 Dataset Requirements

Typically, datasets possess distinct assets and demands. The final goal of the dataset may determine its shape, features and characteristics. Therefore, a good specification of dataset requirements will facilitate the design, development and creation of the dataset. The different requirements determined for the generation of the dataset proposed in this chapter are summarised below.

1. The dataset must utilise a real or a realistic emulation of a 5G multi-tenant network in such a way that it is feasible to generate traffic as realistic as possible. Realistic traffic leads to better results in AI model development and yields improved performance in real-world environments.
2. Providing captured traffic (e.g., in the format of pcap files) alone is insufficient to gain a comprehensive understanding of the network topology and its current state. If a complete conception of the network is desired, metrics coming from all components of the network are required. A complete capture of the network traffic (pcap files) can complement the dataset evaluation.
3. The dataset must be infrastructure-wide. This means that it contains topology inventories, metadata and metrics from all relevant network components, such as hosts (network devices), ports (network interfaces), port datapath technologies, port queues, flows and rules inserted in each port.

4. It is crucial and required that the dataset adheres to an intent-based approach. This entails capturing and maintaining a record of the network rules enforced within the network infrastructure, along with their corresponding metadata and metrics. By encompassing this information, the intent-based dataset ensures comprehensive coverage of the network's operational aspects and facilitates further analysis and evaluation of its performance.
5. The dataset features are designed in a way that the dataset maintains anonymity and privacy. Payloads of generated traffic are unnecessary, as the focus of the proposed dataset is on infrastructure-wide data. This two facts ensure that personal and sensitive data is not disclosed.
6. Data are subject to change over time, for that reason, the dataset and the methods to generate it must be up to date. With such a requisite, it is guaranteed that the dataset always contains the latest information.

6.4 Scenario Emulation and Dataset generation

This section describes the testbed infrastructure for the scenario emulation and details how the data is collected to generate the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. Thus, in subsection 6.4.1 a complete explanation of the experiment implementation details is provided. Then, subsection 6.4.2 provides a description of the different scenarios used to generate the dataset, specifying the technical details of each of the generated scenarios. Finally, subsection 6.4.3 contains information about the data collection process and how the dataset is created. For this purpose, the execution of the experiments is explained in detail.

6.4.1 Implementation details

All software components described in the previous chapters have been designed, deployed and validated in a realistic 5G lab-based infrastructure. The vast majority are implemented in Java 17 (RIA, SMA, RMA, CPM and Collectors), with the exception of the FCA and

the IDEM, which are implemented in Python 3.8. The SMA component uses Snort 3.0 underneath to perform the attack detection. RIA utilises a collection of tools including OpenStack, OpenAirInterface 5G (W44 2022 or higher), Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP), Cisco Discovery Protocol (CDP) and iproute2 (v1.9 or higher) in the Linux stack to detect the network topology. The message bus is implemented with RabbitMQ 3.6. The SQL database is MySQL 8.15. The CPM is a java implementation based on a MySQL 8 engine in order to allow the usage of SQL to reveal analytical, decision making and planning policies. The FCA relies on Linux TC qdisc, OVS 2.17.3 and iproute2 (v1.9 or higher) to enforce the actions.

The emulation tool used for the creation of the network topology is the Common Open Research Emulator (CORE) [94]. It utilises Linux Network Namespaces (netns) to emulate (rather than to simulate) the different devices and networks that form the infrastructure. Each device or network operates within its own private network and process environments, while still sharing the same file system and kernel. Additionally, the Linux Ethernet bridging tools available in the Linux environment enable the emulation of any network type, including wireless mobile networks, thus realistically representing the detailed infrastructure described in this research work. CORE was used for the implementation of a system that allows the creation, configuration, provisioning, emulation and execution of different experimental scenarios in 5G multi-tenant networks. More in-depth specifications of the system used can be found in Section 5.1 of [51].

In the context of our emulated 5G network, it is imperative to highlight the realism of the generated network traffic. The importance of this statement lies in the fact that the entire network is emulated, with the only exception of the link connecting the UE and the RAN component, which is simulated. Despite this limited simulation element, the veracity of the network traffic remains intact. This authenticity is maintained by meticulous prototyping of network components, protocols and behaviours, which ensures that the emulated traffic patterns closely reflect real-world scenarios. For instance, we use real Core network elements provided by Osmocom (SGSNEmu [95] and GGSN [96]) and also by OAI [77]. We also emulate multi-tenancy infrastructure making use of a custom Openstack Neutron-like SDN

controller that populates isolated tenant networks using OVS. Furthermore, the traffic is modelled to support both mobility and multi-tenancy through tunnelling protocols used in 5G architectures such as VXLAN and GTP. Full End-to-End topology emulation has been achieved using Linux containers to perform the deployment of each of the network functions on the relevant emulated devices to create a realistic 5G multi-tenant deployment. Therefore, all data traversing our emulated 5G network reflects genuine (non-synthetic) network traffic, and the emulated environment faithfully represents real-world network dynamics. This approach not only facilitates robust testing and analysis, but also reinforces the credibility of the emulation as a valuable tool for network evaluation and experimentation.

The experiments were run in a physical machine with an Ubuntu release 20.04 LTS distribution with kernel version 5.15.0. As physical resources, it has a 56-core Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2660 v4 @ 2.00GHz and 128GB DDR4 2400 MHz of RAM.

6.4.2 Experiment design

Network security is one of the most important concerns of 5G operators [60]. For this reason, the use-case selected was focus on security policies so it was decided to collect the dataset based on the following intent: “Eliminate any traffic flow exhibiting malicious behaviour or unauthorised access attempts, without disrupting legitimate network traffic.” DDoS constitutes the 38.18% of the global network and application layer attack traffic according to Cloudflare radar [97]. In addition, the most popular DDoS attack type is UDP, being 54.4% of the total. In accordance with this fact, we decided to subject our network to UDP DDoS attacks, so that the resulting dataset records the state of the network while the intent is being fulfilled. Thus, the extracted dataset can be used to generate AI modules capable of making optimal decisions during such intent process. These decisions will be optimal as the specific network policy can be generated according to the state of the network at any given time rather than by default.

Multiple experiments have been designed and carried out in order to obtain a wide variety of data. The parameters studied in our research are: the type of scenario executed, the type of policy to be performed within the network, the datapath technology employed to execute

the policy, the packet rate at which data is transmitted, and the packet size used in these transmissions.

A total of four substantially different scenarios have been developed to achieve a more complete dataset. The four scenarios differ substantially in the number of Edge segments, as well as the number of UEs connected to each Edge. These are described below:

- Scenario 1. It is composed of 2 UEs and 1 Edge. Thus, both UEs are connected to the same Edge.
- Scenario 2. It consists of 4 UEs and 2 Edges. There are 2 UEs connected to each Edge.
- Scenario 3. It has 8 UEs and 2 Edges. Thus, there are 4 UEs connected to each Edge.
- Scenario 4. It is composed 16 UEs and 2 Edges. There are 8 UEs connected to each Edge.

The design of scenarios 1 and 2 is displayed in Figure 6.1. Scenarios 3 and 4 follow the same design as scenario 2, including a higher number of UEs connected to each Edge. They have not been added in the figure for simplicity. For the same reason, network control layers have also not been included in the figure. Note that the number of UEs connected to the RAN has been chosen for specific use cases to have variety. However, this number can be extended, as well as the number of Edges connected to the Core network. This extension of the architecture is easily achievable using the CORE emulator.

The type of action dictates the aspects of the network's performance, behaviour, and operations we will focus on and examine closely. We have been focused on network's behaviour while eliminating any traffic flow exhibiting malicious behaviour or unauthorised access attempts. This involves the choice of the policy to be carried out and the datapath technology with which to enforce it on the network. These decisions will profoundly influence the network behaviour. Three network software datapath technologies have been studied, which are iptables, OVS and TC. Finally, variations in packet rate and size directly impact on performance metrics, in terms of throughput, packet loss, bandwidth utilisation and congestion. For this reason, the variation of the packets traversing the network consisted

Fig. 6.1 Scenarios 1 and 2 architecture design.

of varying i) the packet payload: 32, 128, 256, 512 and 1024 bytes and ii) the packet rate: 50 and 100 packets/sec/UE. Figure 6.2 can be referred to in order to understand the complete encapsulation of the packet in the emulated scenario.

This provides a bandwidth reaching the victim between 132 Kbps in the lowest case and 15 Mbps in the highest case (16 UEs and 100 packets/sec), which are considered low-rate DDoS attacks, according to [98]. Specifically, constant low-rate DDoS attacks were generated. This type of attack consists of sending packets at a constant low rate [99].

The variation of these two parameters, together with the number of UEs, makes 40 executions for each datapath technology, achieving a total of 120 executions for gathering data for the dataset. It is important to mention that depending on the number of UEs, each

Fig. 6.2 Description of the encapsulation type for each network layer.

execution will contain different number of data files, according to the number of network rules active in the network. This means, the more UEs attacking the network, the more network policies from the intent will be processed to drop the malicious traffic.

6.4.3 Experiment execution

This section explains how the data is generated and collected in order to create the dataset. As mentioned in the previous section, the final goal of each experiment is to gather data from different points of the network while malicious traffic is being eliminated from the network. The configuration of each experiment is the same. All the experiments have a duration of 3 minutes. Once all parameters specified in previous section are set and the experiment is run, these are the steps followed by the autonomous system in order to compose the dataset:

1. Every software component involved in the cognitive loop (described in section 2.5.2) is started and operate in a standby mode.
2. The intent is inserted in the network using a CLI (see step 1 “Intent Profiling” in Fig. 2.4). The intent is the same in every experiment: “Eliminate any traffic flow exhibiting malicious behaviour or unauthorised access attempts, without disrupting legitimate network traffic.”
3. CPM translates the intent into a policy template (see step 2 “Intent Translation” in Fig. 2.4), waiting for any traffic alert.

4. The UEs start sending two types of traffic. Bonesi [100] is the tool used for the DDoS attack traffic, while hping3 [101] for the benign traffic (see Fig. 6.1).
5. The software components in the service and compute layers of the ISP Edge start extracting data as the traffic from the UEs cross the network. The exchanged data is shown in Figure 2.4 by red circles.
6. The SMA detects the malicious traffic and notifies the system of the attack through the message bus, using the traffic alert exchange.
7. The CPM performs all the steps described in Section 2.5.2 and generates a network policy. It is then published into the message bus. The policy specifies what to do, where and how. In our use-case, perform a drop action, in a network interface using a concrete datapath technology. The decision of the datapath technology has been previously defined in the configuration of the experiment and is included in the policy template. On the other hand, the decision of the location (network interface) where to perform the drop is calculated by the cognitive loop. Thus, depending on the datapath technology to be used, the drop action will be performed on a particular network interface. In our specific scenario, as we are handling a DDoS attack, it is desired to be stopped it as early as possible. This means that the drop action should be performed as closer to the UEs as possible so that the malicious traffic would not traverse the network. Fig. 6.1 highlights three different network interfaces where it is possible to perform a drop action. Datapath technologies OVS and TC are available at interfaces eth0, eth6 and eth7. However, iptables will be available only at eth0. For this reason, when OVS or TC technology is selected, the drop will be performed at eth6 and eth7 respectively. On the other hand, in case iptables is selected, the drop action will be performed at eth0 as it is not feasible to enforce the action earlier in the network. After all these decisions and the policy finished, step 3 “Intent Resolution” is completed.
8. The policy is published in the message bus. An example of the policy message is shown in Listing 6.1.

9. The FCA receives the policy and translates it into a network rule, which is to drop the malicious traffic. As shown in Listing 6.1, the policy has also specified which network interface (eth6) and with what datapath technology (TRAFFIC_CONTROL) to enforce the rule. As mentioned, the FCA is capable of performing the drop action with the following datapath technologies: iptables, OVS or TC. This completes the step 4 “Intent Activation” in Fig. 2.4.
10. Once the rule is enforced on the network, the malicious traffic is dropped at the specified network interface by the datapath technology defined in the policy. Meanwhile, all components continue reporting network behaviour metrics (according to step 5 “Intent Assurance”). With this final step, we can consider the loop has been successfully closed as now the network restores to its standby mode.
11. The experiment execution continues to complete the 3 minutes. During this time, the UEs continue sending malicious traffic. Such traffic is being stopped at the Edge of the network. In the meantime, all the information and metrics generated during the execution of the experiment have been stored in the database and transformed into the resulting dataset.

```
{
  "Policy": {
    "actionType": "INSERT",
    "actionName": "DROP",
    "priority": 1,
    "flowId": "4BA92944",
    "reportedTime": 1659106981511
  },
  "Params": [
    {
      "paramName": "interfaceName",
      "paramValue": "eth6"
    },
    {
```

```
        "paramName": "technology",
        "paramValue": "TRAFFIC_CONTROL"
    },
    {
        "paramName": "device",
        "paramValue": "Edge1"
    }
]
}
```

Listing 6.1 Example of network policy.

6.5 Dataset description

This section provides an in-depth description of the dataset proposed and created in this research work, with emphasis on its structure, the type of data gathered and the characteristics of its instances and features.

6.5.1 IW-IB-5GNET dataset

The IW-IB-5GNET dataset is composed of several files. As it is an intent-based dataset, each file is associated with a network policy, translated from an intent. As a result, the number of files generated will correspond to the total number of active network policies in each experiment. For each file, the features are ordered topologically. This means that the features are organised in a top-down approach, starting with the device features, followed by the network interface features, datapath technology ones, queues, network flows and network rules. The reader is referred to Figure 5.3 for further details. The aggregation of the features corresponding to all levels of the 5G network topology makes it an infrastructure-wide dataset.

After the execution of each experiment described in Section 6.4.3, all the instances of each resulting file have been merged into a single CSV file. This file forms the IW-IB-5GNET

dataset. As a result of the 120 executions, a total of 700 CSV files have been assembled. The dataset has a final dimension of 64290 x 107, i.e. a total of 64290 instances and 107 features. An excerpt of the dataset consisting of 1000 instances is available online in the author's GitHub repository [84].

6.5.2 Features description

Dataset IW-IB-5GNET comprises 107 features related to the Edge and Core segments of a 5G network. Table 6.2 lists all the features and their positions in the dataset. The features are ordered topologically, starting with the metadata and metrics associated with the device (see 1-3 in grey in Table 6.2), followed by the device port (see 4-5, yellow), datapath technologies and their queues (see 6-33, blue), traffic flows (see 34-49, red) and, finally, the network control rules (see 50-106, green and orange). Features 50 to 61 comprises the metrics and metadata of a particular network rule, enforced and monitored on a particular network interface (specified in feature 4, `iface`). Features 62 to 106 comprise analytical information related to all the network rules currently enforced in the network. With respect to RAN features, it is worth mentioning that we have decided to do not include any value that is not coming from a trusted source. Thus, no physical layer feature is included, as it is the only link in the network that is simulated.

Based on their nature and the kind of information they represent, the features can be categorised into four different types as listed below.

- **Boolean features:** they refer to binary values, indicating the presence or absence of a particular attribute. IW-IB-5GNET dataset has a total of four boolean features, enumerated in Table 6.3.
- **Metadata features:** they are composed of both categorical, numerical and text features. They are mixed together in the same category as they represent characteristics of every particular experiment. Most of them describe basic network characteristics and are essential to understand each specific use case. In addition, most of its values do not change throughout the experiments. However, it is important to keep them in the dataset

Table 6.2 List of features in IW-IB-5GNET dataset. Color indicates topology level: (grey-device), (yellow-interface), (blue-technology), (red-flow) and (green,orange-policy)

No	Feature	No	Feature	No	Feature	No	Feature
1	Hostname	28	TC_rx_bytes	55	currentMatchedPackets	82	OVS_mean_crr
2	ContextSwitchesPerSecond	29	TC_RX_dropped	56	lastMatchedTime	83	OVS_median_crr
3	AbstractionLayer	30	TC_RX_packets	57	ruleComplexity	84	OVS_st_crr
4	Iface	31	TC_TX_bytes	58	totalMatchedBytes	85	OVS_q1_crr
5	Iface_speed	32	TC_TX_dropped	59	totalMatchedPkts	86	OVS_q3_crr
6	IPTAB_activated	33	TC_TX_packets	60	actionType	87	OVS_mean_total
7	IPTAB_complexity	34	encapsulationLayer	61	actionName	88	OVS_median_total
8	IPTAB_maxRules	35	encapsulationType1	62	IPTAB_min_crr_currentMatchedPkts	89	OVS_st_total
9	IPTAB_rx_bytes	36	encapsulationType2	63	IPTAB_max_crr_currentMatchedPkts	90	OVS_q1_total
10	IPTAB_rx_packets	37	sense	64	IPTAB_min_total_totalMatchedPkts	91	OVS_q3_total
11	IPTAB_tx_bytes	38	l3Protocol	65	IPTAB_max_total_totalMatchedPkts	92	TC_min_crr_currentMatchedPkts
12	IPTAB_tx_packets	39	dstIP	66	IPTAB_numberRulesActivatedTotal	93	TC_max_crr_currentMatchedPkts
13	OVS_activated	40	macSrc	67	IPTAB_mean_crr	94	TC_min_total_totalMatchedPkts
14	OVS_complexity	41	macDst	68	IPTAB_median_crr	95	TC_max_total_totalMatchedPkts
15	OVS_maxRules	42	l4Protocol	69	IPTAB_st_crr	96	TC_numberRulesActivatedTotal
16	OVS_rx_bytes	43	tos	70	IPTAB_q1_crr	97	TC_mean_crr
17	OVS_rx_dropped	44	outTos	71	IPTAB_q3_crr	98	TC_median_crr
18	OVS_rx_packets	45	dstPort	72	IPTAB_mean_total	99	TC_st_crr
19	OVS_tx_bytes	46	state	73	IPTAB_median_total	100	TC_q1_crr
20	OVS_tx_dropped	47	totalpktCount	74	IPTAB_st_total	101	TC_q3_crr
21	OVS_tx_packets	48	totalBits	75	IPTAB_q1_total	102	TC_mean_total
22	TC_activated	49	packetSize	76	IPTAB_q3_total	103	TC_median_total
23	TC_queueDiscipline	50	programmableTechnology	77	OVS_min_crr_currentMatchedPkts	104	TC_st_total
24	TC_queueLenght	51	activatedRuleTimeSecs	78	OVS_max_crr_currentMatchedPkts	105	TC_q1_total
25	TC_complexity	52	averageMatchedBytes	79	OVS_min_total_totalMatchedPkts	106	TC_q3_total
26	TC_crr_bwd_guaranteed	53	averageMatchedPackets	80	OVS_max_total_totalMatchedPkts	107	timestamp
27	TC_maxRules	54	currentMatchedBytes	81	OVS_numberRulesActivatedTotal		

in order to have a complete description of the network at each particular experiment execution. The metadata features are listed in Table 6.4. The table describes the data type of each feature. In the case of categorical features, the values they can acquire are specified. In addition, a brief description of what each of these features represent is included.

- **Numerical features:** they represent continuous or discrete numerical values. There are a total of 74 numerical features in the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. Such features are related to metrics measured in real-time, at different network topology levels: device host, interfaces, flows, datapath technologies, queues and rules. The names given to these metrics are sufficiently descriptive for the reader to know what they represent.
- **Date/Time features:** they represent specific points in time. There is only one date feature in the IW-IB-5GNET dataset, `timestamp`, which represents the moment when a concrete extraction has been done. It is represented using the Unix timestamp.

Table 6.3 Description of boolean features in IW-IB-5GNET dataset.

Feature name	Representation	Description
IPTAB_activated	[True, False]	Presence of iptables in the interface.
OVS_activated	[True, False]	Presence of ovs in the interface.
TC_activated	[True, False]	Presence of linux tc in the interface.
Sense	[ingress, egress]	Direction of network traffic flow.

6.6 Results

In this section, we present the analysis and validation of the resultant dataset. This section presents the data obtained through tables and graphs, which can help better understand the dataset. The final objective of this section is to demonstrate the quality and reliability of the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. For the development of such analyses, it has been employed Python 3.9.6 and its libraries for data analysis: Pandas, Numpy, SciPy, Seaborn and Matplotlib.

6.6.1 Dataset preprocessing

Prior to IW-IB-5GNET dataset performance evaluation, we carried out some data preprocessing to ensure that the dataset was clean, consistent and suitable for analysis. This preparatory step was essential to mitigate the potential impact of noise, errors during the experiment executions and irregularities in the data, which can significantly affect the accuracy and reliability of subsequent analysis.

First, as mentioned in Section 6.5, it was necessary to consolidate all the CSV files from various experiments into a single file, simplifying the process of gathering statistics and conducting analysis. Once all data were in a single CSV file, the following were the four steps conducted in our data preprocessing pipeline:

1. Delete all rows whose columns were duplicates. This implies that all their columns have the same value.
2. Delete all rows that satisfied: `activatedRuleTime = lastMatchedTime`. Columns that satisfy this condition are the result of an invalid operation in the execution of the experiment, as they imply that a rule inserted in the network has not matched any

Table 6.4 Description of metadata features in W-IB-5GNET dataset.

Feature name	Data type	Categorical values	Additional info
Hostname	text	-	Data extraction host name.
AbstractionLayer	number	[0,1,2]	Level of virtualization.
Iface	text	-	Interface name where data extraction was done.
Iface_speed	number	-	Network interface speed.
IPTAB_complexity	number	[8]	Level of complexity iptables rules.
IPTAB_maxRules	number	[4096]	iptables rule limit.
OVS_complexity	number	[4]	Level of complexity ovs rules.
OVS_maxRules	number	[16384]	ovs rule limit.
TC_queueDiscipline	text	[noqueue, fq_codel, atm, htb, prio]	Primary iface qdisc queue discipline.
TC_queueLenght	number	-	Max number of packets allowed in the queue.
TC_complexity	number	[8]	Level of complexity tc rules.
TC_maxRules	number	[4096]	tc rule limit.
encapsulationLayer	number	[0, 1, 2]	Number of encapsulations of a traffic flow.
encapsulationType1	number	[gtp, vxlan]	Type of first encapsulation.
encapsulationType2	number	[gtp, vxlan]	Type of second encapsulation.
L3Protocol	number	[ipv4, ipv6, icmp, arp]	Layer 3 protocol of flow.
dstIP	number	-	Flow destination IP.
macSrc	number	-	Flow source mac address.
macDst	number	-	Flow destination mac address.
L4Protocol	number	[tcp, udp]	Layer 4 protocol of flow.
Tos	number	[0]	Type of service.
OutTos	number	[0]	Out type of service.
dstPort	number	-	Flow destination port.
State	text	[active, dropped, inactive]	Flow state description.
programmableTechnology	text	[TC, OVS, IPTABLES]	Data-plane technology used to do the action.
ruleComplexity	number	[1, 2, 3...]	Rule performance complexity.
actionType	text	[INSERT, SET, DELETE]	Definition of action type.
actionName	text	[DROP, PRIORITY, QUEUE, SLICE]	Definition of action name.

packet. As our objective is to optimise rules that are active at a precise moment in time, these rows do not satisfy this condition and have therefore been removed.

3. Analyse and delete columns whose values were empty in all iterations.
4. Delete all rows whose columns contained negative values. None of the features were designed to be negative, so the presence of these values, if any, was due to an invalid operation during the experiment execution.

The preprocessing of the data resulted in the IW-IB-5GNET dataset, whose dimensions were already mentioned in the previous section: 64290 x 107. Its memory usage is 51.2 MB.

Analysis of the different types of features presented in Section 6.5 are discussed below in separate subsections.

6.6.2 Boolean features evaluation

Table 6.5 shows the statistical summary of the boolean features in the dataset. It specifies the number of non-null values in each column, the number of unique values in the column, the most frequently occurring value in each column and the frequency of the top value. This summary is useful for gaining a quick understanding of the distribution and characteristics of boolean data within our dataset. For instance, it identifies the presence of the datapath technologies OVS and TC in all the experiments executed where the drop action was performed (see `OVS_activated` and `TC_activated` in Table 6.5). On the other hand, it demonstrates that there are more cases where it is not possible to enforce a rule in iptables due to its absence on the monitored network interface (see `IPTAB_activated`). The statistics also reveal that most of the network flows dropped are in ingress (see `sense`).

Table 6.5 Statistical values of boolean features in IW-IB-5GNET dataset.

Feature name	count	unique	top	freq
<code>IPTAB_activated</code>	64290	2	False	55569
<code>OVS_activated</code>	64290	1	True	64290
<code>TC_activated</code>	64290	1	True	64290
<code>sense</code>	64290	2	ingress	55569

6.6.3 Metadata features evaluation

As described in Table 6.4, 28 features comprise the variables categorised as metadata in our dataset. Most of them provide us a better understanding of the network infrastructure, traffic flow characteristics and the network control rule active on each particular moment of the extraction. Figure 6.3 shows the number of unique values of each feature presented in Table 6.4.

For instance, three different network interfaces were used throughout all experiments to drop the traffic flows. Other relevant feature is the encapsulation type of the traffic flows,

Fig. 6.3 Number of unique values in each metadata feature.

as it is presented, there were two different encapsulation types: GTP and VXLAN. The programmable technology gives us the datapath technology used to enforce the action on the network. Its value is three, as we have employed three different datapath technologies: iptables, OVS and TC. Similarly, there were three different rule complexities, associated with the enforcement of each datapath technology.

Most of these features consistently maintain a uniform value throughout the entire dataset. This consistency stems from the fact that, as explained in the previous section, the metadata provides us with network-related information that remains relatively static over time. While this information might not hold immediate appeal, retaining it within the dataset is appropriate. This is because, if they were to conduct other types of experiments, this metadata would change, raising its relevance to the dataset.

Focusing now on specific features, Figure 6.4 reveals interesting information connecting `iface` and `programmableTechnology` variables. The count plot is divided in the three datapath technologies (iptables, OVS and TC) used for the enforcement of the network policy.

In addition, such division is classified taking into account where this policy is performed, in terms of its network interface. Thus, we can observe that all actions performed with iptables are enforced in network interface eth0, while TC and OVS vary between eth6 and eth7. This graph confirms the successful performance of the autonomous control loop, since the network policies are performed at the interfaces analysed in Section 6.4.3.

Fig. 6.4 Association between interface and datapath technology used in the action.

6.6.4 Numerical features evaluation

As described in Section 6.5.2, a total of 74 features compose the numerical variables of the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. Some of them were removed during the data preprocessing process. Additionally, features 62 to 106 (see Table 6.2) already represent analytical information. Therefore, they were not considered in this data analysis.

First, we start the data analysis with some descriptive statistics presented in Table 6.6. This table shows the statistics of the 22 non-null numerical features in our dataset. The first two columns indicate the feature name and its unit. The statistics include the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum measures. As can be seen in the table, most of these features are focused on monitoring packets or bytes per second traversing different points in the network. We can also observe information related to the number of packets traversing the

Table 6.6 Descriptive statistics values of numerical features in IW-IB-5GNET dataset.

Feature	Unit	Mean	Std	Min	Max
ContextSwitchesPerSecond	Switch/sec	3.78	2.65	0	9
IPTAB_RX_bytes	Bytes/sec	178080	495268	0	3524780
IPTAB_RX_packets	Packets/sec	987	2661	0	14866
IPTAB_TX_bytes	Bytes/sec	4031111	13392294	0	184598347
IPTAB_TX_packets	Packets/sec	5345	17555	0	151650
OVS_RX_bytes	Bytes/sec	9290003	12603834	9926	78227821
OVS_RX_packets	Packets/sec	20772	18092	93	72736
OVS_TX_bytes	Bytes/sec	2135533	9334686	6354	156582130
OVS_TX_packets	Packets/sec	5014	16145	611	145377
TC_RX_bytes	Bytes/sec	2642547	7151074	0	62570352
TC_RX_dropped	Packets/sec	5145	9556	0	57989
TC_RX_packets	Packets/sec	5682	10507	0	58842
totalpktCount	Packets	6866	3809	840	18120
totalBits	Bits	21578431	25187493	416976	148316160
packetSize	Bytes	395	355	32	1024
activatedRuleTimeSecs	Seconds	59	36	1	144
averageMatchedBytes	Bytes/sec	40171	37985	3665	785862
averageMatchedPackets	Packets/sec	89	39	42	969
currentMatchedBytes	Bytes/sec	37469	91559	0	9513560
currentMatchedPackets	Packets/sec	83	159	0	11859
totalMatchedBytes	Bytes	2299883	2792487	5772	16381370
totalMatchedPackets	Packets	5031	3518	70	14855

network during the experiment and their size in bytes. With these measurements it is possible to identify congestion points along the network, as well as which datapath technologies and on which network interface they are located. Finally, the last 7 variables provide us with information about the effectiveness of the rule currently enforced on the network, corresponding to the intent concerned. We have highlighted this effectiveness according to each of the datapath technologies with which the drop action was carried out. This reflection can be seen in Figure 6.5. In this figure it is represented a box-plot for each of the datapath technologies; iptables, TC and OVS. On the y-axis, on the other hand, the total number of packets that match the drop rule is represented. From this graph it can be concluded that, for the same duration of the experiment (3 minutes), the number of packets that OVS is able to

process is slightly higher than that of TC and, subsequently, that of iptables. These results indicate that OVS is faster in terms of network rule processing time and can be taken into account when performing network optimisation tasks.

Fig. 6.5 Box-plot of total matched packets depending on the datapath technology used.

Following the technical validation of our numerical features, we present Figure 6.6. It represents the data distribution graphs of the numerical columns in the IW-IB-5GNET dataset. A wide variety of shapes in the data distributions can be observed in the figure. First, we can identify discrete values such as ContextSwitchesPerSecond or packetSize. Focusing on the packetSize graph in Fig. 6.6, it can be observed the five different packet sizes chosen for the experiments; these are 32, 128, 256, 512 and 1024 bytes. Many histograms with exponential shape are also present in the figure, such as the features totalBits and totalMatchedBytes. The totalBits feature indicates the number of bits actually traversing a particular network interface, while totalMatchedBytes designates the total number of bytes that match the network rule being monitored. Finally, we observe a variety of non-uniform shapes. Most of these have a high maximum value and much smaller clustered values around it. Examples of these are totalpktCount or totalMatchedPackets. Looking at the graph of total matched packages in Fig. 6.6, we can observe that the majority of values are around the mean, which is 5031. Additionally, its maximum value is 14855 which indicates that in some of the experiments the rule matches a high amount of packets.

Fig. 6.6 Histogram graphs of numerical features in the IW-IB-5GNET dataset.

To conclude with the technical evaluation of the IW-IB-5GNET dataset, the correlation coefficients of the numerical features have been calculated. The technique used was the calculation of Pearson correlation coefficients (PCC), which measures linear correlation between two sets of data. The coefficient values vary between -1 and 1, which indicates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables [102]. Figure 6.7 shows the correlation matrix obtained from these coefficients. It can be seen that features with high correlation are represented with a very light orange colour. In contrast, features with high negative correlation are represented with a dark purple. Features with low correlation between them are represented with intermediate colours. For instance, there is a clear positive correlation between bytes and packets of every pair of features associated to the same monitored instance (i.e. the more packets received, the more bytes received). An example of this can be found at the second and third features in Figure 6.7, `IPTAB_RX_bytes` and `IPTAB_RX_packets` respectively, where it can be noted the very light orange colour representing their positive correlation. Focusing on very negative correlations, we look at the

averageMatchedPackets feature with the activatedRuleTimeSecs feature. The more time a rule is active on the network, the fewer average packets match that rule. In general terms, we observe a clear linear relationship in the lower right part of the correlation matrix. This corresponds to the metrics associated with the network rules, which are highly variable during the execution of the experiments. On the other hand, there is little linear dependence of the metrics associated with iptables with respect to the rest of the features. This is due to the fact that iptables is located at the egress interface of the Edge network. Thus, traffic does not pass through in many of the experiments because the traffic is dropped before reaching the egress interface.

To summarise, the correlation matrix gives us a lot of information about the relationship of our data. Depending on the type of problem we expect to address using our dataset, we will need to pay attention to some patterns or others. For example, multicollinearity (two or more variables are highly correlated with each other) can be problematic in regression analysis, as it can lead to unstable coefficient estimates. Therefore, depending on the final objective of the dataset, the results will be taken as adequate or inadequate, and different actions may need to be taken.

6.7 Discussion

This section serves the purpose of consolidating and documenting the critical insights and deliberations derived from this chapter. This compilation is intended to provide a comprehensive resource for future researchers, enabling them to benefit from our considerations as a valuable foundation for their own scientific research.

Throughout the design and implementation of the proposed framework, we realised the great importance of performing mechanisms to align IDS from all components of the network topology. These are network flows, network ports, datapath technologies available on each network port and device hosts. This is critical to allow the subsequent manipulation of features coming from each of these different entities. We have also realised and understood the real difficulty of achieving this intent-based, infrastructure-wide dataset, as it requires not

Fig. 6.7 Correlation matrix composed of numerical features.

only a complete infrastructure with a sufficient level of integration between the components, but also a complete and fully functional closed-control-loop running on top of it. Taking also into account that, in addition to the above, there is an automatic feature extraction system running.

In the context of the current thesis, the utilisation of network emulators assumes a pivotal role in the generation of diverse scenarios for dataset collections. These emulators enable us to recreate controlled environments with precision and accuracy, facilitating the rigorous examination of various network conditions and their impact on our study. This has favoured the generation of a large number of use cases that, in conditions of limited hardware, would be very difficult to achieve in real life. In addition, the incorporation of a message bus

represents a critical decision with far-reaching implications. It serves as a foundational element that enables the scaling of distributed software components across the infrastructure. This strategic choice not only enhances the system's ability to accommodate an expanding number of components but also fosters improved communication and coordination among these distributed elements.

Upon the successful development of a monitoring tool capable of extracting metrics from a particular entity, a significant advantage emerges: the inherent extensibility of such a tool. This extensible functionality empowers users to incorporate additional metrics as needed, providing the system with future-proof capabilities. Finally, in our initial prototype, we recognised the significance of establishing interconnections between network components among timestamps, as they would play a crucial role in facilitating future AI training at a later stage. Consequently, a fundamental design principle that emerged was the incorporation of timestamps within every available interface in the proposed system. This design choice enables a traceability process. This approach aids in understanding both the context and timing of event generation within the system.

6.8 Conclusions

This chapter recognises the need for a new dataset that could capture the complexities of B5G networks, including their topologies at various levels and the dynamic nature of network control rules. To do so, the framework presented in Chapter 5 has been used to create a novel and comprehensive networking dataset, IW-IB-5GNET, that is infrastructure-wide and intent-based. The proposed dataset addresses the pressing need for more robust and adaptable data-driven solutions in network management and optimisation in B5G networks. These solutions can be used by both ISPs and DSPs to improve the management and optimisation of their network policies in both the Edge and Core network segments. The presented dataset offers several key advantages in terms of network management and optimisation. Firstly, its infrastructure-wide reach ensures that it encompasses the entire network ecosystem, providing a broad view of network dynamics and status. This inclusiveness is vital as networks become

increasingly complex and interconnected. Secondly, the dataset is intent-based, achieving that it not only documents the technical aspects of the network, but also takes into account the underlying intents and control actions that drive network policies. This characteristic makes it the ideal candidate to address the main objective of this thesis, which is the optimisation of such network policies.

The completion of this chapter is essential, since in the following chapters the IW-IB-5GNET dataset will be used to develop the rest of the objectives of this thesis. It is worth mentioning that the results in this chapter have been the most difficult to achieve, as numerous iterations of the design and implementation were carried out until the final dataset structure and adequate results were accomplished.

Chapter 7

IW-IB-5GNET dataset preprocessing and labelling

The information provided in this chapter and all its contributions correspond to the achievement of objective 5.

7.1 Introduction

Accurately labelling a dataset requires a deep understanding of the domain to which it belongs, a crucial requirement to ensure data integrity, quality and usability. This need is essential in the context of network datasets, where the complexity and specificity of the information requires specialised knowledge. Network datasets include data on network traffic, protocols, network policies and potential security threats, among others, which require specialised knowledge to interpret correctly. Incorrect labelling can lead to significant errors in subsequent analysis, misinterpretation of network behaviours and flawed security measures. Therefore, high-level expertise is essential to discern subtle distinctions, identify relevant patterns and provide accurate labels, ensuring the reliability of the dataset and the validity of the conclusions drawn from it.

This chapter explains in depth the additional preprocessing and labelling processes of the dataset presented in the previous chapter. For this purpose, a data pipeline has been designed and implemented in order to adapt the data, from data collection to labelling. In addition, this

chapter presents the fundamentals of the three datapath technologies (iptables, OVS and TC) in terms of performance and efficiency, as the decisive labelling principles highly depend on them.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows: the research methodology is presented in Section 7.2. The two steps of the methodology, which are clustering and labelling, are explained in Section 7.3 and 7.4 respectively. Results of these process are presented in Section 7.5. Finally, Section 7.6 concludes the chapter.

7.2 Methodology

This section describes the methodology followed in this chapter in order to obtain a final labelled dataset. For a better identification of each of the steps, Figure 7.1 represents the process designed and carried out.

The first step is data collection, where raw data is gathered. As explained in previous chapters, raw data is obtained using the IDEM component. From this point onwards, all phases take place offline. Then, in step number 2, data cleaning and EDA are performed. This step involves handling missing values, removing duplicates and correcting errors. The objective is to transform raw data into a consistent format suitable for the following exploratory analysis, where statistical and graphical techniques are used to understand the main characteristics of the data. The reader can refer to Section 6.6 to review these steps. Step 2 results in what has been referred to in the previous chapter as the *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset. This dataset is henceforth referred to as *IW-IB-5GNET-unlabelled*.

Following with the process, step 3 represents the data clustering phase. Clustering techniques are a type of unsupervised ML algorithms that group similar data points together. The use of such technique has helped in managing the *IW-IB-5GNET-unlabelled* dataset by reducing its size without losing significant information. This subset of data has been referred to as *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced*. To conclude with the pipeline, step 4 represents data labelling. This step involves assigning meaningful labels to the selected subset of data (the *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced* dataset). The labels are the three possible datapath technologies to

Fig. 7.1 Comprehensive steps in the Data Science Process: from data collection to data labelling.

obtain optimal network policy implementations. This labelled dataset is called the *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled*.

The presented pipeline is completed in the subsequent chapters, until a complete ML process design is obtained. This chapter focuses on the development of steps 3 and 4.

7.3 Data Clustering implementation

The result from previous chapter, the *IW-IB-5GNET-unlabelled* has around 65,000 instances and 64 features. It would be unfeasible and inefficient to label such dataset due to time constraints. Thus, a stratified sampling based clustering technique has been used. It involves using clustering algorithms to group data into clusters (strata) and then sampling from these clusters to create a representative subset. Around 10% of the original dataset has been decided to be selected in order to train the future model, which corresponds to 6,500 instances approximately.

Clustering is a type of unsupervised ML method used in exploratory data analysis to identify inherent groups within a dataset. The goal is to separate a collection of unlabelled instances into distinct clusters, where samples within the same cluster exhibit similarities and samples across different groups are different [103]. For this approach, the K-means algorithm has been used [104].

The k-means algorithm is a very popular and effective clustering method. The following reasons have been taken into account in their selection. The main one is its simplicity, being

a straightforward method to understand and implement. It iteratively assigns data points to clusters based on their proximity to the cluster centroids and updates the centroids until convergence. Furthermore, it is computationally efficient, presenting a time complexity of $O(nkt)$, where n is the number of samples, k is the number of clusters, and t the number of iterations. This makes it suitable for relatively large datasets. Other relevant factors are its scalability in terms of number of samples and number of features, its convergence and, that it operates with a predefined number of clusters. The latter is a key factor, as will be seen below, in the selection of the subset of data.

The implementation of this technique has been carried out using the Scikit-learn Python library [105]. The steps developed have been as follows:

1. Apply K-means Clustering. This step includes several phases, described below.
 - Binary and categorical features encoding.
 - Input data normalisation using the Standard Scaler. This method standardise features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.
 - Number of clusters specification. This parameter is a prerequisite of the algorithm and also a strength of its use. Specifically in our data, $k = 7$.
 - Fit the K-means algorithm to the input dataset to obtain the 7 cluster assignments.
2. Sample data from the clusters. For each of the clusters obtained, random selection of approximately 1000 instances. The number is not exact because a more exhaustive analysis was carried out. For those clusters where there were many samples, a few more were chosen and the same was done with the groups with fewer samples. This process has resulted in the selection of a total of 7600 instances.
3. Combination of these sampled instances to form the final subset (the *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced* in Fig. 7.1).

The use of this technique has allowed the selection of a subset of data while maintaining the integrity and diversity of the data patterns, which will be crucial for the further development of reliable ML models. Besides, working with a smaller, yet representative subset of

the data reduces computational costs and time, improving efficiency in the subsequent phases of the ML pipeline.

7.4 Data Labelling

In this phase, labels are assigned to each of the samples chosen from the previous section. The *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced* dataset is labelled with one of the three datapath technologies available in our network: iptables, OVS or TC. The target implies that the network policy is either left as it is now or implemented in one of the other technologies available, as one of the other technologies is considered the optimal one.

To perform the labelling accurately, it has been essential not only to clarify theoretical concepts regarding each datapath technology but also to establish some labelling principles. Each of these is detailed below.

7.4.1 Theoretical concepts of datapath technologies

Chapter 2 introduced the different datapath technologies available in our network and their location within the network interface (see Fig. 2.3). In this section, we will focus more on the performance of each of them, as this will be a key factor in the selection of technology.

IPTABLES

As explained before, iptables is a Linux tool used to set up, maintain, and inspect tables of IP packet filter rules. It allows the control of network traffic by defining rules that match packets based on various criteria, such as source/destination IP address, port number, and protocol type. It works by interacting with the packet filtering hooks in the Linux kernel's networking stack, the netfilter framework.

Iptables defines five hook points in the kernel's packet processing pathways: PREROUTING, INPUT, OUTPUT, POSTROUTING and FORWARD. Built-in chains are attached to these hook points [42]. Chains are sets of rules that are applied to network packets as they flow through the Linux kernel's netfilter framework. In addition, iptables comes with

Fig. 7.2 Network packet flow and hook points for the mangle table.

three built-in tables: `filter`, `mangle` and `nat`. Each table is pre-configured with chains corresponding to one or more hook points. As an example, Figure 7.2 shows the relationship between the `mangle` table and its chains. Chains represent hook points in the packet flow while tables represent the types of processing that can occur. In the example shown, the `mangle` table is used for specialised packet alteration.

Each table has its own purpose and default chains. Rules within the same chain are processed sequentially. Specifically, rules in a chain are evaluated in a sequential and top-down manner. This implies that the first rule in the chain is checked first, followed by the second, and so on, until a match is found or the end of the chain is reached. When a packet is matched, the action associated with such rule is executed. For instance, `ACCEPT`, `DROP` or `REJECT`. It is important to mention that, when a rule matches a packet, the corresponding action is taken immediately, and no additional rules in the chain are evaluated for that packet. After evaluating all the rules in a chain, if none of the rules match the packet, then the default chain policy is executed. The packet flow from one network interface to another is presented in Table 7.1.

In terms of performance, since `iptables` processes rules sequentially, it can be considered a linked list data structure. Thus, the time complexity for both insertion and deletion is $O(1)$ in the best case and $O(n)$ in the worst case. Furthermore, the time complexity for search in a linked list is $O(n)$ in both the best and worst cases. This means that the order and number of rules greatly affects performance. Having a large number of rules can potentially slow down packet processing, as more rules must be checked before a match is found. Scalability

Table 7.1 Packet flow in the forwarding path.

Table	Chain
1 mangle	PREROUTING
2 nat	PREROUTING
3 mangle	FORWARD
4 filter	FORWARD
5 mangle	POSTROUTING
6 nat	POSTROUTING

is therefore also compromised, as large rule sets lead to significant performance degradation because each packet requires more comparisons. The type of rule and the type of traffic will also affect the performance and processing time of the rules.

LINUX TC

TC is a user-space program used to configure traffic control in the Linux kernel [40]. Traffic control consists of the following actions: egress traffic shaping, scheduling the transmission of packets, policing the ingress traffic and dropping both on ingress and on egress [106]. TC is composed of classifiers and filters, which work together to conform a hierarchical and flexible rule-matching algorithm. The Queueing Discipline (qdisc) is responsible for the management of packet queues. It provides the structure in which the classifiers and filters operate. The qdisc is the major building block on which all of Linux TC is built. It can be classful, containing classes and other qdisc, or classless. Examples of qdisc are: Fair Queueing Controlled Delay (fqcode), Hierarchical Token Bucket (HTB) and PRIO.

When a packet arrives at the TC datapath in the network interface, it is first handled by the qdisc, as shown in Figure 7.3. It categorises the packet into a class using a classifier, which inspects packet headers or other metadata to determine the appropriate class. The most advanced one is the u32 classifier [107]. It entirely based on hashing tables, which make it robust when there are many filter rules. Filters of the specific qdisc are then used to check the packet against defined rules. These rules are ordered in lists by priority, in ascending order. Filters have actions associated with them, so the packet that matches the rule will be subject to that action. Examples of actions are enqueueing in a specific class, dropping, marking, or

Fig. 7.3 Example of a simple queuing discipline with multiple classes.

redirecting the packet. Finally, qdisc is in charge of managing how the packet is dequeued and transmitted according to the rules and policies in place.

Regarding time complexity, it would depend on the specific implementation of the qdisc and its associated data structures (filters). A linked list that is processed sequentially is one of many possible internal structures of a filter, presenting a time complexity of $O(n)$ as explained before. If, on the other hand, a hierarchical structure is designed (as presented in Fig. 7.3), we will have the complexity of a tree-like architecture. Finally, in terms of performance, the hierarchical nature of classifiers and qdisc ensures efficient management and scalability. Efficiency is enhanced by quick packet matching, this is achieved through the use of specific bits for filters such as u32.

OPEN VIRTUAL SWITCH

As it has been presented in Figure 2.3, OVS is a multi-layer virtual switch on top of TC datapath. It is a powerful tool that uses a combination of multiple rule-matching algorithms to efficiently handle packet processing.

In Open vSwitch, packet forwarding is managed by two main components. The first, `ovs-vswitchd`, is a user-space daemon that operates consistently across different operating systems and environments. The second component, a datapath kernel module, is usually custom-built for the host operating system to optimise performance. Figure 7.4 shows

Fig. 7.4 Components, interfaces and packet flow of OVS.

the interaction between these components. The datapath module, located in the kernel, initially receives packets from a physical or virtual network interface. If `ovs-vswitchd` has provided instructions for these packets, the datapath module executes them, which may involve transmitting the packet, modifying it, sampling it, or dropping it. If no instructions exist, the datapath module sends the packet to `ovs-vswitchd` in the user-space. There, `ovs-vswitchd` decides on the packet's handling and sends it back to the datapath with the necessary actions. Additionally, `ovs-vswitchd` typically instructs the datapath to remember these actions for future similar packets [41].

OVS is often used as an SDN switch, primarily controlled via OpenFlow. This simple binary protocol allows a controller to manage flow tables and their flows by adding, removing, updating, and monitoring them. It also lets the controller divert specific packets and inject packets into the switch. In OVS, `ovs-vswitchd` receives flow tables from the controller, matches incoming packets from the datapath module to these tables, applies the corresponding actions, and then stores the results in the kernel datapath. This design ensures the datapath module doesn't need to understand the details of the OpenFlow protocol, simplifying its operation.

OVS utilises a tuple space search classifier [108] for packet classification in both kernel and user-space. This method involves creating hash tables based on the matching fields of

flows. If all flows match on the same fields, a single hash table is used. When new flows with different match fields are added, a new hash table is created for those fields. Each hash table corresponds to a unique set of fields, and searches must check all relevant hash tables. If a match is found, the flow is identified, and if multiple matches occur, the highest priority flow is selected. This classifier is efficient because updates require only a single hash table operation, making it ideal for environments where flows are frequently added and removed. Additionally, the classifier can handle any number of packet header fields without changes to the algorithm, and it uses memory proportional to the number of flows.

In terms of search complexity, the procedure performed by OVS can be summarised in two steps:

1. Exact Match Cache (EMC): it is a hash table that provides constant time $O(1)$ lookup for exact match entries. It is located in the kernel-space. This is the first and fastest mechanism OVS uses to determine what to do with an incoming packet. If a match is found, the packet can be processed very quickly. If the action for the packet cannot be found in the EMC, the search continues with the second step. This means that the first packet will not find a match, having to take the long path, while subsequent packets will match this cache, as represented in Figure 7.4. This results in an extraordinary improvement in terms of rule lookup time.
2. The Datapath Classifier, located in user-space, handles general packet classification in the slow path using a tuple space search algorithm. Rules are indexed in a megafLOW table based on their field masks, representing an active subset of all OpenFlow flow tables. To avoid the high cost of proactive cross-product computation, the `ovs-vswitchd` user-space daemon populates the megafLOW cache incrementally and reactively. As packets are processed through user-space flow tables, the system tracks which packet field bits are used in classification. The resulting megafLOW must match any fields used in these decisions. This approach ensures that the cache is populated based on current traffic, evolving with new entries added and old ones removed as traffic patterns change.

OVS presents a performance optimisation in terms of rule time matching. This is due to the EMC, which allows the process of packets at high speed for common flows. Furthermore, the combination of exact matches and classifiers allows OVS to scale effectively in various network environments. Finally, the tuple space search algorithm allows for flexible and complete rule matching, compatible with a wide range of policies and network configurations.

7.4.2 Labelling principles

With the knowledge of all these theoretical concepts, plus the practical knowledge of all the network experts in our laboratory, a set of principles for labelling the *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced* data was designed. These assumptions are detailed below:

1. Action Type. The type of action will dictate which datapath technologies can be used. Even if a large number of technologies are available, they cannot be used for all actions. If we go back to Table 2.1, it is seen that the drop action can be implemented with iptables, TC and OVS, indistinctly. However, there are other types of actions for which not all of them can be used. This constraint needs to be the first to be taken into account in the choice of technology.
2. Datapath location. The optimal decision in our use case depends on the action type and its position within the datapath technology interface. To prevent collapsing other datapaths, it is crucial to stop the traffic promptly. Consequently, we will prioritise the technologies shown in Figure 2.3 in the following order: TC, OVS, and lastly, iptables.
3. Datapath complexity. It is a metric primarily intended to represent search classifier complexity. As previously mentioned, iptables and TC share a similar complexity level, whereas OVS exhibits a simpler complexity in match searches. Consequently, the complexity rating for the TC and iptables datapaths is 8, while OVS has a complexity rating of 4. This indicates that OVS is the fastest datapath for rule matching, a crucial factor in use cases involving the dropping of malicious packets in the network. This metric corresponds to the *IW-IB-5GNET* features `IPTAB_complexity`, `OVS_complexity` and `TC_complexity`, respectively.

4. Control status. Refers to the maximum number of rules a datapath technology can support without compromising optimal performance. It is crucial not to exceed this number to avoid high congestion in the control plane of the network. According to the state of the art [109, 110] these approximate limits are 2048 for iptables, 4096 for TC, and 16384 for OVS. This metric corresponds to the features `IPTAB_numberRulesActivatedTotal`, `OVS_numberRulesActivatedTotal` and `TC_numberRulesActivatedTotal`, respectively.
5. Rule structure complexity. Rule complexity is a metric provided by the FCA software, according to specific measurement metrics. The type of rule to be implemented is another key factor in the choice of technology. This is because the more complex the rule, the more delay is introduced into the datapath in terms of time. Therefore, we will prioritise using the fastest datapaths for the most complex rules. This metric corresponds to the `ruleComplexity` feature of the the *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset.
6. Last matched time. This metric indicates the last time (in seconds) a rule matched a packet. A low value means the rule is actively in use, while a high value suggests the rule is not being used, leading to a check delay. Consequently, we will aim to either migrate these rules to OVS or delete those with a high `lastMatchedTime` value. Eliminating unused rules optimises the rule set, reducing the computational load on the network devices and improving overall network efficiency.
7. Rule activated time. This metric represents the number of seconds a rule has been active on the network. Analysing this metric (`activatedRuleTimeSecs`) in conjunction with `lastMatchedTime` allows for a better understanding of rule relevance and usage patterns. This helps to make informed decisions on which rules to keep, delete or migrate, leading to improved network performance by reducing check delays and improving resource utilisation.
8. Average matched packets and bytes. These metrics (`averageMatchedPackets` and `averageMatchedBytes`) aid in identifying the nature of network flows. A high metric

value strongly suggests a potential DDoS attack. Therefore, we prioritise migrating such rules to the outermost point of the network, which is TC and then OVS.

7.5 Results

Taking into account all the information provided in the previous section, labelling has been carried out. This phase has been time-consuming and challenging, as a large amount of data has been labelled.

The type of use case will greatly influence the decision on which technology to use. Thus, when it came to labelling our particular use case with drop rules for DDoS traffic, our main goal has been to maximise the best technology of the three, which is OVS in most of the cases. This is because OVS is the optimal technology in all aspects compared to the others. Although it is true that in certain occasions, TC has been prioritised due to its location within the datapath. Finally, iptables has been prioritised when it is the only available option or when the number of rules inserted in the other technologies is too high.

To explain the labelling process, Figure 7.5 has been presented. In the figure, it can be seen the NetLabeller GUI with different enumerated markers. These numbers represent the process followed in order to label the instance being displayed as a running example. In a first overview (see 'General info' fields), it can be seen that the experiment has been monitored on a physical machine (EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1), on its network interface called eth0. The reader might refer to Figure 6.1 to locate such network interface on the infrastructure. The flow sample affected by the action presents double encapsulation (vxlan and gtp) and its size is 512 bytes. This section also contains additional metadata such as the L3 and L4 protocols, the IP address and the destination port, etc.

Focusing now on the labelling, the first consideration is the type of action (see 1), which is to insert a drop. As we have already seen, this action can be performed with any of the three technologies in both ingress and egress. In addition, it can be checked that the three datapath technologies are available in this concrete experiment, so we have no restrictions regarding this field, meaning that it is possible to label the instance with any of them. The

Fig. 7.5 Example of labelling using the NetLabeller GUI.

second field we look at is in which technology the rule is implemented. In this case, the datapath technology iptables (see 2). Along with this information, it is observed that the rule has been inserted in iptables for a total of 8 seconds and that the information of matched bytes and packets has been updated 0 seconds ago, that is, the rule is active at this precise moment.

Attending now at the datapath location, as the sense of the traffic is on egress (see 3), the first datapath that is able to stop the traffic is iptables. However, we can check that the rule complexity for dropping a packet in iptables is 13 (see 4), which is high comparing with OVS rule complexity for the same action 5, and 3 for TC. Furthermore, as is has been discussed earlier, the complexity of the iptables datapath is 8, whereas OVS complexity is 4 (see label 5). At this point, there is a trade-off between the first datapath or the fastest one. TC can be discarded in this particular example, as it is the furthest along the datapath and has the same complexity as iptables. Therefore, the comparison must be made between iptables and OVS.

It can be seen that OVS is not congested, since the number of dropped packets is 0 (see label 6). Furthermore, the number of rules that are enforced on the network are only 4 and all of them are in iptables (see 7, where it is indicated that there are 4 rules inserted and the appropriate maximum is 2048). This explains why the 'Intent analytical information'

Table 7.2 Summary of *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset sizes after each phase.

Phase	Data Sizes				N° features
	Total	TC	OVS	IPTABLES	
Collection	64290	-	-	-	107
Cleaning and EDA	64290	-	-	-	64
Clustering	7600	-	-	-	64
Labelling	7708	360	7168	180	64

field only has graphs related to iptables rules (see label 8). Because of this, and given that we will always try to prioritise OVS for this type of actions due to its efficient rule search behaviour, the labelling decision for this example is OVS. It will be able to remove packets from the network in less time than iptables, a key factor when handling a DDoS attack. The boundary of this decision will be when OVS has more than 16,000 rules or other performance factors indicate that it is not an appropriate choice. With this information, the labelling of this instance is concluded. All that remains is to select the 'OVS' checkbox at the top (see 9) and click the save button.

A similar procedure to the one explained here has been conducted with all instances of the *IW-IB-5GNET-reduced* dataset.

It is important to mention that, after the labelling process, it was observed that the iptables datapath was not selected in any case. This is because, due to the nature of the experiments conducted, in no case are the other two datapaths saturated enough that it is necessary to select iptables. This made it necessary to re-run new experiments where iptables was better, in terms of being the only technology available or because the others were saturated. For this procedure, it was essential to manually insert rules into the TC and OVS technologies and then run the loop control described in previous chapters. This has not been an easy task, so it has not been possible to obtain many cases from these manual experiments mainly due to resource restrictions. A total of 180 new instances were added with this procedure. Table 7.2 summarises data sizes of the *IW-IB-5GNET* along the different steps described in Figure 7.1. The final result of this chapter is that the initial raw dataset has been reduced and labelled, resulting in a final size of 7708 instances and 64 features.

7.6 Conclusions

In this chapter, two distinct tasks have been addressed concerning objective 5. On the one hand, a clustering process necessary to simplify the size of our dataset, without losing the information necessary to train the model in the following chapters. The algorithm used has been k-means for its simplicity and ease of training.

On the other hand, the labelling process. The main achievement of this chapter has been the labelling of the subset obtained with the clustering. This process has been costly, as it has required an initial part of theoretical study of each of the technologies in the datapath. The knowledge of how each datapath technology work, together with the help of the NetLabeller framework to visualise all the information of the dataset in a single dashboard has facilitated the labelling of this dataset. Such task has been complex, time-consuming and difficult to tackle, taking a considerable amount of time during the development of this research work. As a result, a total of 7708 instances and 64 features are available for training the ML model.

After the labelling process using the NetLabeller tool, OVS represents the 92% of the rows while TC and iptables 5% and 3% respectively. This imbalance between the classes is due to the fact that OVS is the optimal technology in most scenarios, making it more difficult to generate use cases in which iptables or TC are preferable. This is, among others, based on the principles of OVS rule matching, which make it much faster than the iptables sequential matching. The following chapter seeks to address this critical limitation.

Chapter 8

Handling imbalanced networking tabular data using conditional generative models

This chapter and all its contributions are directly related to outcome number 3, the accepted conference paper entitled “Handling Imbalanced 5G and Beyond Network Tabular Data Using Conditional Generative Models” [5]. The original content of this paper has been extended in the following sections: related work (8.2), research methodology (8.3) and experimental results (8.5) with the intention to provide a more complete and exhaustive related work analysis and experimental results.

The objectives associated with this chapter are number 6 and 7.

8.1 Introduction

Data imbalance is a challenge encountered in multi-class classification ML problems when the distribution of classes in a dataset is uneven. In other words, one or more classes have significantly fewer instances compared with others. As a result, models may struggle to adequately learn patterns and features associated with the minority class, as they tend to be biased towards the majority class. This imbalance can present difficulties for ML models during training and evaluation, reducing its performance. Data imbalance can manifest in various domains, such as finance, medicine, or cybersecurity [111]. In the particular context of B5G networks, this issue assumes particular significance as it directly affects the efficacy

of ML models deployed for tasks such as anomaly detection [112], traffic classification [113] and network management and optimisation [3]. B5G networks generate vast amounts of data related to different parts of the network, with various types of communication patterns and activities. In the specific case of network control, the distribution of control policies and their associated network rules and events can show a substantial imbalance, with certain activities occurring more frequently than others. This imbalance poses a challenge for ML models, as they may disproportionately emphasise the majority class of network events, neglecting the importance of less common but also critical activities [114]. Therefore, addressing data imbalance in B5G network data is essential to enhance the reliability and effectiveness of ML models tasked with ensuring the security and optimal performance of these advanced communication networks.

Three approaches exist for managing class imbalanced data: altering the target cost function, employing sampling techniques (under-sampling and over-sampling), and generating synthetic data [115]. The most popular option has consistently been to use sampling techniques, such as Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) and Adaptive Synthetic Minority Oversampling (ADASYN). However, such traditional methods can be computationally expensive for large datasets. Over-sampling methods tend to duplicate existing information which leads to overfitting problems and under-sampling methods are prone to information loss. Thus, in this research work synthetic data methods are explored, as they generate completely new data based on patterns, rather than duplicating existing data.

This chapter explores synthetic data generation methods, in light of the emergence and recent growing popularity of these new techniques in computer networks. Particularly, this chapter presents the implementation, evaluation and comparison of four different generative models: Conditional Tabular GAN (CTGAN), CopulaGAN, Gaussian Copula and Tabular Variational Auto-encoder (TVAE). To do so, a synthetic data generation framework has been designed and implemented along with a hyper-parameter tuning pipeline to obtain the optimal model results (outcome 10). The main contribution lies in the comparison of statistical (Gaussian Copula) versus neural models (CTGAN, TVAE), and a combination of both (CopulaGAN). All these models are characterised by the fact that they are conditional,

i.e., they allow generating conditional synthetic data to deal with the data imbalance problem. The ultimate objective of this comparison is to provide the best generative model with which to generate data for balancing the *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows: related work is presented in Section 8.2. Section 8.3 summarises the methodology, introducing the dataset used, the generative models compared and the research design and procedure. The implementation details are specified in Section 8.4. Experimental results are shown in Section 8.5. Finally, Section 8.6 concludes this chapter.

8.2 Related Work

Traditionally in synthetic data generation, classical statistical methods were used, such as Copulas [116]. These methods consist of constructing a joint multivariate probability distribution for a given dataset, and subsequently sampling from this distribution. More recently, Deep Learning (DL) methods are increasing in popularity, where data generation is accomplished by creating generative models using neural architectures, such as Variational Auto-encoders (VAE) [117] or Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [118]. While generative models have existed for an extended period, it is only in recent years that their application to tabular data generation has gained significant attention, particularly using GANs. Since then, several generative tabular data models have been proposed, such as Tabular GAN (TGAN) [119], CTGAN [120], CopulaGAN [121] and TableGAN [122].

Focusing on networking datasets, numerous research works have explored the viability of utilising synthetic data algorithms to empower synthetic minority instances, aiming to re-balance datasets for training purposes. The popularity of these models is reflected in the multitude of publications in recent years, in which various generative models have been implemented for improving network datasets. Table 8.1 lists the most relevant related work found in the literature. Three clear trends can be distinguished: traffic classification, intrusion detection and anomaly detection.

Table 8.1 Identification of research works related to synthetic network data generation.

	Work	Algorithm	Dataset	Evaluation
Traffic classification	[115]	SMOTE-SVM	NIMS	CART RF
	[123]	ACGAN	NIMS	SVM DT RF
	[124]	TrafficGAN	USTC-TFC2016	MLP CNN
	[125]	FLOWGAN	ISCX	MLP
	[126]	PacketGAN	ICSX2012 USTC-TFC2016	MLP CNN
Intrusion detection	[127]	GAN	UGR'16	MLP
	[128]	GAN	CICIDS2017	RF
	[129]	IDSGAN	NLS-KDD	MLP
Anomaly detection	[112]	CGAN	KDD99 NLS-KDD	FFN
Policy Optimisation	Ours	CTGAN TVAE CopulaGAN Gaussian Copula	IB-IW-5GNET	RF SVM KNN XGB

In the traffic classification section, the first research work is [115]. They used traditional ML models (Classification and Regression Trees (CART) and Random forest (RF)) to evaluate the performance of three algorithms in the Management and Security Group (NIMS) dataset [130]. Two of them were traditional sampling techniques and the third was an improved version of the SMOTE model using Support Vector Machines (SVM). The results showed that the performance of the classification algorithms were improved when they were trained on the augmented dataset. In addition, they proved that the synthetic data generated by the SMOTE-SVM model performed better than the sampling models. One year later, Vu et al. [123], implemented an Auxiliary Classifier GAN (ACGAN) model for the same dataset. The results presented demonstrated that using ACGAN to generate synthesised data for network traffic classification problem helps improving the performance of supervised

learning algorithms. In addition, they showed that the GAN-based model performs better than SMOTE-SVM algorithm.

Liu et al. proposed a new algorithm called TrafficGAN in [124]. They developed a framework for HTTP traffic analysis and generation. They demonstrated the improvements obtained when the USTC-TFC2016 dataset was enriched with synthetic data generated with their proposed GAN-based model. Two other research papers in which the use of generative models in traffic classification datasets has proven successful are [125] and [126], presenting FLOWGAN and PacketGAN respectively.

In relation to the enrichment of datasets for intrusion detection, recent research has been published. Yilmaz et al. [127] implemented a GAN to re-balance a popular networking dataset for intrusion detection, the UGR'16. The results show the performance of a Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) model with the dataset imbalanced and balanced using the generative model. They prove that a priori, even the results with the imbalanced dataset seem to be adequate, such results are misleading as the minority class is not being detected. This is solved using the generative model proposed.

Lee and Park ratify in [128] that the performance of their RF model was better when it was trained with balanced data using a GAN algorithm. They use the CICIDS2017 [131] dataset to perform the experiments.

To conclude this section, the paper of Lin et al. [129] is presented. They propose IDSGAN, an improved GAN model that aims to perform different attacks by generating malicious traffic records. They used the NLS-KDD dataset [86] for training the generative algorithm and the MLP model to evaluate it. It is showed that their proposed model outperforms all the baselines by a wide margin, and the attack results are notable in both malicious traffic categories.

Finally, anomaly detection has also experienced a growing popularity in the application of generative models. As it is shown in the table, Ullah and Mahmoud present in [112] a novel framework for detecting anomalies in IoT networks utilising Conditional GAN (CGAN). They succeeded in constructing realistic distributions for a given set of features to overcome the problem of data imbalance. The performance of the proposed model was evaluated using

a Feed Forward Neural Network (FFN) and tested on two network-based anomaly detection datasets and five IoT network-based anomaly detection datasets. The table only shows the network-based ones, as they are the most concerning to us.

In view of the great popularity and success of generative models for networking datasets recently, it has been decided to evaluate different models to see which one is the most suitable for balancing our dataset. Thus, we will implement and evaluate four different ones, explained in the following section. Note that the evaluation of these models will be carried out according to metrics designed in this chapter. The evaluation with traditional ML classifiers will be carried out in the next chapter.

8.3 Methodology

This section presents the methodology followed in order to implement and evaluate the generative models. Section 8.3.1 presents the dataset details for the evaluation of the generative models. The four models to be compared are explained in Section 8.3.2. Then, the research design and the procedure for their evaluation are explained in Sections 8.3.3 and 8.3.4 respectively.

8.3.1 Dataset

The *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* dataset is composed of 64 features. In order not to over-complicate the training process, a subset of features has been selected. Different steps have been carried out, explained below.

The first one has been a throughout examination of each feature to detect the meta-data information that was not relevant for training the model. Features such as `iface`, `dstIP`, `macDst`, `dstPort` and `timestamp` were omitted during this step. Secondly, features comprising analytical information related to all the network rules currently enforced in the network has been also omitted in terms of simplicity. Thirdly, features that remained invariant across all instances were also removed. For instance, `13Proto`, `14Proto`, `tos`, `actionType` and `actionName`. With this elimination, the total number of features is 35, and the target.

These include 28 numerical features, 5 boolean features and 3 categorical. The target for each row specifies which datapath technology is most appropriate based on the specific needs of each use case and the state of the network at a given point in time.

As previously introduced, the subset examined (*IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* in Fig. 7.1) has an imbalance in the quantities of each target class. Figure 8.1 visually represents this problem, where OVS constitutes almost 92% of the rows, while TC and iptables only 5% and 3% respectively.

Fig. 8.1 Imbalanced dataset in terms of the number of instances for each target class.

8.3.2 Generative Models implemented

We refer to a generative model as a statistical or ML model designed to generate new, synthetic data that resembles a given dataset by capturing and representing the underlying data distribution. There are various types of generative models, depending on the design and fundamental philosophy. We can make a significant distinction between traditional statistical models and ML models. However, there are also generative models that are constituted by a mixture of both. The definition of the four different generative models used in this research work is presented below:

- **GaussianCopula.** A copula is a multivariate distribution that examines the dependence between many variables. It allows the joining of multiple univariate distributions to a single multivariate one [132]. To create a correlation copula, two or more unknown distributions are mapped to a well-known distribution. As a result, a joint probability distribution is created while still maintaining the individual marginal distributions. Copulas are based on the Sklar's theorem [133], which states that any multivariate

joint distribution can be written in terms of univariate marginal distribution function and a copula which describes the dependence structure between the variables. In particular, a GaussianCopula maps the marginal distribution of each variable to the standard normal distribution. Thus, it is possible to define a rich correlation between variables when it is not possible to directly define it. In this research work, a Gaussian copula synthesizer has been implemented to generate conditional tabular data. This probabilistic model uses the definition of each type of data distribution to map it to the Gaussian distribution.

- **CTGAN.** GAN models consist of a system that, given training data, generates synthetic data samples through the adversarial interaction of two neural networks. These networks are called Generator and Discriminator [118]. GANs generate class instances that do not represent random replicas of existing instances without removing valuable information in existing data instances. Thus, they overcome the limitations of traditional techniques such as statistical data sampling [111]. GANs are used in multiple domains, specifically for tabular data, several implementations exist such as CTGAN. CTGAN is a type of GAN that generates conditional synthetic tabular data to address several problems that other TGANs present, such as dealing with mixed data types, non-Gaussian distributions, multi-modal distributions and highly imbalanced categorical columns. All these challenges addressed by the CTGAN make it adequate for the problem presented in this paper.
- **CopulaGAN.** The CopulaGAN model uses a mix of statistical method based on copulas and GAN-based method to train a model and generate synthetic data [121]. As in the case of GaussianCopula, it uses the definition of the distributions of each of the input features to train the model and generate more accurate data. In addition, it builds on the strengths of GAN models for data sampling.
- **TVAE.** They are learning models that mix neural networks with probability distributions. Their main use is to build generative models that are able to produce synthetic data that follow the same patterns as the datasets they are fed on. The use of VAE is

Fig. 8.2 Proposed synthetic data generation framework and workflow description.

very popular for images, although there are also implementations for tabular data. We investigate the use and behaviour of TVAE for this type of data.

8.3.3 Research Design

Figure. 8.2 shows the design and workflow of our synthetic data generation framework. The presented framework is model-agnostic and able to deploy the four generative models. The large grey rectangle represents the complete framework, while the files at the top represent its inputs/outputs.

The process starts with the imbalanced dataset to be enriched, see “Real Data” in Figure 8.2. The data then go through a validation check, which consists of a test that determines whether the logic is valid for all rows of the data. The Validity Check module employs two different methods to verify the data: (i) it generates metadata information of the real

dataset to compile a description of the input data and (ii) it confirms all rows meet a set of pre-specified constraints. Metadata consist of an JSON object that describes the input data, including data types of each column, primary keys, category specification and date-time format. This will ensure that the synthetic data generated complies with the real data format.

Listing 8.1 displays a part of this JSON object.

```
{
  "columns": {
    "IPTAB_activated": {
      "sdtype": "categorical"
    },
    "IPTAB_TX_bytes": {
      "sdtype": "numerical"
    },
    "OVS_activated": {
      "sdtype": "categorical"
    },
    "OVS_TX_bytes": {
      "sdtype": "numerical"
    },
  },
}
```

Listing 8.1 Example of metadata.

Constraints ensure that every row in the generated data follow certain rules, regardless of how much data there are. For example, one constraint is that, for each row, the `packetSize` column must be between 0 and 1500 (bytes) as this is the maximum value for the Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU). Another is that, `totalMatchedBytes` column must be always greater than `totalMatchedPackets` column. Listing 8.2 presents the code of these two constrains specified in a JSON object.

```
{
  "pktSize": {
    "constraint_class": "ScalarRange",
    "constraint_parameters": {
      "column_name": "packetSize",
```

```
        "low_value": 0,
        "high_value": 1500,
        "strict_boundaries": false
    }
},
"totalB": {
    "constraint_class": "Inequality",
    "constraint_parameters": {
        "low_column_name": "totalMatchedPackets",
        "high_column_name": "totalMatchedBytes",
        "strict_boundaries": true
    }
},
}
```

Listing 8.2 Example of constraint definition for the MTU limit.

The complete list of the summary definition of restrictions can be found in Table 8.2. The table specifies the constraint identifier, for example `pktSize` and `totalB` in Listing 8.2. It is explained the features involved in the constraint and its description. Finally, there is a column to specify the type of constraint applied (Constraint class).

The workflow does not continue until the validation check has finished. Constraints ensure that no incorrect data is generated. Next, the Data Transformation module is responsible for carrying out functions to modify the data before and after modelling. Such functions include coding binary and categorical variables and normalising data. Once transformed, the real dataset is ready to be used for training the model. The selected generative model, previously specified in the configuration file, will be trained according to the configuration hyperparameters. As a result of this process, a model capable of generating synthetic data with similar characteristics as the real ones is obtained. This workflow is identical for the four generative models under study.

The workflow continues with the Conditional Sampling module. This component is in charge of solving the imbalance data problem. Therefore, data are generated according to a specified target, so that more data will be generated from the minority classes. Particularly,

Table 8.2 Summary definition of constraints

Constraint ID	Features involved	Constraint description	Constraint class
pktSize	packetSize	[0,1500]	ScalarRange
datapathActive	IPTAB_activated	TRUE if sense=EGRESS FALSE if sense=INGRESS	FixedCombinations
iptabMetrics	IPTAB_*all metrics	0 if IPTAB_activated=False	CancelDatapathMetrics
iptabMetricsRX	IPTAB_RX_bytes	> IPTAB_RX_packets	Inequality
iptabMetricsTX	IPTAB_TX_bytes	> IPTAB_TX_packets	Inequality
ovsMetrics	OVS_*all metrics	0 if OVS_activated=False	CancelDatapathMetrics
ovsMetricsRX	OVS_RX_bytes	> OVS_RX_packets	Inequality
ovsMetricsTX	OVS_TX_bytes	> OVS_TX_packets	Inequality
ovsMetricsRXdrop	OVS_RX_dropped	< OVS_RX_packets	Inequality
ovsMetricsTXdrop	OVS_TX_dropped	< OVS_TX_packets	Inequality
tcMetrics	TC_*all metrics	0 if TC_activated=False	CancelDatapathMetrics
tcMetricsRX	TC_RX_bytes	> TC_RX_packets	Inequality
tcMetricsRXdrop	TC_RX_dropped	< TC_RX_packets	Inequality
datapathActive	encapsulationLayer	1 if sense=INGRESS 2 if sense=EGRESS	FixedCombinations
bits	totalBits	> totalpktCount	Inequality
datapathActive	programmableTechnology	[IPTABLES, TC, OVS] if [IPTABLES, TC, OVS]_activated=TRUE	FixedCombinations
ruleTime	activatedRuleTimeSecs	[1,150]	ScalarRange
avg	averageMatchedBytes	> averageMatchedPackets & %packetSize=0	Inequality
crr	currentMatchedBytesPerPeriod	> currentMatchedPacketsPerPeriod & %packetSize=0	Inequality
totalB	totalMatchedBytes	> totalMatchedPackets & %packetSize=0	Inequality
totalP	totalMatchedPackets	>= averageMatchedPackets	Inequality
totalB2	totalMatchedPackets	>= currentMatchedPacketsPerPeriod	Inequality
totalP2	totalMatchedBytes	>= averageMatchedBytes	Inequality
totalB3	totalMatchedBytes	>= currentMatchedBytesPerPeriod	Inequality
datapathActive	target	[IPTABLES, TC, OVS] if [IPTABLES, TC, OVS]_activated=TRUE	FixedCombinations

we specify in the configuration file the desired number of rows where iptables and TC are the value of the target column. When the target is specified, the models match the columns and create the remaining columns based on the patterns that they learned. Thus, this module

ensures that the final dataset containing real data and synthetic data are not biased. The generated data are subjected to reverse transformations to obtain the format of the initial data. Finally, such new data need to pass the validation test. The validation check is the same done for the real data. Reject sampling is executed for those rows that do not meet the metadata and constraint requirements. This process means that the sampling time can greatly lengthen the synthetic data generation workflow.

It is worth mentioning that the design of the proposed framework is dataset agnostic, meaning that it can be used with any desired dataset. The only requirement is that the data must be tabular.

8.3.4 Procedure: Evaluation Metrics

Evaluating the data quality is a complex process as there is no single correct solution with which to compare results. However, there are different evaluation metrics that can give us an idea of the quality of our synthetic data compared to the real data. Two different reports have been used to evaluate the synthetic data generated, the Quality Report and the Diagnostic Report, provided by the SDMetrics library [134]. We use the Diagnostic Report to ensure that the synthetic data is usable. This report runs some basic checks on the synthetic data to give a general sense of the strengths and weakness of the synthetic data model. It captures the data coverage, structure and synthesis. The overall score should be close to 1.0 to confirm that the model has generated adequate synthetic data. The Quality Report assesses the synthetic data fidelity by examining how accurately it captures the mathematical properties present in real data. Utilising metrics specific to column types, the report quantifies these properties and provides a summary of the findings. It implements the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic [135] for numerical and date-time columns and the Total Variation Distance (TVD) for boolean and categorical ones. The score varies between 0.0 (worst) and 1.0 (best), this last one obtained when synthetic data distributions are exactly the same as the real data ones.

In order to obtain the optimal model results, a hyperparameter tuning pipeline based on the evaluation metrics has been designed and implemented. Figure 8.3 shows the model

Fig. 8.3 Hyperparameter tuning pipeline based on evaluation metrics.

tuning process. This process is based on trials, which are executions of an objective function in order to find the trial which maximises such function.

First, the model is trained with a set of initial random hyperparameters using the framework proposed in Figure 8.2 (which is represented with label 1 in Fig. 8.3). A synthetic dataset is obtained as a result of this process (see 2 in Fig. 8.3). Both real and synthetic datasets are subjected to the data evaluation procedure, which consists of generating the diagnostic and quality reports (see 3). The reports' scores are used to generate the optimisation metric of the objective function, which involves computing the averages of each report (see Algorithm 2 for details).

Results of the current trial are then stored in a log file (see 4 in Fig. 8.3). Finally, the optimisation metric is taken into account for generating a new set of hyperparameters (see 5). The optimisation process ends when the number of trials specified in the configuration file is reached. Then, the trial parameters that achieve the best optimisation metric are chosen.

Algorithm 2 Objective function definition.

def objective:

quality_score = *AVG*(*col_shapes_score*, *col_pair_trends*)*diagnostic_score* = *AVG*(*coverage*, *boundary*, *synthesis*)*opt_metric* = *AVG*(*quality_score*, *diagnostic_score*)return *opt_metric*

8.4 Implementation

The complete synthetic data generation framework has been designed, prototyped and implemented, offline to the B5G network architecture. In terms of software specifications, the whole framework has been implemented in Python3.8. The generative models and their evaluation reports have been implemented using the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) Python library [136], version 1.5.0. Optuna [137] has been the framework used for hyperparameter optimisation and Plotly library for data visualisation. The experiments have been carried out in a physical machine with the following specifications: Dell Precision T5810 with an Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 CPU, 10 cores with hyper-threading, 32794 MB of RAM, 512 GB SSD hard disk and a NVIDIA Quadro m4000. The operative system is Ubuntu release 20.04.4 LTS.

8.5 Experimental results

This section exposes an empirical comparative analysis of the models: CTGAN, CopulaGAN, GaussianCopula and TVAE. Such comparative analysis is the result of the procedure explained in Section 8.3, for each of the generative models.

The real data used to train the models consist of 7708 instances, of which 7168 corresponds to OVS target, 360 to TC and 180 to iptables. The models have been configured to generate 2000 unconditioned rows, 4500 rows targeted by TC and 4700 rows of iptables during the conditional sampling step (see Fig 8.2). This way, a balanced dataset composed of real and synthetic data is obtained.

8.5.1 Hyperparameter tuning and training results

Table 8.3 shows the hyperparameters selected of each model after the tuning process. Note that these parameters correspond only to the ML-based models. The hyperparameters taken into account for the model optimisation are: number of epochs, batch size, discriminator's and generator's Learning rate (LR) for GAN models, and the regularisation term (l2scale) for the TVAE algorithm. Batch size indicates the number of training samples used in one iteration, epochs corresponds to one full cycle through the training dataset and learning rates indicate how much the weights of the model are updated.

Table 8.3 Final hyperparameters for each model.

	Epochs	Batch Size	LR D	LR G	L2scale
CTGAN	10	150	1.9E-04	3.6E-05	-
CopulaGAN	300	50	1.5E-04	5.3E-05	-
TVAE	300	150	-	-	1.0E-05

It is noteworthy that in the case of GaussianCopula, only the specification of the distribution of each of the numerical variables is required, and no tuning is necessary. For this reason, a study of the distributions of each of the features of the dataset had to be carried out. In order to do this, it is needed to pass a `numerical_distributions` argument with `dict` that indicates the distribution that we want to use for each column. Listing 8.3 presents the definition of the distributions of a subset of features. Possible values for the distribution argument are: Gaussian, Gamma, Beta, Student T, Gaussian Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) and Truncated Gaussian. If not specified, the default setting is Gaussian KDE, which is a non-parametric method to estimate the probability density function of a random variable using a Gaussian kernel to smooth the data. It uses the data points to estimate the density function [138].

```
{
'IPTAB_RX_bytes': 'gamma',
'OVS_RX_bytes': 'gamma',
'TC_RX_bytes': 'gamma',
'totalBits': 'gaussian_kde',
'packetSize': 'gaussian_kde',
```

```

'activatedRuleTimeSecs': 'gaussian_kde',
'averageMatchedBytes': 'gaussian_kde',
'currentMatchedBytesPerPeriod': 'gamma',
'totalMatchedBytes': 'gamma',
'totalMatchedPackets': 'gaussian_kde',
}

```

Listing 8.3 Example of distribution definition.

In terms of execution time, Table 8.4 shows the time it takes for each model to be fitted and to sample the synthetic data. Note that these values correspond to each of the models tuned with the hyperparameters listed in Table 8.3. The times are shown in seconds (s) and the total time is also found in minutes (min) to make it easier to comprehend. It can be seen with this last column that the fastest model in overall is the CTGAN taking just 2 and a half minutes to obtain the synthetic conditional data.

Table 8.4 Total execution time for each model.

	Fitting (s)	Sampling (s)	Total (s)	Total (min)
CTGAN	47.46	94.83	142.29	2.4
CopulaGAN	1595.61	355.56	1951.17	32.5
GaussCopula	6.52	56870.57	56877.09	948
TVAE	321.88	152.25	474.13	7.9

Specifying the data distribution of each column slows down the sampling process, as observed in the results of the sampling column of CopulaGAN and GaussianCopula. TVAE is in between the rest of the models in terms of fitting and sampling. Finally, fitting time of GaussianCopula is minimal as it is not a ML-based algorithm. Nevertheless, the bottleneck of this model is in the sampling process, increasing the total time to almost 16 hours (948 minutes).

To conclude this section, Figure 8.4 shows a comparative graph of the number of samples of the target category in the real dataset and in the generated synthetic data. As it can be seen, the number of synthetic instances of each technology is inversely proportional to the number of instances in the real data. In this way, the balancing of the dataset is achieved.

Fig. 8.4 Real vs. Synthetic Data for column target.

8.5.2 Generative models performance

Table 8.5 lists the evaluation scores of the synthetic data generated with each model. ‘Column Shapes’ and ‘Column Pair Trends’ are from the Quality Report while ‘Coverage’ metric is from the Diagnostic Report. ‘Boundary’ and ‘Synthesis’ results have been omitted as they are all equal to 1.0, proving that generated data have successfully passed the validity check. ‘Total’ column represents the final score obtained with Algorithm 2.

Table 8.5 Evaluation metric scores for each model.

	Column Shapes	Column Trends	Coverage	Total
CTGAN	0.732	0.760	0.882	0.8531
CopulaGAN	0.817	0.806	0.893	0.8880
GaussCopula	0.593	0.775	0.931	0.8304
TVAE	0.693	0.778	0.869	0.8457

Overall, CopulaGAN is the best performing model. Its highest total score indicates that it is the model that best fit the shape and correlations of the real data. As for the diagnostic report (coverage column), it is observed that the best model is GaussianCopula. This is because the data distributions were indicated prior to model training and with such information, it is able not only to cover the range of the original data to a greater extent but also to reproduce the correlations between the data better. Finally, TVAE and GaussianCopula are the models that score worst in the quality report compared to CTGAN and CopulaGAN. This indicates that models based on GANs are best suited to fit the data distributions.

Results of Table 8.5 can be visually demonstrated by plotting histograms and correlation matrices. Three different features have been randomly chosen to represent these results.

Figures 8.5, 8.6 and 8.7 correspond to the KDE distribution plot of three different numerical features of the dataset, to summarise model performances. The x-axis shows the range of values for each feature being plotted, while the y-axis represents the density of occurrence of the feature at different points along the x-axis. In the figures, the real data distribution is the only one that is filled in. The synthetic data distributions are represented as continuous lines of different colours. The more closely the continuous lines resemble the filled pink curve, the better the distribution of synthetic data.

Fig. 8.5 KDE distribution of real vs. synthetic data for column totalpktCount.

As it can be seen, each figure has a very different distribution. This will make each model a better fit to one column or another. For example, Figure 8.5 represents numerical distributions of the totalpktCount column for each model. It is observed that the only model that is not quite similar is CTGAN (purple), while the rest of the models fit very well to the variation of the real data. Figure 8.6 shows that all models fit the distribution of the packetSize column fairly well, with the exception of the GaussianCopula (blue). Finally, in Figure 8.7 all models generate reasonable approximations of the totalMatchedPackets column, even though CTGAN and GaussianCopula tend to generalise a little more.

Figure 8.8 illustrates the correlation matrix of real data and synthetic data using the four different models. The method employed for the matrix generation involved computing

Fig. 8.6 KDE distribution of real vs. synthetic data for column packetSize.

Fig. 8.7 KDE distribution of real vs. synthetic data for totalMatchedPackets.

the PCC for the numerical features, which quantifies the linear correlation between two sets of data. The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, quantifying the degree to which two variables are related. Concretely, each row and column in the matrix represent a different numerical feature, and the intersection of a row and column contains the correlation coefficient between those two features.

Fig. 8.8 Comparison of correlation matrices of numerical features.

Figure 8.8 also provides rich information about the data relationships and how well the generative models capture and are able to reproduce such relationships. In general, all models exhibit the ability to effectively capture correlations among features. However, it is apparent that CTGAN encounters challenges in accurately capturing certain numerical correlations.

Table 8.6 Correlation MAE for each generative model.

CTGAN	CopulaGAN	GaussCopula	TVAE
0.1815	0.1420	0.1114	0.1179

In order to quantify the error of these matrices with respect to the real one, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) has been calculated. Table 8.6 represents the MAE, for each of the models with respect to the correlation matrix of the real data. It shows that the model with the highest correlation error is CTGAN (which is consistent with Figure 8.8), followed by CopulaGAN.

8.6 Conclusion

This chapter addresses the imbalanced data issue of the *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* dataset, which involves comparing generative models to oversample the minority classes iptables and TC. The empirical results presented focus on the performance of four generative models: CTGAN, CopulaGAN, GaussianCopula and TVAE. The first contribution of this chapter is the development of a comprehensive tuning pipeline tailored for training and sampling each model. All this is integrated in a single framework that is also model agnostic. This framework aims to optimise the generative models, ensuring their effectiveness in addressing the imbalanced data problem. The comparative results involve two parts, the first one in terms of time execution, with CTGAN being the fastest model versus TVAE the slowest. The second part, in terms of data evaluation, provides a comprehensive analysis of model performance. Notably, the findings reveal that CopulaGAN stands out as the best model for generating synthetic data, obtaining a total score of 0.888. It is however true that CTGAN also achieves very satisfactory results and is substantially faster than CopulaGAN (2 minutes vs. 32). Thus, it is concluded that GAN-based models performed best in handling our imbalanced tabular dataset. It is worth noting that different results using the proposed framework can be achieved as the results presented in this work may vary depending on the input dataset used.

In the next chapter, the synthetic data obtained with the CopulaGAN model will be used to train a specific supervised ML classifier tailored to the use case presented in the introduction chapter. By using the synthetic data generated to train the future model, we will take advantage of all the benefits discussed in the related work section.

Chapter 9

Firewall optimisation using machine learning classifiers

This chapter and all its contributions are directly related to outcome number 4, the accepted conference paper entitled “Multi-Layer Multi-Technology Firewall Optimisation in Beyond 5G Networks Using Machine Learning Classifiers” [6]. The content of this paper has been substantially expanded, especially in the following sections: related work (9.2), proposed architecture (9.3), methodology (9.4), implementation (9.5) and empirical validation (9.6). The objectives associated with this chapter are number 8 and 9.

9.1 Introduction

As already discussed in the introduction chapter, integrating AI with 5G techniques such as NFV and SDN is considered key technology enablers for B5G networks [139]. These techniques have changed network service deployment and operation, favouring the softwarisation of network components [140]. An important task emerging from such softwarisation is the automation of network security functions, which is leading to an unprecedented number of solutions for anomaly detection, firewalling and cyber-attacks discovery, among others. Such solutions trigger the definition and deployment of virtual distributed firewalls in order to mitigate traffic threats. Specifically, rule-based firewalls are the most widely deployed among traditional ones [141].

Firewall rules define how to react to ingress/egress traffic based on predefined security policies. In many cases, the definition of these firewall rules are human-defined or specified by an intent-based approach. While it is true that, with the automation of B5G services, both location and deployment of the firewall occur automatically. For this reason, it is considered that virtual firewalls deployed in B5G networks are a type of VNF, as it is a software-based instantiation of a network function that traditionally would have been implemented using dedicated hardware [142].

Optimising rule-based firewalls is critical for improving network performance, given the multitude of factors that can impede efficient operation. One of the key factors is that the volume of rules on a firewall inherently affects its performance, as an excessive number of rules inevitably affects its throughput [109]. In addition, the order of rules plays a crucial role, as an incorrect order of rules can introduce performance bottlenecks, especially when rules that are rarely matched are examined unnecessarily [143]. Furthermore, the reliance on human-defined rules introduces an inherent susceptibility to errors, as an oversight or misjudgement can compromise the efficiency of the network. Additionally, human decision making faces the challenge of defining automatic execution rules in advance without considering the state of the network at the particular time of enforcement. This often leads to sub-optimal decisions that will affect performance. Therefore, the implementation of firewall optimisation mechanisms is necessary to mitigate these performance limitations and ensure that the network operates at its full potential.

In this chapter, it is presented an approach for rule-based firewall optimisation that uses a supervised ML classifier to detect which datapath technology is the optimal at a particular time. This chapter aims to conclude the main objective of this thesis, which is to provide the network with an AI-based model for self-governance in the selection of optimal network control function technology by deploying virtual firewalls on the network. The *IW-IB-5GNET-balanced* dataset has been used for model training and evaluation.

The main contribution of this chapter is the study and analysis of multiple ML classifiers able to predict the best datapath technology to be used to implement firewall rules. To this aim, the chapter presents a comparison of four ML models: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN),

Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random forest (RF) and Extreme Gradient Boosting, XGBoost (XGB). To the best of our knowledge, this contribution is the first attempt to address firewall optimisation with this approach. The following are the main innovations presented in the chapter:

- Proposal of a novel multi-layer and multi-technology B5G architecture to enhance rule-based firewall optimisation using a ML-based approach.
- Presentation of a fine-grained subset of features over the B5G network to be used by the ML classifier.
- Empirical validation of a highly resilient ML model for the prediction of the optimal virtual function implementation of firewall rules.

The rest of the chapter is organised as follows: Section 9.2 presents the limitations of the current related work. Section 9.3 presents the proposed architecture that enables firewall optimisation. The methodology and the completed ML pipeline are presented in Section 9.4. The implementation details are specified in Section 9.5. Empirical validation of the ML classifiers are presented in Section 9.6. Finally, the conclusion is found in Section 9.7.

9.2 Related Work

Recently, research works are focusing on firewall optimisation and performance using different approaches. These approaches can mainly be divided into three different directions. The first one focuses on finding the optimal location where to deploy the firewall. The second approach focuses its efforts on finding the optimal deployment of virtual firewalls. The works presented with this approach are closely related to the previous ones and, on many occasions, the contributions are presented together. The third, on the other hand, focuses on optimisation based on rule ordering mechanisms and dependency resolution. We will focus more in-depth analysis on the latter group, as the objectives are similar to ours.

Starting with the first approach, based on the location of the firewall, Bringhenti et al. in [144] propose a methodology to automatically define the optimum allocation scheme

and configuration of firewalls in the logical topology of a virtual network. They achieve a performance improvement by minimising the number of firewalls to be allocated and the number of rules to be configured. Another example is [48] by Sanchez-Navarro et al., in which a new cognitive management framework to optimally decide the concrete location where to perform VNF placements is presented. It is based on new spatial metrics in 5G networks. Empirical results show that the approach scales effectively across large network topologies, handling over 1 million mobile devices and connections. It also achieves real-time performance in calculating spatial metrics, taking about 1 ms with optimisation, and managing constant topology changes in 5G networks within tens of milliseconds.

The second research focus is on the optimal deployment of firewalls, such as Salva-Garcia et al. in [145]. They propose an efficient automatic deployment of virtual firewalls using a VNF to deal with efficient rule distribution. Their results prove its advantageous performance and scalability, focusing particularly on the VNF-based firewall deployment time. Another related work is [146] where the authors introduce a new method for automated firewall allocation and configuration, utilising the flexibility of virtualised networks. Their contribution automates manual tasks and ensures correct security configurations through a formal method, identifying the optimal solution. Validation of the framework proposed shows it is effective for scenarios involving tens of virtual firewalls and similar numbers of security requirements.

Most of the research work in the third group is focused on the Optimal Rule Ordering (ORO) problem, which consists of dynamically updating the ordering of already enforced rules. Bagheri and Shameli-Sendi present in [143] a firewall performance improvement by introducing a new way of ordering rule-based firewalls distributed in a cloud. They consider that the most optimal rule order is when the topmost rules have the maximum hit rate. They achieve to eliminate inter-rule dependencies to enhance the performance and flexibility of ORO inside firewalls. Chowdhary et al. in [147] analyse the rule dependency relationships between the rules of different VNFs and propose a object-oriented policy conflict detection and resolution framework (OOPC). Its results achieve very fast security policy conflict detection in a cloud network with 60,000 OpenFlow rules. Previous works

include Abedin et al. [148], proposing algorithms to eliminate rule anomalies and merge rules, reducing the size of anomaly-free rule sets. However, their approach is limited to centralised firewalls. Zhang et al. [149] address anomalies using a firewall policy rules merging model based on rule-service, combining rule protocol, source port, and destination port. The model resolves conflicts with an action constraint strategy obtaining less filtering hits while processing the same packets as traditional firewall. Finally, Saâdaoui et al. [150] propose a new approach to rule-set optimisation and clean-up, by removing redundant rules from a firewall and an automatic method to detect and fix misconfigurations. This work addresses rule misconfiguration through techniques such as modifying rule fields, reordering, and removing rules, applied to dynamic environments. However, it does not regenerate rules.

Despite these and many other promising proposals of firewall optimisation, none of them consider the type of technology with which to implement such rule-based firewalls. In addition, little work has been found in the literature that proposes an optimal AI-based firewall solution. As highlighted by Ahmadi in [151], incorporating AI-based firewalls on a large scale presents a potent solution to address the dynamic and evolving nature of modern networks. These two factors have been the main motivation of this research work. This chapter aims to address this gap in the literature.

9.3 Proposed architecture for firewall optimisation

Figure 9.1 introduces the B5G network deployment together with the general architecture of the AI-based firewall optimisation framework proposed in this chapter. The architecture is split into two planes and three main layers, already explained in previous chapters. The lower part of the figure corresponds to the deployment of a B5G network, where both physical and virtual resources are located. It is in this part where the virtual firewalls are deployed, in each of the available interfaces of both the Edge and the Core segments of the B5G network. The colours of the firewalls represent their multi-technological characteristics (different types) in terms of the datapath technologies.

Fig. 9.1 Proposed multi-layer, multi-technology architecture workflow for firewall optimisation using ML-based classifier.

To enable our firewall optimisation approach, it is essential to have deployed sensors and actuator throughout the network. These components constitute the service and compute layers, represented in the middle part of the figure (control plane). Sensors are in charge of the topology discovering and the monitoring of every network component (device, network interface, datapath technologies, rules, and etc). As depicted in the figure, the sensors extract metrics from the multi-layer multi-technology virtual firewalls deployed in the infrastructure.

SMA, RIA, and RMA are our monitoring sensors, already explained in Section 2.5.2. The actuators, on their side, are in charge of controlling resources, communications and services of the network. In this particular case, the actuators (FCA and Policy Engine) are able to configure and insert the rules in the desired technology, based on network policies.

The management layer is located at the upper part of the figure. It is responsible for providing cognitive management capabilities to the network. This layer makes use of the metrics coming from the service and control layer to create informed decisions, automate and optimise network management tasks. This layer is composed of multiple components already explained in the previous chapters. In addition, new components after the data extraction module have been added, which are the Data Pre-processing module, the Firewall Optimiser, the Policy Engine and the Network Policy Conflict Solver. The components required for the ML-pipeline are explained below, assuming that the network is up and running and thousands of rules are currently inserted in the virtual firewalls of the B5G network.

The first essential component is the data storage, already explained in Section 5.3. In summary, all metrics from the monitoring sensors are stored in real time in a relational database so that all real-time network information is available at a single point. The data extraction module is in charge of gathering from such database the necessary features to feed the ML model. Specifically, the data extraction process consists of extracting, separately, the features of each specific rule enforced in the network. Thus, at the end of this process, a raw input to the model for each network rule to optimise is obtained (see Raw dataset in Fig 9.1). Once the data for a given point in time and for a concrete rule has been extracted, data are pre-processed in the corresponding yellow component, so that they are suitable as input to the model (see Processed dataset).

The Firewall Optimiser module, which is a ML classifier (see yellow box in Fig. 9.1), is then ready to make a prediction, in accordance with the decision principles explained in Chapter 7. The output of the model will be which datapath technology is the optimal firewall technology for the implementation of a rule. The Policy Engine component then uses the result of the Firewall Optimiser to rewrite the network intent if necessary. If a new intent needs to be written, it will have to go through the module in charge of ensuring that there are

no conflicts with existing policies, the Network Policy Conflict Solver. Finally, the optimised network policy is published in the message bus, where the FCA translates the policy into specific rules and configurations that will be executed by the network infrastructure in the data plane. It is important to highlight that, as a SDN, a dedicated machine manages the cognitive part of the management layer separately from the rest of the network. This separation ensures that there is no additional overhead on the data plane.

The proposed architecture presents a novel approach to firewall optimisation, promising a paradigm shift in efficiency and adaptability. By enabling the simultaneous analysis of hundreds of network rules, this innovative system enables the management layer to respond swiftly to changing network conditions without the need for human intervention. As the decision-making process is carried out based on real-time information from network sensors, this framework supports datapath technology-based rule balancing, allowing the deployment of network rules in all possible datapath technology configurations. It also drives an improvement in rule-matching time, as the rewritten rules are optimal at each analysed time. This solution will be highly desirable in our use-case, subject to a multitude of DDoS attacks, where optimal firewall performance is a necessity. Having the right rules implemented will result in effective attack management. With its ability to adaptively change configurations based on real-time feedback, this optimisation loop not only improves network performance, but also lays the foundation for a more resilient and scalable firewall deployment.

The rest of the chapter focuses on the ML pipeline in order to achieve the best ML classifier implementation, which will be the Firewall Optimiser module in Figure 9.1.

9.4 Methodology

This section introduces the methodology followed to obtain the ML-based optimisation model. First, the complete ML pipeline is presented in Section 9.4.1. Different models have been used to find the best one, these are described in Section 9.4.2. Finally, evaluation metrics for the model performance are explained in Section 9.4.3.

9.4.1 Machine learning pipeline for model development

Figure 9.2 presents the complete ML pipeline followed through previous and current chapters in order to achieve the best classifier. This is an extension of the already presented Figure 7.1. Chapter 7 has covered up to data labelling (tasks 1 to 4 in Fig. 9.2). The balancing of the data, represented in task 5, has been done in Chapter 8. In this chapter the remaining tasks are addressed, which are framed in the blue rectangle from tasks 6 to 9.

The labelling process has lead us to develop a data augmentation framework in order to balance the dataset. This framework has resulted in the generation of synthetic data samples of TC and iptables that also define the training set. After the data augmentation process (task 5), the *IW-IB-5GNET-balanced* dataset has been obtained. This dataset has been subjected to a set of pre-processing techniques and normalisation in order to adapt it to different classification models (see task 6). In addition, feature selection techniques have been performed to compose the final subset of features. Then, data has been split into two subsets, the training set and the test set. The train set is used to train each of the ML models and obtain the best hyperparamentes (task 7). The trained model results in the classifier, which is evaluated with the test subset (task 8). The best performing model, which is called Firewall Optimiser in Figure 9.2 indicated as task 9, is the one selected to be deployed in the B5G network.

The Firewall Optimiser component represents the final culminating innovation of this thesis.

9.4.2 Machine Learning classifiers

Four different supervised learning algorithms have been compared in order to find out which one performs better for our proposed framework and data. A brief description of the basic operation of each of them is given below:

- **K-nearest Neighbours (KNN)**: classifies data based on closest training samples. The process involves computing the K nearest neighbours for a new input, and the classification of the new input is determined by the majority among its neighbouring

Fig. 9.2 Complete ML pipeline (Blue rectangle identifies the modules addressed in the current chapter).

data points. This method is used for its simplicity of execution and low computation time [152]. The following are the parameters of this model that have been studied:

- `n_neighbors`: specifies the number of neighbours to use when making a prediction for a data point. When a new sample needs to be classified, the algorithm looks at the `n_neighbors` closest training samples in the feature space. The class of the new sample is determined based on the classes of these nearest neighbours.
- `weights`: defines how the influence of the neighbours is weighted when making a prediction. The three possible options are: (i) `uniform`, all neighbours have equal weight; (ii) `distance`, neighbours are weighted by the inverse of their distance, meaning that closer neighbours have a greater influence on the prediction than more distant ones. This one is particularly useful when dealing with noisy data or data where the class boundaries are not clear. Finally, (iii) `callable` for any other user-defined function.

- **Support vector machine (SVM):** SVMs can be understood from a geometric point of view, as they seek to find the boundary that separates the different classes with the greatest possible margin. This boundary is determined by those data samples that are closest to the other class, which are called support vectors. It is a widely used algorithm as it is very robust and has a solid mathematical basis [153]. The following are the parameters studied of this model:
 - `kernel`: specifies the type of kernel to be used in the algorithm. The kernel function transforms the data into a higher dimensional space to enable linear separation. The four possibilities are: (i) `linear`, which means no transformation; (ii) `poly` for the polynomial kernel; (iii) `rbf` Radial Basis Function (RBF), which corresponds to the Gaussian kernel and (iv) `sigmoid` for the sigmoid kernel.
 - `C`: corresponds to the regularisation parameter, controlling the trade-off between achieving a low error on the training data and minimising the norm of the weights. A small value may lead to a higher bias and a lower variance. Whereas a larger value aims to correctly classify all training examples (lower bias, higher variance), which could lead to over-fitting. The default value is 1.0.
 - `gamma`: defines how far the influence of a single training sample goes, with low values meaning far and high values meaning near. This parameter is only used for the `rbf`, `poly` and `sigmoid` kernels. The possible options are: `scale`, `auto` or a float. The default value is `scale`, which computes $[1/(n_features * X.var())]$ as `gamma`.
- **Random Forest (RF):** is a type of ensemble classification composed of multiple randomised decision trees that cooperate for distinguishing the class label for new unlabelled instances. The classification prediction is done by averaging. Its ease of use and model understanding, as well as its high accuracy, make it a widely used model in the research community [154]. The studied parameters of this model are listed below:

- `n_estimators`: specifies the number of trees. A larger number of trees usually improves the performance and stability of predictions, but also increases the computational cost.
 - `criterion`: specifies the function to measure the quality of a split. Supported criteria are `gini` for the Gini impurity and `log_loss` and `entropy` both for the Shannon information gain. The default criteria is `gini`.
 - `max_depth`: specifies the maximum depth of the trees. This parameter helps in preventing overfitting.
 - `max_features`: indicates the number of features to be taken into account when looking for the best split.
 - `max_leaf_nodes`: this parameter specifies the maximum number of leaf nodes in each tree. This helps to avoid overfitting by limiting the growth of the tree.
 - `min_samples_leaf`: specifies the minimum number of samples that a leaf node must have. This parameter also prevents overfitting by ensuring that leaf nodes have a minimum number of samples. A higher value will make the model more conservative.
- **Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost or XGB)**: is another boosting ensemble method, that combines multiple weak decision trees to create a global strong model. It is based in the gradient boosting algorithm and its objective is to minimise a loss function. It includes key features such as regularisation, columns sub-sampling or tree pruning to prevent overfitting. These features, together with its speed design, ease of use and performance make it a good choice for classification problems [155]. The parameters studied are:
 - `max_depth`: specifies the maximum depth of the trees. This parameter controls the complexity of the trees. Deeper trees can model more complex patterns, but may result in overfitting.

- `n_estimators`: specifies the number of trees or boosting rounds to fit. More trees can improve model performance but it will extend the training period, as well as overfitting if there are too many of them.
- `learning_rate`: controls the step size at each iteration. It is also known as η . Smaller values make the model more robust, but require more rounds of boosting to converge.
- `gamma`: this parameter specifies the minimum loss reduction required to make a further partition on a leaf node of the tree. Its default value is 0. Higher values make the algorithm more conservative by preventing overfitting.
- `reg_lambda`: specifies the L2 regularisation term on weights. This parameter helps to avoid overfitting by penalising large weights. The default value is 1.
- `reg_alpha`: specifies the L1 regularisation term on weights. It adds a penalty for large coefficients, encouraging sparsity and the default value is 0.
- `subsample`: indicates the fraction of samples to be used for fitting the individual base learners. The default value is 1, but decreasing this value adds randomness that will help to prevent overfitting.
- `colsample_bytree`: specifies the number of features to be used for each tree. This parameter, as the previous one, prevents overfitting by creating different tree structures. When the value is 1, all features are used.
- `min_child_weight`: specifies the minimum sum of instance weight needed in a child. Higher values prevent partitioning a leaf node when the sum of instance weight is less than `min_child_weight`. This can help prevent overfitting.
- `max_leaves`: indicates the maximum number of leaves in a tree. This parameter allows the control of the maximum complexity of the trees, which prevents overfitting. The default value is 0 that means unlimited.
- `objective`: indicates the learning task and the corresponding loss function. In our specific case, it will be `multi:softmax`, for multiclass classification using the softmax objective.

- `eval_metric`: this final parameter specifies the evaluation metric to be used during training. The default varies depending on the objective parameter. For the multiclass classification it is used the `mlogloss` metric.

9.4.3 Procedure: Evaluation Metrics

Four supervised learning algorithms have been analysed in order to find out which one is the optimal selection for our proposed framework. The evaluation metrics calculated to assess the classifiers' performance are: accuracy, recall, precision and F1-score. As the proposed problem is a multi-class classification one, recall, precision and F1-score metrics are calculated for each class as binary problems and then the averages of the three results are obtained.

A description of how each evaluation metric has been calculated is presented below. Note that TP means True Positives, TN stands for True Negatives, FP is False Positives and FN, False Negatives.

- Recall: measures the classifier's ability to find all instances where a particular datapath technology is truly optimal. This is crucial to ensure that there are no missed opportunities to use the optimal technology for a given scenario. For each datapath technology:

$$Recall_{tech} = \frac{TP_{tech}}{TP_{tech} + FN_{tech}} \quad \text{where } tech \in \{IPTABLES, TC, OVS\}$$

High recall for a technology indicates that the classification model is effective at identifying scenarios where that technology is the best choice.

- Precision: measures the classifier's ability to not label an instance as a concrete datapath technology that corresponds to another one. It is particularly important in this work to ensure that suboptimal technologies are not used unnecessarily. For each technology:

$$Precision_{tech} = \frac{TP_{tech}}{TP_{tech} + FP_{tech}} \quad \text{where } tech \in \{IPTABLES, TC, OVS\}$$

High precision for a specific technology suggests that when the model predicts that technology as optimal, it is likely to be the correct prediction.

- F1-score: it is interpreted as a harmonic mean of the precision and recall, where their contribution to the measure are equal. Thus, it provides a balanced measure of the model's performance. This metric is particularly useful in the present multi-class classifier in order to evaluate the model's performance across all three datapath technologies. For each one:

$$F1score_{tech} = \frac{2 * TP_{tech}}{2 * TP_{tech} + FP_{tech} + FN_{tech}} \quad \text{where } tech \in \{IPTABLES, TC, OVS\}$$

A high F1-score for a concrete technology suggests that the model achieves a good balance between correctly identifying scenarios where that technology is optimal and avoiding false positives.

- Accuracy: measures the overall correctness of our model's predictions across all three datapath technologies. It represents the proportion of correct predictions (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined. In our context:

$$Accuracy = \frac{CorrectPred_{IPTABLES} + CorrectPred_{TC} + CorrectPred_{OVS}}{Total\ predictions}$$

A high accuracy indicates that our model is generally reliable in selecting the optimal datapath technology for various use cases.

9.5 Implementation

This section presents the implementation steps, corresponding to tasks 5 to 9 of Figure 9.2. All this process has been carried out in an offline phase separate from the B5G network. In terms of software specifications, the whole process has been implemented in Python3.8, making use of popular well-known libraries such as Pandas and Numpy for data manipulation and analysis, and Scikit-learn and XGBoost for the ML classifiers deployment.

9.5.1 Data Augmentation

With the aim of addressing the data imbalance presented, a data augmentation technique was used. In particular, we implemented a CopulaGAN model [121] as in the previous chapter it was demonstrated that it stood out as the best model for generating synthetic tabular data based on our dataset. The results were 3% better than using CTGAN and 4% better than using TVAE.

CopulaGAN model was used to oversample the minority classes (iptables and TC) of the *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* dataset. Such synthetic data generated are used for training the classifiers, thereby balancing the distribution and improving the model's ability to learn from all classes equally. Table 9.1 summarises the data amounts used for each step of the process. Particularly, we used a total 7708 real data samples to train the CopulaGAN model. Then, we generated a total of 9292 synthetic samples using the CopulaGAN model. At the end of this process, a total of 17000 instances were compiled to train and test the ML classifiers. Thereby, an improved training set balance among the datapath technologies was achieved.

Table 9.1 Description of dataset sizes.

	Total Size	Total/Target		
		iptables	OVS	TC
Real Data	7708	180	7168	360
Synthetic Data	9292	4747	0	4545
Total	17000	4927	7168	4905
	100%	29%	42%	29%

9.5.2 Data pre-processing and feature selection

The *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* dataset included pre-existing data cleaning procedures carried out in task 2 of Figure 9.2. Nonetheless, a comprehensive reassessment has been conducted to detect and rectify any instances of null values and duplicates throughout the entire dataset, including the newly generated synthetic data (*IW-IB-5GNET-balanced* in Figure 9.2). The pre-processing step has also covered fixing any data errors, handling missing values, identifying and selecting the most important features, normalisation and data splitting. The type of

normalisation depends on each specific classifier implemented. Thus, it is specified in the following section.

Regarding feature selection, the *IW-IB-5GNET-labelled* dataset also included some initial selection, carried out with the aim of reducing the size of the synthetic data to be generated. Even though, in this new phase, a more rigorous process of feature selection has been carried out thereby eliminating two more features. Table 9.2 comprises 33 features of the *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset that compose the final dataset structure. Colour indicates topology levels: blue refers to datapath technology metrics, red to flow metrics and green and orange to rule metrics.

Table 9.2 Final features after feature selection.

1	IPTAB_activated	18	state
2	IPTAB_RX_bytes	19	totalpktCount
3	IPTAB_RX_packets	20	totalBits
4	IPTAB_TX_bytes	21	packetSize
5	IPTAB_TX_packets	22	programmableTechnology
6	OVS_activated	23	activatedRuleTimeSecs
7	OVS_RX_bytes	24	averageMatchedBytes
8	OVS_RX_dropped	25	averageMatchedPackets
9	OVS_RX_packets	26	currentMatchedBytesPerPeriod
10	OVS_TX_bytes	27	currentMatchedPacketsPerPeriod
11	OVS_TX_dropped	28	ruleComplexity
12	OVS_TX_packets	29	totalMatchedBytes
13	TC_activated	30	totalMatchedPackets
14	TC_RX_bytes	31	IPTAB_numberRulesActivatedTotal
15	TC_RX_dropped	32	OVS_numberRulesActivatedTotal
16	TC_RX_packets	33	TC_numberRulesActivatedTotal
17	sense		

To perform the feature selection, the correlation matrix of the features was obtained. Features pairs presenting correlations greater than 0.85 or less than -0.85 were chosen for omission, with one feature from each pair being retained. This process resulted in the elimination of two features, *encapsulationLayer* and *ContextSwitchesPerSecond*. This final step is essential not only for reducing redundancy but also for enhancing computational efficiency. Figure 9.3 shows the Pearson correlation matrix between the final numerical

features after omitting high correlation ones. The x-axis and y-axis are labelled with the corresponding number of feature in Table 9.2.

Fig. 9.3 Correlation matrix composed of final numerical features.

Splitting the dataset into train and test sets was the final step of task 6. Table 9.3 presents the subset's splitting, where a 80%-20% approach was followed. It is worth mentioning that the test set exclusively comprises real data, while synthetic data has been merely utilised for training the classifiers. This ensures the credibility of the results, as the models are tested only on real data. In addition, it can be seen that the training set is balanced to ensure that models learn equally from all classes.

Table 9.3 Train and test split.

	Total Size	iptables	OVS	TC
TRAIN SET	14000	4747	4708	4545
TEST SET	3000	180	2460	360

9.6 Empirical validation

This section aims to empirically validate the proposed ML model for firewall rules optimisation. It corresponds to tasks 7, 8 and 9 in Figure 9.2.

9.6.1 Hyperparameter tuning and training results

In order to obtain the best models' configuration, a hyperparameter tuning process has been carried out. Optuna [137] is the python library used for the optimisation process. The metric selected to be optimised was the F1-score. This deliberate decision has been motivated by the fact that the test set still has some imbalance in the data (as shown in Table 9.3). Thus, the accuracy metric is inappropriate as a high accuracy is achievable whether the classifier correctly predicts the majority class. However, F1-score provides a metric that strikes a balance between recall and precision metrics, which take into account each class separately. Therefore, using F1-score, the imbalance of classes is not a problem when evaluating the model.

Figure 9.4 presents the evolution of the F1-score over the last 50 best iterations of each classifier. The x-axis (trial number) represents different hyperparameter configurations for each model, while the y-axis represents the F1-score value obtained. From this figure, it can be seen that the best performing model is the Random Forest throughout all hyperparameter configurations, followed by XGBoost. Both have a very similar F1-score evolution. On the other hand, it can be observed that the KNN model needs less than 50 iterations to reach its maximum. The final hyperparameters that achieve the best F1-score for each classifier are shown in Table 9.4.

Table 9.4 also specifies whether each classifier needs normalisation and which one has been used. Particularly, Standard Scaler¹ from Scikit Learn has been used for KNN and SVM models, which standardises features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. Finally, training times have also been calculated for each of the specified configurations. This

¹The standard score of a sample x is calculated as: $z=(x-u)/s$, where u is the mean of the training samples and s is the standard deviation of the training samples.

Fig. 9.4 Evolution of F1-score during hyperparameter tuning.

concludes that SVM is the model that takes the longest to train with a clear difference, 8.7 seconds compared with less than 1 second for the rest of them.

9.6.2 Models performance comparison

Table 9.5 shows a comparative analysis of the quantitative metric results for each classifier, with hyperparameters specified in Table 9.4. As explained in Section 9.4.3, the results reflect the average of each of the classes separately.

Based on the results, it is concluded that the best model is Random Forest, as it has the highest F1-score (0.9083) and, consequently, the best recall. Furthermore, it is the best performing model in terms of training time (0.4s). It is also observed that KNN, despite having the lowest F1-score, has the best precision (0.9166). While it is true that the greatest accuracy is obtained in both RF and XGBoost (0.9710), XGBoost is not considered the best model because the imbalance presented in the test set makes the accuracy not the most appropriate metric.

To take a closer look at the prediction of each of the classes separately, the confusion matrix of each classifier was calculated. The confusion matrix, shown in Figure 9.5, is presented with the normalised predicted values, where 0 is the minimum and 1 is the

Table 9.4 Final hyperparameters and training results for each classifier.

Model	Normalisation	Hyperparameters	Value	Training Time (s)
KNN	Standard Scaler	n_neighbors	8	0.7
		weights	uniform	
SVM	Standard Scaler	kernel	rbf	8.7
		C	8	
		gamma	scale	
RF	No	max_depth	8	0.4
		criterion	entropy	
		n_estimators	97	
		max_features	5	
		max_leaf_nodes	20	
		min_samples_leaf	17	
XGB	No	max_depth	6	0.5
		n_estimators	104	
		learning_rate	0.05	
		gamma	13	
		reg_lambda	20	
		reg_alpha	0	
		subsample	0.85	
		colsample_bytree	0.8	
		min_child_weight	1	
		max_leaves	3	
		objective	softmax	
		eval_metric	mlogloss	

maximum. On the y-axis are the actual labels while on the x-axis are the predicted labels. This means that, for example in the case of XGB classifier, it is able to correctly predict all instances of OVS. Similarly, RF classifier is able to correctly predict 99% of OVS instances and 98% of TC, encountering some problems with iptables (73%). On the other hand, we observe that KNN and SVM classifiers, despite having lower F1-scores, are able to predict iptables better than RF and XGB classifiers. It is worth noting that the results presented in Table 9.5 and Figure 9.5 have been obtained from a training set composed of synthetic data. However, the test set is composed of real data only. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of using synthetic data to train ML classifiers when there is a clear data imbalance problem and generating more data is not a trivial task.

Table 9.5 Results of the quantitative metrics for each classifier.

	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy
KNN	0.7678	0.9166	0.8269	0.9387
SVM	0.8357	0.8872	0.8598	0.9537
RF	0.9304	0.9003	0.9083	0.9710
XGB	0.8787	0.8865	0.8816	0.9710

Fig. 9.5 Comparison of the confusion matrix of the classifiers under study.

9.6.3 Firewall Optimiser model

After performing the comparison of the four classifiers, it is concluded that the best model for the deployment of the Firewall Optimiser is the Random Forest. This section further details the performance of this model with the dataset under study.

As it has been introduced in Section 9.4.2, one of the benefits of RF is that it can reduce overfitting since the averaging of uncorrelated trees lowers the overall variance and prediction error. The prediction obtained from this model is the average result of each of the decision trees that make it up. In our RF implementation, all decision trees use the same criterion for splitting decision, which is entropy. This criterion is derived from information theory, which measures the amount of uncertainty or randomness in the data. It ranges from 0 (pure) to $\log_2(n)$ for n classes (maximum impurity). One of the differences between Gini and entropy is that entropy places its emphasis on balancing the sizes at the two child nodes [156]. Thus, entropy is more sensitive to changes in probabilities at each node, penalising impurity more heavily compared to Gini. This can lead to splits that produce purer child nodes.

To better understand the behaviour of performance in relation to its hyperparameters, several graphs are presented below. These graphs show the accuracy obtained as a function of the parameters mentioned in Section 9.4.2. Specifically, the accuracy of the model is evaluated in each graph as a function of the number of estimators (`n_estimators`), along with one of the other parameters shown in Table 9.4. For all experiments, the number of estimators has been varied between 50 and 110 in steps of 5. All other parameters that are not analysed have been left at their default values, except for the criterion, which we have always used entropy as it is the best type for our data.

Figure 9.6 shows the variation of the accuracy as a function of the number of estimators and the maximum depth of the trees (`max_depth`). As can be seen in the figure, the number of estimators has a major influence on the accuracy obtained. From 70 trees, the model is able to predict with a very high accuracy. Regarding the tree's depth, it is concluded that a low value affects model performance although not to a large extent. This is meaningful, as the trees cannot branch far enough to reach a final result. As the depth value increases, the

Fig. 9.6 Accuracy obtained with RF as a function of number of estimators and maximum depth.

accuracy obtained from the model improves. As shown in the figure, the highest values are around 8, which is in line with our final results for this model.

Figure 9.7 shows the variation of the accuracy as a function of the number of estimators as in the previous one, and the maximum number of features (`max_features`). The results show how, by adding the maximum number of features parameter, we can achieve much higher accuracy even for a very small number of estimators. For instance, for the case of 50 estimators, an accuracy of 0.95 is achieved, when in the previous case not even 0.7 was reached. The accuracy varies depending on both parameters, but in any case, values above 0.925 are always obtained. This shows that, by restricting the maximum number of features with which to do the splitting, more robust trees are generated with which we will obtain better results.

Fig. 9.7 Accuracy obtained with RF as a function of number of estimators and maximum features.

Figure 9.8 represents the variation of the accuracy as a function of the number of estimators and the maximum number of leaf nodes in each tree `max_leaf_nodes`. This parameter limits the growth of the trees, so a larger number of trees in the forest will be needed in order to obtain accurate performance. This fact is shown in the graph, as it is obtained an accuracy above 0.95 just with more than 100 estimators. This parameter is highly important, as it greatly reduces the risk of overfitting.

Finally, Figure 9.9 represents the variation of the accuracy as a function of the number of estimators and the minimum number of samples that a leaf node must have `min_samples_leaf`. Recall that a high number of the latter parameter will result in a more conservative model, thus leading to a more robust model. It is clear from the figure that, by adding this parameter, the optimal number of estimators is around 80. However, there is no clear pattern that determines what is the optimal number of the minimum number of samples.

Fig. 9.8 Accuracy obtained with RF as a function of number of estimators and maximum leaf nodes.

Analysing all these parameters separately helps us to understand how each of them affects the overall behaviour of the RF model. However, in none of the cases it is obtained the best accuracy presented in Table 9.4. This is due to the fact that we have to combine all of them to obtain the optimal combination of hyperparameters.

Another crucial element in assessing performance is the importance given by the classifier to each of the features in our dataset. Thus, the feature importance of the RF model has been calculated. Figure 9.10 presents a visual representation of which features have the most significant impact on the target variable. The 15 most relevant have been represented. The graph allows the understanding of the most relevant features for the classifier in order to make the predictions. These are clearly the direction of traffic (`sense`) and whether there is a virtual firewall in iptables (`IPTAB_activated`), followed by the number of rules inserted

Fig. 9.9 Accuracy obtained with RF as a function of number of estimators and minimum samples by leaf.

in the TC virtual firewall (TC_numberRulesActivatedTotal). These results are consistent with the analyses performed in the labelling chapter (Chapter 7).

To conclude with the Firewall Optimiser performance, when it comes to deploying the model, the choice of RF is the most appropriate, not only because of its excellent results, but also because of its speed in terms of decision making. Speed has been a crucial evaluator in the decision to choose RF as the classifier to deploy in the network, as the optimisation of the network rules must be done as fast as possible if optimal performance is to be achieved.

9.7 Conclusion

This chapter presents a new multi-layer and multi-technology framework that enables a novel approach to optimise virtual rule-based firewalls in B5G networks, where different datapath technologies co-exist. The framework is integrated in a multi-tenant B5G network architec-

Fig. 9.10 Feature importance obtained with Random Forest classifier.

ture. The proposed architecture is able to analyse multiple network rules simultaneously, enabling the management layer to swiftly adapt to changing network conditions and improve optimisation without human intervention. Utilising real-time data from network sensors, the framework supports rule balancing across various datapath technology configurations. This results in faster rule-matching times, as rules are continually optimised.

The proposed framework focuses on a supervised ML classifier in order to select the optimal datapath technology for every network rule already enforced in the virtual firewall. The network rules that are being optimised are rules for dropping data packets from DDoS attacks. All this information is compiled in the *IW-IB-5GNET* dataset, processed and discussed in previous chapters.

In order to select the best classifier, a comparative analysis of four ML models (KNN, SVM, RF and XGB) has been carried out. Based on the F1-score, RF outperforms the rest of the classifiers, obtaining a total of 90.83% and, an accuracy of 97.10%. It is followed by XGB, which obtains 88.16%. Furthermore, in terms of training time, both KNN, RF and XGB have very short training times (less than 1 second) compared with SVM (8.7 seconds).

This chapter concludes the aim proposed in Chapter 3. The next chapter will expose the conclusions together with a discussion about the limitations that have been taken into account in the research work presented.

Chapter 10

Conclusions, Limitations and Future Work

This final chapter presents the general conclusions drawn from the whole research process of this PhD thesis. These conclusions bring with them several limitations to be highlighted for each of the steps of the research process. Finally, the chapter concludes with guidelines for future work.

10.1 Conclusions

Traditional mobile network technologies often struggle with limited capacity, higher latency, and reduced flexibility in handling diverse traffic patterns. In contrast, 5G and beyond advancements offer significant improvements in these areas. 5G provides increased capacity, allowing for up to 1000 times more connected devices than 4G networks. This enhanced capacity is particularly beneficial for deploying multiple network control functions simultaneously. Additionally, low latency in 5G enables real-time decision-making and faster response times for network control functions. The increased programmability and flexibility of 5G also allow for more sophisticated control at the datapath level, enabling more efficient datapath technology selection and implementation. All these advancements offered by B5G networks

provide a robust foundation for improving network optimisation strategies, particularly in the context of this research on optimal control function technology selection.

This research work has presented a novel approach for the empowerment of B5G network infrastructures using AI capabilities to perform autonomous decisions in the selection of optimal network control function technologies. This goal has been validated applying the concrete use-case of the network protection against cyber-attacks. The contribution presented in this thesis represents a novel technique in the state of the art of deploying multi-technology and multi-layer virtual firewalls in networks, especially IBNs such as B5G. As it has been verified in the literature review of different chapters, the contribution of this research work represents the first attempt to introduce AI in the autonomous selection of NCF technology for deploying virtual firewalls.

The successful achievement of the thesis' aim has led to the development of the 9 objectives highlighted in Chapter 3. These objectives can be divided into 5 stages: (i) network and tool preparation, (ii) dataset extraction, (iii) data labelling, (iv) data augmentation and, (v) production of the ML model.

The first stage, the network and tool preparation, has consisted in the development and validation of three software components, corresponding to three different innovations (objectives 1, 2 and 3). The first component consists of a network monitoring tool able to extract metrics from multi-technology NCF, which are the datapath technologies. Specifically, these technologies are iptables, TC and OVS. The second network component corresponds to a software that is a data extractor and dataset creator, able to gather multi-domain and intent-based network metrics. This tool is aligned with the intent-based network already present in our laboratory. In terms of performance, IDEM is able to extract all network information in less than 0.5 seconds, regardless of the number of rules inserted in the network. Therefore, it has been demonstrated that IDEM is highly scalable in terms of the number of rules. The third component, a visualising and labelling tool able to present in a dashboard the network information useful for the technology decision. This tool presents all extracted network information and has the possibility to configure the labelling type. This makes it a tool for labelling different use cases. In terms of performance, NetLabeller has been proven

to be very fast in terms of displaying information on the dashboard with respect of the state of the art.

The second stage consisted of the extraction of the dataset (objective 4). This stage has been achieved through the execution of numerous experiments in an autonomous network, subjected to DDoS attacks. The stage has required the full synchronisation of a multitude of software components, including the three explained in the previous paragraph. It has also covered the formalisation of the dataset in a suitable format ready for manipulation. As a result, a total of 64,290 instances and 107 features have been obtained. During this stage, complete labelling of a subset of the data extracted has also been successfully accomplished (objective 5). This task has been complex and required a lot of theoretical understanding of the underlying technologies for adequate labelling. As a result, a comprehensive subset of the data has been obtained in this step, ready for ML application. Particularly, a total of 7708 instances were labelled. This subset of the extracted and labelled data supposes the fourth innovation of the thesis. This novel dataset is the first of its kind, representing the first attempt to optimise network rules using AI.

Objectives 6 and 7 are the results of stage four, data augmentation. These steps have been essential in order to enrich the subset of data obtained in the previous phase, which resulted to have an imbalance in the data classes. To do so, a generative AI conditional tabular data framework has been developed, corresponding to the fifth innovation. Such framework allows the implementation of four different generative models: CTGAN, CopulaGAN, GaussianCopula and TVAE. The framework has been used to obtain the best generative model able to oversample the minority classes of our concrete imbalanced dataset. The selected model corresponds to a CopulaGAN implementation. As a result of this data augmentation process, a total of 9292 new samples have been compiled in the real dataset, allowing for a balanced subset of training data.

Finally, the last stage of the thesis corresponds to obtaining the model for the optimal datapath technology selection. The objectives associated with this stage are 8 and 9. In this stage, the final network architecture including the deployment of the ML model for the optimisation of network rules inserted in the datapath technologies has been proposed. During

this process, a framework for the generation of ML-based classifiers for tabular data has been developed. This framework has allowed the identification of the best classification algorithm for the present use-case. The model selected has been the Random Forest, characterised by its rapid training (0.4 seconds) and easy implementation. This model is able to predict correctly the optimal technology for implementing network policies with an accuracy of 97.10% and presents a F1-score of 90.83%. This model, called the Firewall Optimiser, is the sixth innovation of this research work, being the first attempt in the literature to optimise virtual firewalls using AI.

10.2 Research Limitations

Despite the comprehensive approach and rigorous methodology employed in this research work, several limitations must be acknowledged. One major general limitation and several specific limitations of different phases of the methodology can be highlighted. In general terms, the scope of the presented research work was constrained by the high dependency on the B5G network infrastructure within the research laboratory and all its software components. This led to a reduction in the scope application to a single network control function (the drop action) and the number of datapath technologies used. The nature of this limitation can be understood as a consequence of a number of specific constraints, explained below.

In the implementation and empirical validation phase of the data extraction tool and data labelling tool, two limitations are highlighted. In terms of the data extraction software, the IDEM component, although it allows parameterisation of the metrics to be extracted, the extracted metadata is fixed and cannot be extended with current implementation. This limitation is a consequence of the complexity of the existing data model in the B5G environment network used. Furthermore, the maximum accuracy is 1 second due to the dependency it has with all the network monitoring software components. As for the labelling tool, the most obvious limitation is that the implementation of the current dashboard does not allow for customisation, due to the complexity that its development would have caused in terms of time available. This limitation means that in future AI model enhancements requiring new

data extraction, this dashboard will need to be restructured to support new data fields or remove existing ones.

With regard to the dataset obtained, multiple restrictions can be highlighted. The lab-based experiments that were conducted are limited by several factors. Firstly, at the topology level. The experiments have been performed on 4 different network topologies, which does not represent the full range of real-world topologies. This limitation may result in the model not being able to correctly generalise in different new scenarios. Secondly, our experiments were constrained by the number of datapath technologies due to the lack of available implementations in our testbed. Including more technologies would have helped create a more complex and comprehensive dataset. Furthermore, the current implementation of the cognitive loop does not allow the insertion of rules from different technologies in the same experiment. Thirdly and most importantly, the number of rules inserted into the network was restricted, being a total of 32 rules simultaneously in the best cases. The nature of this limitation is the lack of resources in our laboratory. This has led to the creation of a limited dataset in terms of the number of rules inserted into the network, a determining factor when choosing the optimal technology. To address this limitation, we enriched our dataset with synthetic data. As a result of all these limitations, the final dataset has reduced variability.

The use of synthetic data generation to balance the dataset was a necessary approach to overcome the limitation of insufficient balanced real data. While this technique helped mitigate class imbalance and improved model training, it is important to acknowledge its inherent challenges. Synthetic data, by its nature, lacks ground truth, which can introduce some uncertainty regarding its accuracy in representing real-world scenarios. This absence of authentic verification means that the model's performance may be influenced by data that do not perfectly reflect actual network conditions. Addressing the limitation of generating more balanced real data in the future would largely resolve this challenge.

Finally, limitations are concluded with the implementation and deployment of the ML-based classifier to predict the optimal technology for NCF. As the deployed Random Forest classifier has been trained on a limited dataset with restricted variability, it may face signifi-

cant challenges when encountering new data, primarily due to problems with generalisation. This issue arises because the model has been exposed to only a narrow range of scenarios during training, reducing its ability to accurately predict outcomes for more diverse or unseen data. Additionally, the model's performance is affected by the imbalance of the data, despite being trained on synthetic data. It has been shown that the model is almost perfect in predicting OVS cases, but fails on several occasions when it comes to TC or iptables, the minority classes. This factor is attributed to the fact that the generative model is also better at generating data from OVS than from the minority classes. Future experiments showing new use cases will overcome these limitations, as more real and balanced data will become available to train the models. Better data quality will enhance AI model training and evaluation results.

10.3 Future work

Given all the limitations highlighted in the previous section, future work will focus mainly on the enrichment of the current dataset so that the classification model (RF) can be enhanced. For this purpose, different lines of work are identified.

To enrich the dataset more data is needed. However, such data cannot be obtained with the network we currently have, but several additions have to be introduced. Firstly, the inclusion of new datapath technologies such as XDP or Netronome BPF offloading. The inclusion of these new technologies will bring new principles in relation to technology selection. Secondly, the extension of the cognitive loop control capabilities to new network actions, such as flow prioritisation, bandwidth limitation or bandwidth guarantee. This addition will also enrich the principles in relation to technology selection. Another important addition will be the generation of different network topologies, in addition to the 4 existing ones. This will help to provide a wider spectrum of real-world scenarios, enriching the dataset and leading to better results from the ML classifier. This improvement will also include the variability of the type of traffic sent by users, as well as the type of cyber-attacks. Finally, a crucial aspect will be the study of how to improve the available network resources in order to be able to not only

introduce a larger number of rules in the loop framework but also to increase the bandwidth supported by the emulated network. This will allow the generation of more scenarios in which the OVS datapath is no longer the optimal technology and other technologies can be chosen, thus reducing the data imbalance problem. In order to introduce more rules in datapath technologies, it will be necessary to improve network resources utilisation, specially by the software components that interact with network rules. Furthermore, to increase the supported network bandwidth, the possibility of using the CORE version in distributed mode will be explored. This new version of the framework is being developed by another member of the lab. All these changes will lead to a significant enhancement of the quality of the extracted data. Enriching the dataset will lead to more adequate and generalisable results from the Random Forest classifier. In addition, this dataset enhancement will greatly reduce the crucial dependence on synthetic data to train the model, thus eliminating the uncertainty caused by the generative model.

Additional lines of future work are listed below. Firstly, the performance improvement of the IDEM component to be able to extract data every less time, as it is now limited to 1 second. Secondly, the improvement of the NetLabeller tool so that the dashboard is more customisable by the user. This will enhance network efficiency, since right now it only allows the visualisation of all the network metrics studied in this research work. This would make that the IDEM component only needs to extract the features that are really important for decision making and only represents those in the labelling dashboard. This will also facilitate the use of these tools for other research projects involving the extraction and labelling of network data. Third, the development and implementation of the Network Policy Conflict Solver component, the module in charge of ensuring that there are no conflicts between existing policies and the optimal decision made by the Firewall Optimiser, so that the optimisation loop of the architecture proposed in this research thesis is closed. Finally, to reconsider the name of the ML classifier, which is Firewall Optimiser, as this name was chosen for the use case where it acts as a firewall to remove packets from the network. This decision is motivated by the consideration that the ML model is intended to perform many

more control actions than those performed by a firewall. Therefore, it will be convenient to use a more generic name appropriate to the functionality of this component.

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